

Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean

Report on the stakeholder mapping and water governance for demo sites

VERSION 1.1

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Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work Package
CO	Consortium
PU	Public
R	Report
O	Other
DEM	Demonstrator
PT	Platform
NbS	Nature-based solution
MED	Mediterranean
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
RSS	Remote Sensing Solutions GmbH
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València
IDRICA	Idrica
SEMIDE	Euro-Mediterranean Information System on know-how in the Water sector
TdV	La Tour du Valat
TUC	Technical University of Crete
UNIPR	Università di Parma
UNISS	University of Sassari
UNINA	University of Naples Federico II
RSCN	Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature
LPM	Living Planet Morocco
AGRI	AgroInsider
ESIM	Higher School of Engineering of Medjez El Bab
BU	Boğaziçi University
BMP	Best Management Practices

Executive summary

The overall objective of the "Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean" (OurMED) project is to design and explore innovative and sustainable storage and distribution systems tightly integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale. This is achieved by the combination of scientific and local knowledge, emerging from new and long-lasting spaces for social learning among interdependent stakeholders, society actors and scientific researchers in eight local and one regional MED demo sites. OurMED calls for a transition from a mono-sectoral water management approach based on trade-offs, to equitable multi-sectoral and integrative management that addresses all water bodies' capabilities and needs towards sustainability.

The objective of this document is to assess and understand the present water and ecosystem governance in demo studies. To fulfill this objective, this document contains system characterization of the demo studies, stakeholder mapping and governance analysis. The case studies include Agia (Greece), Arborea (Italy), Bode (Germany), Jucar (Spain), Mujib (Jordan), Sebou (Morocco), Medjerda (Tunisia), Konya (Turkey) and the MED regional scale.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This document is the deliverable number D3.1 of the “Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in the Mediterranean OurMED” Grant Agreement Number 2222 project.

The deliverable provides an assessment of water and ecosystem governance schemes in demo sites: Agia (Greece), Arborea (Italy), Bode (Germany), Jucar (Spain), Mujib (Jordan), Sebou (Morocco), Medjerda (Tunisia), Konya (Turkey) and the MED regional scale.

For each case study, first a social-economic system characterization and the water management issues are presented. The stakeholders in water governance are identified and mapped. Water governance in each case study is separately explored and assessed.

This deliverable summarizes the initial stage of the research to be completed within WP3 of the project.

1.2 Demo sites

The main characteristics of the eight demo sites are summarized in Table 1. The demo sites show diverse differences in size, population, and location (inland/coastal) of the groundwater basins. The basin sizes range from 250 to 50,000 km² and the population from 7,000 to 6,200,000 people. The climatic properties are also different with various key problems and unique features (Table 1).

Table 1 Summary of demo-sites.

Demo site	Size (km ²), location	Pop.	Climate ^a	Unique feature	Key problems
Agia, Crete Greece	250, Island, North MED	0.07	Mild temperate, dry summer	Important for flora and fauna	Seawater intrusion
Arborea, Italy	854, Island, North MED	0.07	Mild temperate, dry summer	10 areas for conservation, 3 Ramsar sites	Water distribution, pollution and energy
Bode, Germany	3300, Inland, North MED	0.37	Mild temperate and dry winter	Drinking water reservoir, droughts, deforestation	Water quantity, quality deterioration
Jucar, Spain	22200, Coastal, West MED	1.0	Mild temperate, dry summer	Albufera Natural Park, Ramsar	Sedimentation, Eutrophication
Konya, Turkey	50000, Inland, East MED	3.2	Mild temperate, dry summer	Restoration of dry wetlands	Overexploitation
Medjerda, Tunisia	23700, Coastal, South MED	2.2	Mild temperate, dry summer	Transboundary, 2 Ramsar sites, 1 Ramsar City	Sedimentation and water distribution
Mujib, Jordan	6600, Inland, East MED	0.56	Dry and desert	Key Biodiversity for the Dead Sea	Water quality and distribution
Sebou, Morocco	40000, Coastal, South MED	6.2	Mild temperate, dry summer	39 wetlands, 7 Ramsar sites, 2 National parks	Water distribution, biodiversity
MED regional	2 Million, diverse landscape	480	MED climate	Biodiversity hotspot worldwide	Water scarcity, climate change

1.3 Methodology

Stakeholder analysis is a crucial component of understanding the complex social and political dynamics in our case studies. It helps identify and understand the individuals, groups, or entities that can affect or be affected by a particular project or policy decision.

Desktop work (literature review, analysis of local news outlets) was integrated with fieldwork (interviews, focus group discussions).

OurMED comprehensive stakeholder analysis involved three key sub-components:

- System characterization involves gaining a thorough understanding of the system or project under consideration. It included identifying the boundaries of the system (e.g. the boundaries of the demo site basin, a particular part of the demo site, a sub-basin, a specific town, etc.), its objectives, key processes, and the environment in which it operates.
- Stakeholder mapping involves the identification and analysis of individuals, groups, or organizations that have an interest in (i.e. the stakeholders) or can influence (i.e. the actors) the outcome of the project. A comprehensive list of groups, organizations, and individuals connected to water management within each demo site was compiled. After that, stakeholders were classified based on their status (public, private, civil society), role (Table 2), capital (human, economic, social) (Table 3; Figure 1), and interest and influence (Figure 2).
- Governance analysis focuses on understanding the formal and informal structures that guide decision-making, accountability, and communication within the system. It involved assessing the roles, responsibilities, and relationships among key actors. The governance analysis included two sub-components: (i) understanding decision-making processes and (ii) reviewing policy and regulatory frameworks.

There are a number of ways to demonstrate stakeholder mapping. Examples are provided below.

Table 2 CATWOE classification.¹

Actor	People/groups who are involved in the situation and who will take part in the solution. They perform a certain function within a system or process.
Owner	People/groups who have the power to control the system and decide whether it will be implemented or not (e.g. the funders of a development project, the head of a public agency deciding not to make available data...).
Customer	Target of a product/service, end-users and those who are impacted by the decisions of owners and actors (e.g. consumers, water users, farmers, tourists). Many customers are marginalized stakeholders (e.g. children, elderly people, women) and should be regarded with special attention when aiming at sustainability.

¹ <https://www.designorate.com/catwoe-problem-solving/>

Figure 1 Example of CATWOE Analysis.

Figure 2 Example of stakeholder analysis diagram.

Table 3 Classification of stakeholders based on their stock of resources.

SOCIAL CAPITAL	ECONOMIC CAPITAL	HUMAN CAPITAL
Capacity to involve other actors	Capacity to contribute as a sponsor	Appropriate knowledge/skills suitable in the program
Representativeness of a specific category	Influence on resources' allocation	Awareness and propensity to change
Engagement in local communities	Capacity to access to exogenous resources	Capacity to engage in public debate
Capacity to activate social change	Capacity to provide in-kind support	Communication skills in different media
Acknowledgment among local institutions and citizens	Influence on the job market	Good access to public venues

Figure 3 Example of classification of stakeholders based on their stock of resources.

Another possible classification is through mapping the stakeholder and actors into a matrix where we highlight the scale of governance (national, regional, and local) and also the actors as state, market, and civil society (Table 4).

Table 4 Stakeholders classification based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local).

	STATE	MARKET	CIVIL
NATIONAL			
REGIONAL / BASIN SCALE			
LOCAL / SUB-BASIN SCALE			

Power and interest analysis plots stakeholders on a power-interest grid and visualizing their level of influence and interests helps prioritise efforts to engage and communicate with stakeholders effectively.

2 Agia, Greece

2.1 System Characterization

This section provides an overview of the Agia region, focusing on its geographic setting, demographic trends, and water resource management challenges.

The Agia region is situated 3.5 km west of Chania city, nestled in the central part of the Keritis River drainage basin in Crete. The Keritis River in Crete has different biophysical attributes that are characterised by its hydrological properties, which are influenced by the prevailing sub-humid Mediterranean climate. The seasonal variations in precipitation, which are mainly concentrated in the winter months, have a significant impact on the river's discharge dynamics and water availability. The geological formations, especially the Trypali carbonate rocks, play a crucial role as they facilitate groundwater recharge and influence the hydrology of the river. In addition, the proposed water infrastructure projects in the catchment area aim to increase water storage capacity and reduce erosion, underlining efforts to sustainably manage water resources. Furthermore, the designation of protected areas in the river basin plays an important role in protecting biodiversity and maintaining the ecological integrity of the surrounding landscape. Taken together, these factors contribute to the complex interplay of environmental factors that shape the biophysical attributes of the Keritis River.

Covering an area of approximately 210 km², the region is characterized by a relatively gentle topography. According to the 2011 census, the wider municipal unit encompassing Agia has a population of around 8,596 residents. However, this number significantly increases during the summer months due to the influx of tourists, which exerts additional pressure on the region's water resources.

The climate of the study area is sub-humid Mediterranean with humid and relatively cold winters and dry and warm summers. During winter which starts in November, the weather is unstable due to frequent changes from low to high pressures. The annual rainfall for the broader Chania area has been estimated to be 665 mm (Chartzoulakis et al., 2001). The precipitation in Agia is estimated at 855 mm. About 65% of the annual precipitation is lost due to evapotranspiration, 21% as runoff to sea and only 14% recharges the groundwater (Chartzoulakis et al., 2001). The rainfall is mainly concentrated in the winter months while the drought period extends to more than 6 months (May–October). The monthly evaporation ranges from 140 mm to more than 310 mm in the peak month. As a result, water resource availability is limited due to the spatio-temporal variations of precipitation (Tsagarakis et al., 2004).

In the study area, designated regions form part of the Natura 2000 Network, which serves as a comprehensive European Ecological Network. This network encompasses areas hosting natural habitat types and species of significant importance at the European level. Structurally, the Natura 2000 Network is organized into two distinct categories of areas:

- "Special Protection Areas (SPAs)" for birds, as defined in Directive 79/409/EEC "on the conservation of wild birds".

- "Sites of Community Importance (SCIs)" as defined in Directive 92/43/EEC. SCIs are designated considering habitat types and species listed in Annexes I and II of Directive 92/43/EEC as well as the criteria of Annex III of this Directive.

The regions forming part of the Natura 2000 Network, in the watershed, include Lake Agia with code GR4340020, Lake Agia - Platanias - Keritis River & Fasa Valley with code GR4340006 and Therisso Gorge with code GR4340007. These areas have been selected for protection due to the presence of significant natural habitat types and species crucial for the conservation of biodiversity at the European level. The protection of these areas is important for maintaining ecosystems and safeguarding species dependent on them. The National Park of Samaria with the code GR4340014 and the White Mountains & Coastal Zone with the code GR4340008 are also included in the Natura areas.

2.1.1 Main issues

Water allocation and rational water resources management in the area is vital since the demand from both the tourist and agricultural sectors is highly increasing. Water is also distributed across the domestic consumption sector, for households and local communities' water requirements and the industrial sector, which includes olive processing industries in the region, using significant water amounts during the olive oil production process. The Keritis-Therissos basin, known for its copious water reserves, plays a pivotal role in meeting the aforementioned irrigation and domestic water requirements of a substantial area within the Chania Prefecture. Most of the water comes from the karst aquifer of Agia, which is the main source of water in the area. Water is extracted from the Platanos, Kolympa and Kalamionas springs as well as from pumping wells, located 2 km south of the Agia springs and supervised by the Municipal Enterprise for Drinking Water Distribution and Sewerage Management of Chania (DEYACH), the Organization for the Development of Crete (OAK) and the Local Organization of Land Reclamation (TOEV). The pumping wells are mainly operated from May to November each year extracting about 14 Mm³ of water. The rational management of the aforementioned water sources is crucial for the water resources sustainability in the area. Although there is plenty of groundwater of good quality for the time being, a serious issue in the area is the multiplicity of water management agencies when allocating water to the different sectors trying to efficiently meet their existing needs. In addition, the severe understaffing and fragmentation of the public agencies complicate the systematic data collection and water resources monitoring by the existing water management bodies. There is a significant lack of accurate water consumption data both for the touristic and agricultural sectors, which causes difficulties in studying the groundwater system with numerical models and scientific tools. There are uncontrolled high-water abstractions from too many private wells, which create a non-socially fair way of water distribution in the area. It is important for the citizens to feel confident in the existence of a fair water distribution process.

It is also notable that the water management strategy initiative in the area includes the management of the Agia Lake, a small water body of approximately 0.2 km² and an average depth of 4 m. Originally a marshland, it was converted into a reservoir as part of the Comprehensive Water Management Plan for Crete to enable the construction of a hydroelectric power plant. Although the power plant operation was later discontinued,

the lake has evolved into a natural reservoir characterized by a remarkable bird population, diverse ecosystems and its designation as a Natura 2000 site. Human activities, in particular the excessive abstraction of irrigation water below the ecological regeneration threshold during low rainfall periods, have led to environmental issues of the Agia Lake ecosystem, i.e., eutrophication and water quality deterioration. The management of Lake Agia must comply with the environmental conditions approved by the Ministerial Decision EPO 125585/24.1.2007. This legal framework provides for a number of measures essential for the management of the lake to ensure the preservation of Agia Lake ecological integrity and the sustainable utilization of its resources.

Nevertheless, threats such as climate change impacts will further threaten the region's water security and sustainability. The need for comprehensive water management strategies necessitates. The active community engagement and government support will enhance the region's resilience. Opportunities will also arise from an appropriate legislative framework, and implementation of directives and policies which promote the rational and fair management of water resources, ensuring equitable distribution, sustainable use, and protection of water quality, balancing the needs of all stakeholders while preserving the ecosystem.

2.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder mapping involves the identification and understanding of the interests, influences, and relationships of several parties involved in an area, ensuring effective communication and collaboration. In the Agia demo site, desktop analysis and literature review provided data both for Agia system characterization and stakeholder mapping. Fieldwork, i.e. interviews and focus group discussions are also being organized and are still in the process of execution. Interviews and focus groups will be taking place throughout the whole duration of the OurMED project. In addition, the 1st Living Lab was organized in the Agia study area involving nearly 46 participants in the process of the significant issues' identification in the area and generally stakeholder mapping. All the aforementioned processes contributed to the creation of a comprehensive list of groups, organizations, and individuals connected to water management within the Agia demo site. The list was compiled properly, and stakeholders were classified based on their status, role, capital, interest and influence. Table 5 contains all the aforementioned information for the most significant stakeholders in the Agia demo site identified till today, however, the list is dynamic and it will be updated throughout the whole project duration.

Table 5 Stakeholder mapping in Agia demo site.

Case study focus	Stakeholder description	Stakeholder group	Scale	Status	Sphere of activity	Issue in relation to water	Actual influence
Water Management	Directorate of Water	Decentralized Administration of Crete	Regional	Public	Admin	Water Management; Water use regulator;	Water protection and management (quantity and quality);
Water Management, Pollution reduction	Regional authority	Region of Crete Directorate of Technical Infrastructure)	Regional	Public	Admin	Water quality, Water Management	Key stakeholder for water quality control/management
Drinking and Irrigation water supply	Governmental Organization, supervised by the Greek Ministry of Infrastructure	Organization for the Development of Crete	Regional	Public	Drinking water provision (uptake; distribution)	Drinking water allocation	A key stakeholder for irrigation water allocation
Sewerage networks and wastewater treatment plants	Water supply, treatment and distribution association; wastewater collection and treatment	Municipal Enterprise for Drinking Water Distribution and Sewage	Local	Public	Drinking water provision	Management of water supply and sewerage networks;	Ability to guarantee water distribution and proper water quality
Water allocation planning among different sectors	Local authority	Platanias and Chania Municipalities	Local	Public	Admin	Planning balanced use of water among the different sectors	Water supply management among sectors; Public awareness
Water resources management	Scientist Society, Scientists from academic institutions - University (e.g. Technical University of Crete)	Researchers	National	Public	Expanding and promoting scientific knowledge in landscape architecture	Exploitation of water resources to guide the landscape development in the study area	Ability to influence policy and practice through scientific evidence
Drinking water quality; Water resources availability; Quality of Life	Civil Society	Cultural Association of Agia	Local	Civil society	Human consumption; Hygienic services; Life quality	Drinking water availability and water availability for irrigation; Drinking water quality; Wastewater management	Ability to influence consumption behavior by increasing public awareness

Water user	Citizens	End users of water for civil uses	Local	Civil society	Human consumption; Hygienic services; Life quality	Drinking water availability; Drinking water quality;	Ability to influence through consumption behaviour
Water user; groundwater pollution reduction	Farmers	Farmers	Local	Private	Farming	Groundwater availability for irrigation; Water quality; Water pricing; Pollution reduction	Ability to influence through consumption behaviour;
Irrigation water supply	Legal entities of private law	Local Organizations of Land Reclamation	Local	Public	Irrigation water provision	Irrigational water allocation associations	A key stakeholder for irrigation water allocation
Groundwater quality and quantity status/ Water allocation	Geologists, Retired/Region of Crete	Experts/ Geologists	Local	Private	Geology of the study area, Water resources management	Provide assistance related to geological and water resources management issues	Work experience regarding the geological system and water resources management
Agro-food, agricultural production means, methods and supplies	The Company operates as an Anonymous Development Company of a Local Self-	Regional Developmental Company of Crete S.A. - PANETEK S.A.	Local	Public	Project Management Public Company	Public awareness, promotion on sustainable agro-food	Public awareness;
Artificial Lake of Agia	Museum for the utilization of water resources and renewable energy sources in the study area	Museum of Small Hydro-power Plant of Agia	Local	Public	Gallery for STEAM and robotics for students	Education regarding utilization of water resources and renewable energy	Public awareness; education and
Protection management of the natural environment of the Agia Lake (Natura 2000 area)	Supervised by the Ministry of Environment and Energy,	Management Unit of Samaria National Park and Western Crete Protected Areas	Local	Public	Implement the environmental policies and educational programs	Lake's ecosystems and maintain biodiversity.	Authority to implement conservation policies,
Ecosystem preservation	Environmental NGO	WWF Hellas	National	Civil society	Advocacy; Consciousness-raising	Climate change impacts;	Ability to influence policy and practice; consumption behaviour by increasing public awareness
Water user; groundwater pollution reduction	Tourism Operators	Tourism Operators	Local	Private	Tourism	Local	Ability to influence groundwater quantity through consumption behaviour

Moreover, Agia demo site's stakeholders were classified based on their status (Public, Private, Civil society) and role (Actor, Owner, Customer) using the CATWOE classification analysis (Figure 4). CATWOE analysis within the Agia demo site showed that most of the stakeholders are at the local level, however there are also stakeholders at the national level i.e., Ministry of the Environment and Energy, Ministry of Rural Development and Food, researchers etc. Owner stakeholders are mainly public local institutions i.e., the Decentralized Administration of Crete and the Region of Crete, who are key stakeholders for water management and pollution control in the Agia region, implementing policies, infrastructure development and local governance. The Organization for the Development of Crete (O.A.K. S.A.) can be categorized as both a local and national stakeholder. It focuses on the development and management of projects within the region of Crete, addressing local needs and priorities as a local stakeholder. Nevertheless, it operates under the broader framework of national policies and strategies, contributing to the overall development goals of Greece, under the umbrella of the Greek Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport as a national stakeholder. Same happens for NGO (WWF) which operate as both a national and local stakeholder in various environmental projects, including the Agia demo site in Chania, Crete. At the national level, WWF Greece works on broader environmental policies, advocacy, and conservation programs. Locally, WWF Greece engages with the local community, local authorities, and other stakeholders to address conservation and sustainability issues, promote biodiversity, and implement solutions tailored to the local context. The Cultural Association of Agia forms also a local civil society stakeholder capable of mobilizing community and developing local initiatives.

Private local stakeholders are tourism operators and agricultural businesses or farmers. On the one hand tourism operators provide high-quality services, ensure customer satisfaction, and contribute to the local economic growth of the tourism industry, employment creation while adhering to regulatory and ethical standards. On the other hand, agricultural businesses or farmers apply sustainable land management practices, ensure food safety and quality, maintain ecological balance, and contribute to local and global food supply chains while considering environmental and social impacts. Individual experts (i.e. geologists) are also private local stakeholders who contribute with their experience, expertise and knowledge in optimal water resources management. The academia site (i.e. researchers) also contributes through research, development and educational programs however at the national level and at the public status. Figure 4 also shows that most of the stakeholders have a positive role in relation to the OurMED project (i.e. followers and/or supporters).

Figure 4 Water governance stakeholder map of Agia demo site (Crete).

Furthermore, in order to understand stakeholders' influence and role in local initiatives, they were classified according to their capital (human, economic, social) given the guidelines of Table 3 in the Methodology section (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Agia demo site stakeholders' classification based on their stock of resources.

Moreover, a grid plot was used (Figure 6) to visualize the classification of Agia demo site's stakeholders based on their interests and influence. This plot helped to prioritize efforts to engage and communicate with stakeholders effectively.

Figure 6 Stakeholder grid based on power/interest in Agia, Greece.

Lastly, the Agia demo site’s stakeholders and actors were mapped into a matrix which highlights the scale of governance (national, regional, and local) and their contributions to society (state, market, and civil) (Table 6).

Table 6 Stakeholders’ classification based on their scale of governance (national, regional, local) and their contribution (state, market, civil) in Agia, Greece.

	<u>STATE</u>	<u>MARKET</u>	<u>CIVIL</u>
<u>NATIONAL</u>	Ministry of Environment and Energy	-	WWF Greece
	Ministry of Rural Development and Food	-	
<u>REGIONAL / BASIN SCALE</u>	Region of Crete	Regional Developmental Company of Crete S.A. - PANETEK S.A.	-
	Decentralized Administration of Crete	-	-
	Organization for the Development of Crete (supervised by Greek Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport)	-	-

<u>LOCAL / SUB-BASIN SCALE</u>	<i>Municipality of Chania</i>	<i>Tourism and Hospitality Operators</i>	<i>Educational and Research Institution Scientist society - Researchers from Technical University of Crete (Chania)</i>
	<i>Municipality of Platanias</i>	<i>Agricultural Businesses</i>	<i>Individual experts (i.e. geologists)</i>
	<i>Local Organizations of Land Reclamation (supervised by Region of Crete)</i>	-	<i>Individual Farmers and Farmers Associations</i>
	<i>Municipal Enterprise for Drinking Water Distribution and Sewerage Management of Chania</i>	-	<i>Cultural Association of Agia</i>
	<i>Municipal Enterprise for Drinking Water Distribution and Sewerage Management of Platanias</i>	-	<i>End users of water for civil use</i>
	<i>Management Unit of Samaria National Park and Western Crete Protected Areas (supervised by Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency)</i>	-	<i>Museum of Small Hydropower Plant of Agia</i>

2.2.1 State Actors

In Agia demo site (Greece) the state actors as stakeholders include various government bodies and public organizations at the national, regional, and local levels. These actors play crucial roles in governance, policy implementation, and public service delivery. Their collaboration and coordination are vital for effective governance, public service delivery, and the implementation of policies that benefit the local community and environment. State actors at the national level are:

- The Ministry of Environment and Energy, which regulates environmental protection measures, oversees energy projects, and ensures sustainable resource management
- The Ministry of Rural Development and Food, which provides support and funding for agricultural practices, ensures food safety and quality and promotes rural development

At the regional level:

- The Region of Crete, which implements national policies at the regional level, coordinates regional development projects and is responsible for regional planning and development, environmental management, economic development and infrastructure projects
- The Decentralized Administration of Crete oversees regional development initiatives, implements government policies at the local level, manages regional resources and infrastructure, fosters economic growth and addresses the needs of the local population while ensuring adherence to national laws and regulations.
- The Organization for the Development of Crete (supervised by the Greek Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport), which coordinates and implements development initiatives aimed at fostering economic growth, sustainable development, and social progress within the Crete region. This includes formulating and executing regional development plans, promoting investment opportunities, improving infrastructure and public services, enhancing environmental sustainability, and addressing the needs and aspirations of the local community.

At the local level:

- The Municipalities of Chania and Platanias which provide public services, manage local infrastructure, oversee urban planning, and engage with the community.
- The Local Organizations of Land Reclamation
- The Municipal Enterprises for Drinking Water Distribution and Sewerage Management of Chania and Platanias
- The Management Unit of Samaria National Park and Western Crete Protected Areas (supervised by Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency), which enforces environmental regulations, oversees conservation efforts, manages visitor activities, and protects biodiversity.

2.2.2 Market Actors

Market actors in Agia demo site are diverse and include a variety of private sector entities, local businesses and regional companies that contribute to the local economy through services, investment, and employment opportunities. These stakeholders are vital for the economic development of the area since their activities help drive the local economy and support the community's overall prosperity.

Market actors at the regional level are:

- Regional Development Company of Crete S.A. - PANETEK S.A. which enhances and promotes regional economic development and investments and supports local businesses. In addition, it facilitates economic growth through development projects and works on various economic initiatives to enhance the economic growth and competitiveness of Crete and improve the local economy.

Market actors at the local level are:

- Tourism and Hospitality Operators who enhance local tourism, provide accommodation and hospitality services contributing to the local economy through tourism revenue.
- Agricultural Businesses like agricultural cooperatives, who support and promote agricultural production and marketing, ensure sustainable farming practices, maintain high standards of food safety and quality etc.

2.2.3 Civil Actors

Civil actors in Agia demo site (Greece) include a variety of organizations and individuals from civil society who contribute crucially to the socio-cultural and environmental well-being of the community. Their activities and initiatives contribute significantly to the well-being and development of the local community, complementing the efforts of state and market actors. At the national scale they are:

- Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and especially the environmental NGO, WWF Greece, which advocates for environmental protection and conservation, protects local ecosystems and raises public awareness.

At the local scale:

- Community groups or associations, individual farmers or farmers associations, who represent and promote the interests of local farmers by providing support to farmers and promote sustainable farming practices
- The Cultural Association of Agia, which preserves and promotes local culture by organizing events and promoting traditional events.
- The educational and research institutions such as the Technical University of Crete, which conducts research within projects, offers education to students on various topics regarding environmental sustainability and development and collaborates well with local stakeholders in several initiatives.

2.3 Governance Analysis

In Greece, many different authorities are involved in water governance, concerning its different aspects (i.e. roles, responsibilities, and relationships among key actors) and the level at which they are responsible. In the following section, it is attempted to delineate the involved authorities based on their level of governance: national, regional, and local, in terms of policy and regulatory framework and of decision-making structure and processes.

The water governance system has a **centralized** structure for what concerns river basin management plans and water use permits, while it maintains a **decentralized** structure when it comes to local water management and resource allocation. More specifically, according to Law 3199/2003 (GG, 2003) for Water Protection and Management, which harmonizes the National Law with the provisions of the EU WFD, 2000/60/EC Directive, the following responsible authorities for water protection and management are defined:

- The **National Water Commission** has been designated as the high-level inter-ministerial body, which is responsible for formulating the water resources management and protection policy in the country scale.
- The **National Water Council**, advises the National Water Commission on the national programs for the water protection and management on the country water potential scale, while it takes note of the Annual report submitted by the National Water Commission, on the state of the country's aquatic environment, the implementation of water protection and management legislation. It consists of 26 members (representatives of parties and organizations) and the President, the Minister of Environment and Energy. The National Water Council is convened by its President at least once a year.
- The **Special Secretariat for Water** has the responsibility of programs' preparation regarding the protection and management of the country's water resources and the

coordination of services and government agencies for any issue related to water protection and management. The Secretariat, in collaboration with the Directorates of Water of the Decentralized Administrations, prepares the national programs for the protection and management of the country's water resources and monitors and coordinates their implementation.

The following authorities hold the responsibility at the regional level.

The **Decentralized Water Council**, consists of the Coordinator of the Decentralized Administration, the Directorate of Water manager, representatives from the involved Regions and Regional Entities, representatives from the involved Municipalities and Municipal Companies of Water Distribution and Sewerage (DEYA), representatives from the local chambers (technical, geotechnical, commercial and industrial), a representative from the agricultural association, a representative from the Local Organization of Land Reclamation, a representative from environmental NGOs and a representative from the Management Body of Protected Areas. The Decentralized Water Council is a social dialogue and consultation body on water protection and management issues. When the River Basin Management Plan of an aquatic compartment is prepared by the respective Decentralized Administration, the Decentralized Water Council shall give its opinion before the approval of the Management Plan and expresses its opinion to the General Secretary of the Decentralized Administrators according to article 28 of Law 4325/2015 (Government Gazette 47/A/2015) for every submitted water protection and management issue. In addition, the Decentralized Water Council, before giving an opinion on the Management Plan, shall publish it, in order to achieve public awareness on its content as well as public participation in the consultation process, within a deadline set by the Decentralized Water Council.

The **Directorates of Water** of the **Decentralized Administration** apply the responsibilities of the Decentralized Administration for water protection and management and exercises the responsibilities assigned to the Decentralized Administration in accordance with current water resources legislation. The Decentralized Administration of Crete issues the permits for water use to any other authorities and individual users. Specifically, in Crete, the Decentralized Administration of Crete, is responsible for the River Basin Management Plans of the aquatic compartment of Crete (Figure 7). In addition, the **Region of Crete** has the responsibility for the implementation of the policies in general, the control/monitoring of water quality through the Department of Hydroeconomics and the control of environmental pollution of water through the Department of Environment and Hydroeconomics of the regional entities. It also has an advisory/consultative role to the Decentralized Administration with its work.

Finally, for issues regarding the implementation of Directive 2000/60/EC, Local Authorities of 1st and 2nd degree are involved at the Regional Level.

According to the "New Architecture of Local Government and Decentralized Administration - Kallikratis Program" Law 3852/2010 (Government Gazette 87/A/2010), the responsibilities defined by Law 3119/2003 (Government Gazette 280/A/2003) on the protection and management of water resources are divided between the State Administration and the elected Regions. The State Administration (the Ministry of Environment and Energy and the Decentralized Administration) is responsible for the formulation of the strategic protection and management, whereas the elected Regions

are mainly responsible for the implementation of the strategic planning. More specifically, the responsibility for determining the water protection measures is applied by the Decentralized Administration. On the other hand, the elected Regional Authorities and the Municipalities are responsible for the control of compliance with the water protection measures, the control of the surface and groundwater management for irrigation purposes, the control of the tasks' execution for groundwater detection and water resources development projects, and the point and diffuse emissions' controlling on water resources (Figure 8).

Regarding the responsible authorities for water quality, they are categorized as of 1st, 2nd and 3rd degree of responsibility following the provisions of Articles 11(a) and 9 of C3α/761/68 of the Sanitary Layout, as amended (Governance Gazette 189/68B, 988/74B). These authorities:

- **The responsible authorities for water supply** (1st degree of responsibility)
 - o For the water supply of Municipalities, the responsible authority for water quality monitoring is the network operator authority (i.e., Municipalities, Municipal Companies of Water Distribution and Sewerage (D.E.Y.A.), Municipal Associations etc.)
 - o For industries, companies, and institutions with private water supply, the responsible authority is their legal representatives.
 - o For private water supply, the responsible authority is the operator of the water supply network (owner or nominee of the water supply system).
- **Environmental Hygiene and Sanitary Services of the Regional Units** (2nd degree of responsibility). They do not replace the Water Supply Manager (Municipality etc.), however they cooperate with them in order to ensure the continuous and uninterrupted supply of healthy and safe drinking water, the quality of which meets the requirements of the legislation.
- **Ministry of Health** (3rd degree of responsibility). Specifically, the Directorate of Public Health (Department of Environmental Health Management) collects water quality data for human consumption by the responsible authorities and after their evaluation sends the required data to the European Commission to provide information and notification. The Ministry of Health prepares guidelines to the responsible authorities in order to fulfil their obligations.

Last, some of the main water users and distributors are the Municipal Companies of Water Distribution and Sewerage (DEYA) which are responsible for providing drinking water and sewage services to households and other users (e.g. hotels) and their activities are under the supervision of the respective Municipality.

The following Figures 7 and 8 show the Connection between the national and regional water authorities in Greece and the Water Governance System in Crete, respectively.

Figure 7 Connection among the national and regional water authorities in Greece.

Figure 8 Water Governance System in Crete.

2.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

Water governance in Crete, as part of Greece, is shaped by a combination of European Union directives, national legislation, and regional measures and policies. The key elements of the policy and regulatory framework regarding water governance at the EU Level are the:

- *EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) (EU WFD, 2000)* aims at good qualitative and quantitative status of all surface, ground and coastal waters by 2027. In addition,

- it requires from EU Member States to develop and implement River Basin Management Plans to achieve environmental objectives.
- *EU Drinking Water Directive* (EU DWD, 1998) aims at setting standards for the drinking water quality to protect human health as well as monitoring and reporting drinking water quality.
 - *EU Bathing Water Directive* (EU BWD, 2006) establishes standards and improves the quality of bathing waters and protects public health.
 - At the National Level (Greece) the water governance policy and regulatory framework includes the:
 - *Greek Water Law* (GWL, 2003), which translates the EU WFD (2000/60/EU) into national law and establishes the legal framework for the protection and sustainable management of water resources in Greece.
 - *Presidential Decree* (PC, 2007), which specifies the measures for the water resources protection and management aligned with EU WFD.
 - *National Strategy for Water Resources Management* which sets national guidelines for sustainable water management regarding water resources protection and conservation.
 - At the Regional Level (Crete) the policy and regulatory framework includes:
 - The responsibilities and actions of the *Regional Directorate of Water of Crete*, which is responsible for the implementation of water policies at the regional level as well as for the development and the implementation of the *River Basin Management Plan for Crete*. Specifically, the *River Basin Management Plan for Crete* (RBMP, 2017) forms a detailed plan for the water bodies status in Crete regarding pressures, impacts and measures to achieve the objectives of the EU WFD along with public consultation and stakeholder engagement.
 - *Several regional measures* to address water management challenges in Crete (i.e. water scarcity, climate and energy crisis, coastal waters protection, maintenance of groundwater quality etc.)

2.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

The decision-making structure and process regarding water governance in Crete involves multi-layered governance levels involving EU, national, and regional authorities. At the European Union level, decision making is carried out by the European Commission, which develops and enforces water-related directives and regulations as well as the European Environment Agency, which provides data and advice on the state of water resources in Europe. At the National Level (Greece) decision making processes are effectuated by the specialized department within the Ministry of Environment and Energy, the Special Secretariat for Water, which focuses on water resources management, national water policy and strategy development and coordination with regional authorities. It is notable that the Ministry of Environment and Energy is the primary body responsible for the development of national water policy, environmental protection, and the implementation of EU directives. Specifically, in the Aquatic compartment of Crete, the water services are provided by four basic categories of water providers/authorities that act as water managers for the area of their responsibility. Their decisions are based on the regulatory framework of the national law and the internal rules of each organization (RBMP, 2017). The key components at the Regional Level (Crete) are: the Decentralized Administration of Crete, which owns significant autonomy regarding administrative

processes as well as the responsibility to implement national water policies at the regional level. Specifically, the Regional Water Directorate of the Decentralized Administration of Crete, owns the responsibilities of managing water resources, monitoring water quality, as well as ensuring compliance with regulations. The aforementioned regional authority prepares and implements the River Basin Management Plans based on national guidelines and local conditions. These Plans are being subject to public consultation (stakeholders including citizens, businesses and environmental groups) to provide feedback on water management plans and policies and continuously they must be approved by the Ministry of Environment and Energy.

At the Local Level (Agia), the decisions are typically made through consultations and meetings that ensure the participation of stakeholders to address local needs, prioritize and allocate effectively water resources and promote sustainable development and efficient resource management in the study area. The key decision-making institutions are: the *Municipalities* (of Chania and Platanias), which manage local water supply and sanitation services, maintaining infrastructure, monitoring water quantity and quality, enforcing regulations at the local level, implementing projects and initiatives to enhance water resources and reduce pollution. In addition, *the Local Water Supply and Sewerage Companies (DEYA)* (of Chania and North Axis, DEYAX and DEABA, respectively), which are public utilities responsible for the provision of clean drinking water and effective wastewater treatment services to the end users, have also a significant role. Furthermore, the *Organization for the Development of Crete (O.A.K. S.A.)* is the main irrigation water provider either to individuals or to other water distribution organizations using its own irrigation network, taking part in water-related issues in the local area of the demo site. Especially for the irrigation management and drainage systems in agricultural land, the *Local Organizations of Land Reclamation (TOEV)* in Crete play a significant role in decision-making. The TOEVs are legal non-profit entities of private law supervised by the Region of Crete and are responsible for providing irrigation water to end users such as individual farmers or farmers associations. They also control the operation and maintenance of irrigation and drainage infrastructure for water distribution and drainage management for infrastructure development compliance with regulations and generally they ensure efficient water use, improve agricultural productivity and sustainable management of water resources and engage local communities in water governance. TOEV ensure the implementation of water-saving technologies and drainage and irrigation practices to protect soil and water quality and ensure the overall water management and environmental sustainability. Specifically, 8 TOEVs are active in the area (TOEV of Tavronitis, TOEV of Alikianos, TOEV of Agia Marina and Platanias, TOEV of Vatolakos, TOEV of Fournes, TOEV of Meskla, TOEV of Koufos and TOEV of Varypetro).

2.3.3 Analysis

The policy and regulatory framework for water governance in Agia case study, in Crete, integrates EU directives, national laws, and regional measures, aiming to ensure sustainable water resources management, water quality protection and active participation of stakeholders in water management processes. The key components of water governance in the Cretan case study are:

- Water resources use and allocation as well as the accurate definition of the permits for water abstraction and discharge
- Water quality regular monitoring and data reporting to the public and to the European Commission
- Water infrastructure development and maintenance (i.e. water supply systems, wastewater treatment plants etc.)
- Pollution control from point and diffuse sources as well as implementation of best practices to prevent and/or control pollution
- Public participation and awareness and stakeholder engagement in decision making processes related to water resources management

Despite the above, the main issue in the demo site remains the multi-layered governance levels which finally cause polyphony conditions. There are too many and different water resource management agencies involved in the area, which leads to a multiplicity of management agencies. Their interests are often different, so are priorities (farms, hotels, etc.). Sometimes there is also a lack of willingness to cooperate with each other or even competition between the management bodies. The creation of a unified water resources management body for Crete, according to the plan of the Ministry of Rural Development, based on an integrated management plan, the good collaboration of the involved water management bodies of the area for the optimal utilization of the water potential of Agia as well as the creation of an integrated information network – lobbying could make a significant contribution to the consolidation of the existing situation. However, some stakeholders doubt the creation of the unified water resources management body, as the water management plan governing its operation is being designed by a foreign company. This makes the stakeholders skeptical on whether this company could understand the needs of their area.

Another significant issue is the severe understaffing and fragmentation of the public agencies in conditions of heavy bureaucracy which leaves no time for field visits. There is a lack of human resources to organize systematic data collection, monitoring of the water resources systems and check for the data accuracy in the existing water management bodies. There is significant lack of adequate and accurate water consumption data and actually the absence of real data both for the touristic and agriculture sectors. Water management bodies need to be reinforced with new personnel properly trained by the old employees to collect and evaluate the data correctly.

Moreover, the water distribution network and infrastructure in the demo site are outdated or of poor quality. There are many leaks and losses both in drinking and irrigation water along the network and too much water is lost. After all, the hydro-irrigation system is mixed and it is difficult to separate it. The improvement and maintenance of the network form a necessity in the area.

Lastly, there is high consumption of irrigation water in the area, there are too many private wells and the abstractions are actually uncontrolled. A non-socially fair way of water distribution is formed in the area. It is important for the citizens to feel confident in the existence of a fair distribution of water, this is a social and psychological need of them. Thus, it necessitates a "fair water resources management".

A balanced SWOT analysis analyzing strengths, addressing weaknesses, capitalizing on opportunities and recognizing threats is crucial for effective and resilient water resource

management in the demo area. Table 7 presents the Strengths and Weaknesses and external Opportunities and Threats related to the specific area and can be used for the evaluation of the area by organizations or individuals.

Table 7 SWOT analysis in the Agia demo site.

<u>Strengths</u>	<u>Weaknesses</u>
<p>Rich water potential - Sufficient water of good quality</p> <p>The water table is maintained at a high level</p> <p>Ability to collect large amount of water</p> <p>Local, Regional and National Governments involvement in the sustainable management of water resources - Water management is improving (albeit slowly) as there is good cooperation between the agencies now</p> <p>The wells are being mapped and there will be more data for evaluation</p>	<p>High consumption of irrigation water – too many private wells - Uncontrolled abstractions, non-socially fair way of distributing water</p> <p>Lack of adequate and accurate water consumption data and actually absence of real data both for touristic sector and agriculture</p> <p>There is no single water management body in the area - too many different water management agencies involved leading to multiplicity and polyphony of management agencies. Lack of willingness to cooperate</p> <p>Fragmentation and unsystematic management of agencies, which are increasingly understaffed. Lack of human resources to organize systematic data collection, monitor water resources and check for data accuracy</p> <p>Water distribution network and infrastructure are outdated or of poor quality. There are many leaks and losses both in drinking and irrigation water along the network and too much water is lost</p>

<u>Opportunities</u>	<u>Threats</u>
<p>Application of models for rational water management in the area – the tools could be used for water supply agencies</p> <p>Apply of good practices for the maintenance of biodiversity, landscape, soil protection and water resources in one of the main Natura 2000 ecosystems of Crete – Application of Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)</p> <p>Use of water for energy production with a green footprint</p> <p>Positive attitude of stakeholders for active participation and cooperation</p> <p>Proper management of financial instruments</p>	<p>Climate crisis with dry periods may lead to less available water and cultivated land drought</p> <p>Energy crisis</p> <p>Ageing of networks causes large losses in water distribution networks - lack of investment in infrastructure</p> <p>Understaffing of public authorities’ services</p> <p>Non-cooperation or competition between management bodies</p> <p>There is great confidence that the Agia - Myloniana aquifer is excellent in terms of quality and quantity</p> <p>Existing mindset of wasting water in all uses (water supply and irrigation) - poor management practices</p> <p>Reckless use of water in agriculture and insufficient training of farmers in proper water management based on the new directions (Common Agricultural Policy (CAP))</p> <p>Hyper-tourism - Tourism development without central planning - non-limitation of water consumption</p> <p>Questions on the ability to handle potential increase of the seasonal fluctuation of water demand between wet and dry season</p>

Stakeholders of the study area are mainly public water management and supply agencies who declare their willingness to actively participate and cooperate with the research community, provide data and train themselves in studying and applying numerical models and integrated tools like digital twins. They are very interested in Natural based Solutions (NbS) and they want to elaborate on the project.

On the other hand, individual stakeholders and mainly farmers are very interested in the actions of the project and the solutions given to them for a sustainable use of water and fertilizers. They declare their willingness to train themselves in proper water management methods based on the new directions (Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)). However, they seem to hesitate in expressing their aspects in front of the representatives of the local or regional water management agencies, they remain silent even if they have complaints about water pricing and allocation.

Stakeholders and operators from the tourism sector are absent for the time being and there is not a clear picture for their aspect till today. This has been also negatively commented by the rest of the stakeholders, since the specific stakeholder category is significantly active in the Agia demo site and should be actively participating in rational water management processes both for their information as well as for their proper training and consulting. However, stakeholder mapping is a dynamic process and more

information could be gathered in the future to map also the needs and views of the touristic sector.

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3 Arborea, Italy

3.1 System Characterization

The Italian demo site is located in central-western Sardinia, Italy, within the coastal Oristanese district, downstream from the left bank of the River Tirso. It includes the villages of Arborea, Marrubiu, and Terralba, with a combined population of approximately 18,800 people.

Until the 1920s, the Arborea plain was an uninhabitable swamp infested by malaria-carrying mosquitoes. Between the 1920 and 1930, extensive land reclamation efforts transformed the landscape: sand dunes were leveled, brackish wetlands were drained, and new agricultural land was created. Hundreds of families emigrated from north-eastern Italy to establish a new community named Mussolinia, now known as Arborea. The new settlers were allocated rectangular plots of land, each ranging from 2 to 4 hectares, depending on family size. These plots, aligned north-south and surrounded by *Eucalyptus* windbreaks, were compensation for their immense manual labor during the reclamation process, fostering a strong sense of ownership and community cohesion. A comprehensive drainage and irrigation network was implemented, comprising primary and subsidiary channels oriented both east-west and north-south, along with two powerful dewatering pumping stations that have operated continuously since their installation. The Omodeo Dam, the largest reservoir in Europe at that time, was built upstream on the River Tirso to ensure water availability for the plain. Over time, the sharecropping system evolved, with sharecroppers becoming landowners and developing a robust cooperative system involving approximately 200 farm owners. A Producers Cooperative, a Dairy Cooperative and a Cooperative bank are supported by around 150 farms managing 30,000 dairy cattle and some 3,000 beef cattle across a 6,000-hectare irrigated plain. This makes the area one of the most productive agricultural sites in Italy and Europe. In 2005, the Arborea district was designated as a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone (NVZ).

The dairy district of Arborea is surrounded by diverse agricultural systems, including over 3,000 hectares of paddy rice cultivation (primarily for seed production), as well as the cultivation of artichokes, tomatoes, melons, winter cereals (such as durum wheat and barley), and forage crops. Other significant economic activities in the region include fish farming in the remaining wetlands. These marsh wetlands are crucial ecological assets, representing about half of Sardinia's wetland heritage and a substantial portion of Italy's wetlands. They are designated as Sites of Community Importance and Special Protection Areas under the EU Natura 2000 directive and are protected under the Ramsar Convention.

The region's climate is Mediterranean, characterized by an average annual temperature of 16.7°C and average annual precipitation of 575 mm, with 75% of rainfall occurring between October and March. The annual average reference evapotranspiration is 1164 mm, resulting in an aridity index of 0.49 (semi-arid). Weather observations have shown a clear trend of rising temperatures in recent decades, with an increasing incidence of heat waves affecting crops and dairy livestock. While average monthly rainfall has not shown a clear trend, extreme weather events, including dry spells and flooding, have been noted

(Nguyen et al., 2016). The coastal area of Arborea is characterized by intense and persistent western winds and the presence of Mount Arci (about 800 meters above sea level), located only 15 km from the coastline. This mountain acts as a physical barrier for western rainfall clouds of Atlantic origin, contributing to groundwater flow that counteracts seawater intrusion and poses a potential threat of extreme flooding events.

Figure 9 Arborea Nitrate Vulnerable Zone and adjacent wetlands.

Figure 10 Left: a carrot field at Arborea. Right: milking session at a dairy farm in Arborea.

3.1.1 Main issues

The intensive dairy cattle system in Arborea is characterized by a high nutrient input, primarily nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P). These nutrients are fundamental for crop nutrition but can potentially contribute to groundwater contamination with nitrates and surface water with phosphates leading to eutrophication of the neighbouring wetlands and lagoons.

Surface water

The Regional Agency for Environmental Protection (ARPAS) has been monitoring the quality of surface water in the Arborea NVZ since 2007. This monitoring involves the assessment of various parameters, including pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen, oxygen saturation, electric conductivity, salinity, phosphorus, Chlorophyll a, turbidity, and microbial and algal growth (ARPAS, 2017). While nitrate concentrations in surface water generally remain below the threshold of 50 mg L⁻¹, the presence of elevated total phosphorus concentrations exceeding 2.0 mg L⁻¹ suggests significant eutrophication. This eutrophication primarily stems from phosphorus pollution rather than nitrate concentration, posing a threat to the health of aquatic ecosystems within the NVZ (ARPAS, 2017).

Groundwater

Extensive hydrogeological studies conducted between 2010 and 2015 have revealed significant levels of nitrate pollution in groundwater across the Arborea plain (Biddau et al., 2019; Ghiglieri et al., 2016; Pittalis et al., 2018). The investigation involved examining over 350 wells associated with the Sandy Hydrogeological Unit (SHU) and the Alluvial Hydrogeological Unit (AHU) aquifers. In the central region of the Arborea Non-Water Use Zone (NVZ), the piezometric surface suggests a local recharge area for the SHU aquifer, with water flowing towards the sea. In the southern part of the district, the piezometric contour lines indicate a general flow from east to west, with a gradient that decreases in this direction, indicating an increase in transmissivity. The flow paths suggest lateral recharge from the SHU to the AHU aquifer.

Figure 11 Piezometric contour lines and main groundwater flow directions (SHU) (modified from Ghiglieri et al., 2016).

The nitrate concentration measured on samples taken from 350 wells in the plain ranged between 1.58 and 406 mg L⁻¹. Almost 50% of SHU and AHU waters exceeded the 50 mg L⁻¹ threshold value recommended by WHO; the maximum value of 406 mg L⁻¹ was observed in SHU samples. In the southern part of the plain, the concentrations were almost uniformly above 50 mg L⁻¹. An increasing trend from east to west in the direction of the main groundwater flow prevailed, highlighting an additional pollution source located outside the Arborea NVZ (Fig. 47). Contributions from nitrate sources located within the southern part of the NVZ directly affect SHU. A second highly polluted area was identified in the NE sector of the NVZ. In this area, the recharge of SHU is local, and

there is no contribution from AHU outside of the NVZ. Therefore, the high nitrate concentrations were attributed to the local anthropogenic activities.

Since 2007, ARPAS has also carried out the monitoring of the quality of groundwater in the NVZ. The monitoring network consists of 44 sampling points (28 piezometers and 16 wells). The groundwater monitoring has a tri-monthly frequency. In Table 1, the average annual nitrate concentrations of the 44 groundwater sampling points under the monitored period (2007-2020) are reported. As indicated by the values in bold, 18 points over 44, distributed in the whole NVZ, showed average nitrate concentrations up to 6 times above the threshold value of 50 mg L⁻¹.

Table 8 Mean and SD (italics) values of nitrate concentration in the ARPAS' s groundwater monitoring network of the Arborea NVZ under the monitored period (2007-2020). Source: Arpas.

Sample No.	NO ₃ mg L ⁻¹		Sample No.	NO ₃ mg L ⁻¹		Sample No.	NO ₃ mg L ⁻¹	
17PZ008	11,55	<i>11,78</i>	P 15	89,02	<i>30,46</i>	P 33	23,22	<i>26,91</i>
P 01	12,88	<i>7,80</i>	P 16	43,13	<i>23,78</i>	P 34	53,38	<i>32,38</i>
P 02	171,51	<i>26,79</i>	P 17	44,09	<i>15,71</i>	P 35	68,51	<i>16,49</i>
P 03	23,76	<i>26,02</i>	P 20	286,70	<i>70,92</i>	P 36	40,04	<i>18,60</i>
P 04	329,81	<i>59,81</i>	P 21	22,01	<i>31,33</i>	P 37	5,73	<i>19,21</i>
P 05	32,93	<i>38,13</i>	P 22	148,99	<i>37,82</i>	P 38	141,24	<i>46,03</i>
P 06	98,45	<i>54,44</i>	P 23	198,40	<i>84,22</i>	P 39	56,37	<i>38,81</i>
P 07	30,05	<i>15,32</i>	P 24	57,34	<i>32,41</i>	P 40	53,73	<i>16,24</i>
P 08	97,76	<i>37,43</i>	P 26	226,38	<i>26,00</i>	P 41	32,35	<i>18,71</i>
P 09	83,07	<i>69,89</i>	P 27	64,33	<i>12,57</i>	P 42	56,97	<i>20,58</i>
P 10	125,11	<i>23,07</i>	P 28	80,38	<i>23,61</i>	P 43	84,23	<i>24,77</i>
P 11	115,62	<i>37,07</i>	P 29	2,96	<i>5,22</i>	P 45	3,25	<i>2,58</i>
P 12	189,43	<i>74,92</i>	P 30	3,06	<i>7,81</i>	P 46	5,54	<i>1,91</i>
P 13	76,25	<i>29,89</i>	P 31	2,50	<i>2,75</i>	P 47	14,02	<i>23,53</i>
P 14	181,03	<i>44,61</i>	P 32	1,50	<i>1,09</i>			

NRD-UNISS carried out an agronomic study at a field scale in the Arborea area to evaluate the impact of four fertilization systems on nitrate losses in the double-crop system (Demurtas et al 2016). A clear seasonal dynamics of nitrate concentration was observed in the three years, with the maximum occurring in autumn–winter. The main findings of this study showed that: (i) replacing organic with mineral sources of N did not substantially reduce nitrate leaching in the short term; (ii) nitrate leaching is unavoidable in autumn–winter, even without any fertilization for the autumn–spring crop; (iii) nitrate concentrations were still high at the end of the maize crop cycle despite the high N removal of the maize crop; (iv) the lowest nitrate concentration during the leaching period was observed when using only organic fertilizer with high C/N ratio for the ryegrass, but crop yield was halved because of the nitrogen stress observed at the end of the winter.

3.2 Stakeholder Mapping

The living lab in Arborea involves stakeholders from the public and private sector, academia, and civil society. Particular attention was paid to including also traditionally marginalized stakeholders, such as women and youth. The following operative steps were followed to ensure effective stakeholder mapping and analysis. All the relevant groups and individuals with an interest in water storage and distribution were identified. Stakeholders were then analyzed based on the scope of their involvement, to better

understand their relevance, interaction and the perspectives they offer. More specifically, for each key stakeholder, the following attributes were analyzed:

- Their status: stakeholders were categorized based on the quadruple helix approach (public, private, academia, and civil society).
- Their resources: recognizing the stock of resources available to stakeholders is crucial to mobilizing the heritage of information and knowledge whose stakeholders are holders. That is why stakeholders were also analysed based on their stock of economic, social and human capital.
- Their role: stakeholders were categorised based on the CATWOE approach (customers, actors, owners).

Table 9 Stakeholders in the Arborea Living Lab categorised by human (HC)/social (SC)/economic (EC) capital. Darker shades indicate higher levels of capital.

	STAKEHOLDERS	HC	SC	EC
PUBLIC SECTOR	REGIONAL COUNCIL FOR AGRICULTURE			
	ORISTANO LAND RECLAMATION CONSORTIUM			
	REGIONAL AGENCY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION (ARPAS)			
	REGIONAL AGENCY FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF REGIONAL PROGRAMS FOR AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT (LAORE)			
	SARDINIA WATER AUTHORITY (ENAS)			
	REGIONAL AGENCY OF THE HYDROGRAPHIC DISTRICT OF SARDINIA (ADIS)			
	MUNICIPALITY OF ARBOREA			
	FORESTRY CORP			
	PROVINCIA ORISTANO			
	PROVINCIA SASSARI			
PRIVATE SECTOR	FARMERS' COOPERATIVE			
	DAIRY COOPERATIVE 3A			
	HORTICULTURAL FARMS			
	FISHERMEN COOPERATIVE			
	COOPERATIVE BANK			
ACADEMIA	UNIVERSITY OF SASSARI			
	UNIVERSITY OF CAGLIARI			
	EURO-MEDITERRANEAN CENTER ON CLIMATE CHANGE (CMCC)			
CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS	ENVIRONMENTALIST CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATION LIPU			
	MEDSEA FOUNDATION			

Figure 12 Stakeholders in the Arborea Living Lab.

3.2.1 State Actors

Below is a succinct description of the main public stakeholders involved in the Arborea living lab.

- **Autonomous Region of Sardinia**
In Sardinia water and the entire water network is public, i.e. owned by the Autonomous Region of Sardinia (RAS); however, the management is entrusted to other stakeholders, whose activities are planned and controlled by the RAS.
- **Oristano Land Reclamation Consortium**
Its main area of competence is irrigation water; its main roles are the provision of water for irrigation to farms and the management of the irrigation water systems.
- **Regional Agency for Environmental Protection (ARPAS)**
ARPAS is responsible for the environmental monitoring of water for civil, irrigation and industrial uses. Its main roles are the control of the application of agro-environmental measures at farm scale and the monitoring of water quality in wells, channels and wetlands.
- **Regional Agency for the Implementation of Regional Programs for Agriculture and Rural Development (LAORE)**
LAORE is the Agency for the implementation of regional programs in the agricultural sector and for rural development. It promotes the integrated development of rural areas and the environmental compatibility of agricultural activities by supporting the multifunctionality of businesses, territorial specificities, quality productions, and market competitiveness."
- **Sardinia Water Authority (ENAS)**

ENAS is responsible for the uptake and distribution of raw water for civil, irrigation and industrial uses. ENAS owns the dams and sells water to Abbanoa S.p.a. (water for civil uses), the Land Reclamation Consortia (water for irrigation uses) and the Industrial Consortia (water for industrial uses), which are responsible for the distribution of water to end users.

- **Regional Agency of the Hydrographic District of Sardinia (ADIS)**

ADIS is a key stakeholder at the policy level of Sardinia's water governance system. It plans and controls the activities of ENAS, Sardinian Public Water Authority. ADIS aims to (a) protect and enhance the condition of aquatic ecosystems and terrestrial ecosystems and wetlands directly dependent on aquatic ecosystems for water supply; (b) facilitate sustainable water use based on long-term protection of sustainable water resources; (c) aim for strengthened protection and improvement of the aquatic environment; (d) ensure gradual reduction of groundwater pollution; (e) contribute to mitigating the effects of floods and droughts; (f) contribute to ensuring an adequate supply of surface and groundwater of good quality for sustainable, balanced, and fair water use.

- **Municipality of Arborea**
- **Provincial authorities**
- **Research institutions**

3.2.2 Market Actors

Below is a succinct description of the main private stakeholders involved in the Arborea living lab.

- **Farmers' Cooperative**

Arborea Farmers' Cooperative plays a significant role in the Sardinian agri-food system, with around 200 members, including ordinary members and sector members (Meat and Fruit and Vegetable Producers' Organizations), achieving an annual turnover of approximately 40 million euros.

- **Dairy Cooperative**

The dairy cooperative plays a significant role in the Sardinian agri-food system, with around 200 members. Its services include the collection, processing, and commercialization of cow's milk produced in the Arborea territory.

- **Fishermen Cooperatives**

Fishermen cooperatives carry out aquaculture in the wetlands surrounding Arborea.

- **Cooperative bank**

3.2.3 Civil Actors

Below is a succinct description of the main civil society organisations involved in the Arborea living lab.

- **Environmental civil society organisations**

Environmental civil society organisations aim to ensure biodiversity conservation, raise environmental awareness, and promote the sustainable management of marine and coastal resources in Sardinia and the Mediterranean Sea.

3.3 Governance Analysis

The effective governance of surface water resources in Arborea plays a crucial role in the sustainable management of the area's natural resources. Governance analysis involves examining the institutional structures, main policies, and regulations that govern water allocation, use and management in the basin. In this section, the aim is to uncover the effectiveness, efficiency as well as gaps and weaknesses of the existing governance framework in addressing water-related challenges. By analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of the current governance mechanisms, relevant stakeholders and decision-makers can identify areas for improvement and implement strategies to ensure and enhance the sustainable management of groundwater and surface water resources in the Arborea Plain.

3.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

Italian law (D.L.112/2008) establishes that water and the entire water network - from collection to sewage treatment plants - are public assets. However, management can be entrusted to private or public-private companies. This legal framework traces its origins to the 1989 Water Resources and Soil Conservation Act, which outlines the principles of integrated water resources management and delineates competencies between the central government and regional/local administrations. In adherence to Italian law, water management in Sardinia falls entirely under the public sector, with water being owned by the Autonomous Region of Sardinia. Irrigation entities (Consortia) are responsible for the management of collective irrigation. In the context of climate change, both the National Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation and the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan comprehensively address water-related risks across all sectors.

The existing EU legislation imposes a protective framework with standards for all water bodies within member countries, particularly targeting pollution sources. Key directives driving this effort include the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60/EC), the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) and the Floods Directive (2007/60/EC).

Since 2009, a series of plans and decrees have aimed at managing water quantity effectively. In 2015, the Ministry of Agriculture introduced the Ministerial Decree "Guidelines for the regulation by the regions of the methods for quantification of water volumes for irrigation", which promotes the use of water metering and the application of water pricing instruments based on consumption volumes. Key instruments for managing water use include robust metering, monitoring, and reporting systems that facilitate quantifying irrigation volumes, issuing permits, and setting future usage targets, especially within the agricultural sector. Furthermore, policy instruments such as subsidies, cost recovery mechanisms for water supply, and targeted agricultural advice and research further incentivise water use efficiency.

Concerning water quality, key policy instruments include the Inter-ministerial Decree, stipulating criteria and technical standards for regional regulation of agronomic use of livestock manure and wastewater. Additionally, Action Programs of Vulnerable Areas by Nitrates of Agricultural Origin are established at regional level. These multifaceted policy instruments underscore a comprehensive approach to managing water resources and enhancing water quality in Sardinia.

3.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

Water management in Sardinia is entirely under the public sector, and water is owned by the Autonomous Region of Sardinia.

Almost all the water for civil or agricultural uses comes from reservoirs. The total potential capacity of 58 dams is 2,790 Mm³, with dams' capacity ranging from 0.043 to 792 Mm³. The dams are owned by ENAS (Water Authority of Sardinia), which is responsible for the uptake and distribution of raw water for civil, irrigation and industrial uses. ENAS then sells raw water to Abbanoa S.p.a. (water for civil uses), the Remediation Consortia (water for irrigation uses) and the Industrial Consortia (water for industrial uses), which are responsible for the distribution of water to end users.

The demo site is part of the Oristano Irrigation and Land Reclamation Consortium, which encompasses a total area of 85,363 hectares, out of which approximately 36,000 hectares are served by irrigation and 15,000 hectares are irrigated. The irrigated district is supplied with high-pressure irrigation water pumped from the channels connected to the Eleonora d'Arborea dam.

Figure 13 The Oristanese irrigation and land reclamation consortium. Left: total area; Right: irrigated districts. Source: www.bonificaoristanese.it

The annual water deficit in the Arborea irrigated plain is compensated with approximately 6000 m³ ha⁻¹ of irrigation water supplied by the Consortium, with 75% used for summer crops like silage corn and 25% for supplementary irrigation of autumn-spring haycrops. The Consortium also maintains water infrastructures and implements strategies to minimize leakages and accurately monitor delivered water for irrigation. Each farmer has a counter for monitoring actual consumption, which aligns with cropping system water requirements. The shift to sprinkler irrigation systems has improved efficiency compared to low-efficiency surface systems, reducing freshwater input to wetlands and increasing water salinity, thereby creating a new habitat for aquaculture. At farm scale, irrigation is managed at the moment without precision irrigation systems, as the water price is only partially dependent on actual consumptions.

Monitoring of water for hygienic, sanitary, and environmental purposes in Sardinia is overseen by two regional agencies, ARPAS and ASL.

Private citizens intending to use surface water (rivers) or groundwater (wells) for various purposes must obtain a written license from the provincial authority.

Figure 14 The water governance structure of Sardinia. Source: Maurizi (2020).

3.3.3 Analysis

There is a widespread sense of urgency among stakeholders to address water quality concerns, particularly nitrate pollution, along with the generational turnover in economic activities that have driven development in this rural district over the last decades. This urgency has been instrumental in fostering a shared sense of purpose among stakeholders and increasing their willingness to participate in the living lab, which they believe will bring value to them.

The living lab workshop held in April 2024 highlighted the complexity of the addressed water challenge, with stakeholders recognising the importance of a systemic, holistic approach encompassing not only technical and scientific innovations but also new forms of collaboration and multi-scale, multi-stakeholder governance models.

During the workshop, diverging visions about the future and main needs and priorities emerged among stakeholders, revealing apparent and latent conflicts. One significant divergence exists between the focus of environmental agencies on water pollution and concerns about potential infringement procedures by the European Commission if effective actions to mitigate nitrate pollution are not implemented, and the focus of local

cooperatives on the crisis faced by dairy farms due to the lack of generational turnover and substantial investments made to support the dairy industry. The Arborea district, designated as a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone (NVZ) since 2005, has faced challenges in complying with EU nitrate directives. The main prescriptions of the ND action plan for dairy farmers included the restrictions on the disposal of the effluents which include the construction of new stocking tanks for the slurry, the limitations on the amount and periods of distribution of the organic fertilizers that could be disposed in the NVZ cropland (170 kg N ha^{-1}), representing some half of the net double cropping N uptake (approximately $350\text{-}400 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$). However, the significant annual effluent output per farm exceeds the prescriptions outlined in the ND. To ensure appropriate plant nutrition, farmers must comply with a N fertilization plan which results in the need to purchase mineral N fertilizers to meet crop requirements fully. Moreover, the surplus manure and slurry must be exported outside the NVZ, incurring substantial additional costs for land renting, estimated to be up to 10% of the milk price. Despite efforts to align with these directives, groundwater nitrate concentrations remain high, exceeding recommended thresholds of 50 mg L^{-1} . The long-term turnover of the aquifer, estimated to be 20 to 30 years, exacerbates this issue (ARPAS, 2023; Ghiglieri et al., 2016; Linker et al., 2024 under revision). Farmers perceive the prescribed fertilization practices as ineffective and costly, leading to concerns about the sustainability of agricultural operations.

The living lab serves as a platform for dialogue among stakeholders, integrating socio-technical discussions with visionary conversations about the future of the rural community. This process fosters learning and awareness of the complexity involved in addressing water challenges. As one public administrator involved in the living lab remarked, “The water district agency is probably learning that things are far more complex than just applying an EU directive”. During the workshop, approximately 30 ongoing or recent initiatives in the Nitrate Vulnerable Zone (NVZ) were mapped and shared, engaging stakeholders from private and public organizations. This collaborative effort highlighted the need to mitigate fragmentation among initiatives through coordination to achieve significant improvements in water resource quality. At the workshop's conclusion, participants agreed on a roadmap for co-designing sustainable, actionable pathways to address water quality concerns. Proposed options for mitigating nitrate pollution, currently being tested in the living lab, were grouped into four main categories: (i) initiatives/studies to improve the understanding of hydrological and nutrient dynamics at district and farm scales (e.g. soil infiltration assessments, hydrogeological studies and models, and coastal forest management); (ii) “upstream” actions to reduce nutrient loads in livestock farming and optimise the storage and management of effluents (e.g. mitigating nutrient surplus, ammonia stripping from animal effluents, struvite crystallisation from the liquid fraction of effluent bio-digestates, and enhancing animal diet efficiency); (iii) “downstream” actions to remove nitrates from polluted groundwater through environmental remediation actions (e.g. forest infiltration areas to enhance denitrification, anaerobic bioreactors to decontaminate drainage water, thermochemical treatments like the hydrothermal carbonization); (iv) actions to promote governance innovations, community activation, awareness-raising, addressing issues such as improving the attractiveness of the agricultural sector for young people and women.

The living lab demonstrates the potential of collaborative, participatory approaches to tackle complex water socio-ecological challenges. However, challenges remain in terms of governance and institutionalization. Sustainable outcomes will require sustained engagement, continued partnership building, and the mainstreaming of living lab principles into local policy and practice.

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4 Bode, Germany

4.1 System Characterization

The Bode River flows from the northern region of the Harz Mountains and empties into the Saale River. The Bode catchment spans approximately 3300 km² and extends from the rugged Harz Mountains to the north-eastern lowlands, encapsulating diverse landscapes and climatic conditions. Annual precipitation ranges from over 1500 mm in the Harz Mountains to less than 500 mm in the lowlands, with mean annual air temperatures ranging from 5°C at the summit of the Brocken to 9.5°C in the eastern Magdeburg Börde region. The land use within the catchment is diverse: 70% arable land, 26% forested or semi-natural habitats, 7% urban areas and open-cast mining sites, and 1% water bodies and wetlands. Agriculture is predominant in the plateaus and lower-elevation areas, while forested regions are significant for environmental conservation and research. Urban areas contribute to local economies through various industries (Wollschläger et al., 2016).

The Bode catchment area, located in central Germany, is a significant study site for the OurMED project. Despite being outside the Mediterranean region, it provides valuable insights due to its status as Germany's largest drinking water reservoir and its highly fertile soils. The Bode catchment is part of the TERENO² Harz/Central German Lowland Observatory and has been intensively monitored, providing valuable hydrological and hydro-chemical data. Research focuses on water quantity, quality, and the impacts of climate change, with high-resolution data collected for over 10 years. Monitoring metrics include discharge and water chemical properties such as oxygen content and anions.

The Bode catchment area exhibits a spatial gradient of varied nitrate sources. The southern, naturally protected headwaters in the Harz Mountains have low nitrate concentrations. As the river extends, the influence of agricultural land use increases. According to Mueller et al, 2016., the major tributaries can be categorized into four primary groups (Figure 15):

1. The mountainous river headwaters, contributing about 28% of the total flow, discharge into the Rappbode drinking water reservoir and include the Kalte Bode, Warme Bode, Rappbode, and Luppode streams.
2. Transfer streams such as the Hassel, Selke, and Holtemme, accounting for 27% of the total discharge, flow between protected forest areas and agricultural land. Within these transfer streams, 21 subcatchments near the headwaters are entirely forested. Further downstream, nine subcatchments show increasing agricultural impact, with mixed forest and agricultural zones (each covering around 50% ± 10%). Additionally, 13 subcatchments are predominantly agricultural, with more than 60% of each subcatchment covered by arable land.
3. The northern agricultural lowlands, primarily arable land, include the Großer Graben, contributing 21% of the total discharge.
4. Other minor tributaries, not included in the sampling network, along with diffuse inflows (including groundwater), contribute 22% of the total discharge.

² <https://www.tereno.net/>

Figure 15 Location of the Bode catchment with major sub catchments and spatial distribution of stream discharge gauges. The Selke tributary is heightened with runoff stations and land use information (Mueller, C. 2016).

The catchment area includes sub catchments with varied hydrological characteristics and human impacts:

1. **Hassel/Rappbode:** Flashy hydrology, predominantly good chemical status, extensive forests, and a drinking water reservoir.
2. **Selke:** Flashy hydrology, low wastewater loading, and moderate agricultural intensity.
3. **Holtemme:** Flashy hydrology, high wastewater loading, and more intensive agriculture.
4. **Grosser Graben:** Monotonous, highly regulated hydrology, low wastewater load, and highly intensive agriculture.
5. **Lower Bode:** A mixture of the characteristics from all other sub catchments.

4.1.1 Main issues

The main water-related issues in the Bode River basin are significant and multifaceted. The prolonged drought in recent years has severely impacted the catchment area, leading to extensive deforestation and negatively affecting both water quantity and quality. This situation necessitates an urgent shift from a mono-sectoral water management approach, which is based on trade-offs, to a more balanced multisectoral management that considers the needs of all stakeholders.

The drought conditions have exacerbated nutrient leaching into the drinking water reservoir and the downstream parts of the river network due to reduced forest uptake,

decreased dilution capacity, and an increased risk of soil erosion. Consequently, farmers in the region are likely to shift to more irrigated crops, utilizing both surface water and groundwater, which will put additional pressure on the water resources.

Historically, many headwater sections in the Bode catchment have been subjected to acidification caused by a combination of natural factors, such as siliceous bedrock (granite) and peatland near the springs, and anthropogenic factors, including forestry practices that predominantly use coniferous trees and acidic atmospheric depositions (Stöcker, 1994; Langheinrich et al., 2002). Among the widespread problems in the catchment, eutrophication due to nutrient inputs (nitrogen and phosphorus) and pesticide contamination from agricultural activities are notable (Jiang et al., 2014, 2015; Ippolito et al., 2015; Munze et al., 2015). Future land use changes, such as the shift to energy crops, may further increase agricultural inputs of nutrients and pesticides to surface waters (Kattwinkel et al., 2011; Jomaa et al., 2016).

Climate change has already altered the hydrological regime and may continue to do so. Expected changes include increased winter precipitation, reduced snowmelt, decreased summer precipitation, and altered ecohydrological boundary conditions of the river system (Anis and Rode, 2015). These changes will also affect the interactions between groundwater and surface water, particularly during the summer season (Kropp et al., 2010).

4.2 Stakeholder Mapping

The approach used to carry out stakeholder mapping within the Bode catchment is indicated below:

- Literature review: Investigation reports and publications on water management in the Bode catchment. These are government reports, academic papers, and magazines by environment organizations.
- Web Search and Official Websites: This is information obtained from web pages of official agencies, both local and on the state level, research institutions, and NGOs. This also included some specific searches in German to ensure that the details were more generalized and wide-ranging in scope.
- Categorisation and Analysis: According to the roles, power and interests pertaining to water resources management, the high-profile stakeholders identified were categorized into various categories and then analyzed based on their social, economic, and human capital.

These steps were crucial in capturing the full scope of stakeholders involved in the Bode catchment area. Later on, the identified stakeholders were categorized into different classes according to their roles, influence, and interests concerning water resource management. The categorization process included several methods:

1. **Status Classification:**
 - Stakeholders were classified based on their status, such as state, market, or civil society actors. This helped in understanding the hierarchical and functional positions of the stakeholders within the governance structure.
2. **Resource-Based Classification:**
 - Stakeholders were analyzed based on their economic, social, and human capital. This provided insights into the resources each stakeholder could

bring to the table and their capacity to influence or support water management efforts.

3. Role-Based Analysis Using the CATWOE Framework:

- The CATWOE framework was applied to understand each stakeholder's role in the water management system. This included defining their Customers (C), Actors (A), Transformation Process (T), World View (W), Owners (O), and Environmental Constraints (E). This analysis clarified how each stakeholder contributes to or is affected by the water management processes.

4. Power/Interest Diagram:

- Stakeholders were also mapped using a Power/Interest diagram to visualize their influence and interest in the Bode catchment's water management. This tool helped prioritize stakeholders for engagement and strategic communication based on their power to affect outcomes and their interest in the project's success.

Here is the initial list of potential stakeholders for the Bode River catchment demo site:

1. European Commission (WFD)³:

Function: Oversees the implementation of the Water Framework Directive, aiming to achieve good qualitative and quantitative status of all water bodies in the EU by 2027.
Interests: Sustainable water management, environmental protection, and compliance with EU directives.

2. International Commission for the Protection of the Elbe River (ICPER)⁴:

Function: Coordinates international efforts to improve water quality, manage flood risks, and protect the Elbe River Basin.
Interests: Sustainable river basin management and compliance with the Water Framework Directive and Floods Directive.

3. Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, and Nuclear Safety (BMU)⁵:

Function: Develops and implements Germany's environmental policies, including water management and climate protection.
Interests: Environmental conservation, sustainable development, and policy implementation at the national and EU levels.

4. Drinking Water Authority (FEO)⁶:

Function: Supplies high-quality drinking water to approximately 2.5 million people in Saxony-Anhalt, Saxony, and Thuringia.
Interests: Ensuring secure and reliable water supply, maintaining high standards of water quality, and enhancing infrastructure resilience.

5. German Working Group on Water Issues of the Federal States (LAWA)⁷:

Function: Facilitates cooperation among German federal states on water management and policy implementation.

³ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water_en

⁴ <https://www.ikse-mkol.org/>

⁵ <https://www.bmu.de/>

⁶ <https://www.feo.de/>

⁷ <https://www.lawa.de/English-About-LAWA.html>

- Interests: Harmonizing water management practices and ensuring compliance with EU water policies.
6. **Landesbetrieb für Hochwasserschutz und Wasserwirtschaft (LHW)⁸:**
 Function: Manages flood protection and water resource management in Saxony-Anhalt.
 Interests: Effective flood protection and sustainable water management practices.
 7. **Lower Water Authority (Untere Wasserbehörde)⁹:**
 Function: Regulates water usage and quality within its jurisdiction, ensuring compliance with environmental standards.
 Interests: Sustainable water use and protection of water resources.
 8. **Lower Nature Conservation Agency (Untere Naturschutzbehörde)¹⁰:**
 Function: Protects natural habitats and ensures that water management practices do not harm ecosystems.
 Interests: Biodiversity conservation and ecological sustainability.
 9. **Elbe River Basin Authority (FGG Elbe)¹¹:**
 Function: Coordinates water and flood risk management across the Elbe River Basin.
 Interests: Sustainable river basin management and cross-border cooperation.
 10. **Ministry of Economy, Tourism, Agriculture and Forestry (MWL)¹²:**
 Function: Oversees economic development, tourism, agriculture, and forestry policies in Saxony-Anhalt.
 Interests: Promoting sustainable economic practices and effective resource management.
 11. **Ministry of Science, Energy, Climate Protection, and Environment (MWU)¹³:**
 Function: Manages science, energy, climate protection, and environmental policies in Saxony-Anhalt.
 Interests: Innovation in energy and climate policy, and environmental sustainability.
 12. **Farmers' Association of Saxony-Anhalt¹⁴:**
 Function: Represents the interests of local farmers, advocating for water availability and quality.
 Interests: Sustainable agricultural practices and water resource management.
 13. **Maintenance Association of Saxony-Anhalt¹⁵:**
 Function: carry out the maintenance of smaller rivers, streams and ditches to support flood protection and resource sustainability.
 Interests: Infrastructure resilience and sustainable maintenance practices.
 14. **Environmental NGOs:**
BUND Sachsen-Anhalt¹⁶:

⁸ <https://lhw.sachsen-anhalt.de/>

⁹ <https://www.magdeburg.de/index.php?ModID=9&FID=37.2044.1&object=tx%2C698.8841>

¹⁰ <https://www.magdeburg.de/index.php?ModID=9&FID=37.2046.1&object=tx%2C698.8841#>

¹¹ <https://www.fgg-elbe.de/home.html>

¹² <https://mwL.sachsen-anhalt.de/>

¹³ <https://mwu.sachsen-anhalt.de/>

¹⁴ <https://www.bauernverband-st.de/ueber-uns/vorstand/>

¹⁵ <https://www.uhv-lsa.de/>

¹⁶ <https://www.bund-sachsen-anhalt.com/>

Stakeholders capable of including other actors, representing important constituencies, and participating effectively in local civil society.

- High: Examples include the European Commission, ICPER, BMU, Farmers' Association, BUND, and NABU, due to their influence and broad recognition.
- Medium: Stakeholders like LHW, FGG Elbe, and Maintenance Association have good engagement and acknowledgment but are more specialized or localized in their reach.
- Low: Stakeholders that mainly operate within specific jurisdictions or have limited broader social influence.

Economic Capital:

- High: Stakeholders with significant financial resources or influence over resource allocation, such as the European Commission, BMU, FEO, MWL, and MWU.
- Medium: Stakeholders like ICPER, LAWA, and LHW, who have some influence and access to resources but are not the primary economic drivers.
- Low: Stakeholders primarily focused on regulatory roles or advocacy, such as the Lower Water Authority, Lower Nature Conservation Agency, and environmental NGOs.

Human Capital:

- High: Stakeholders possessing advanced knowledge, skills, and communication abilities necessary for water management and policy development, such as the European Commission, ICPER, BMU, FEO, and MWU.
- Medium: Stakeholders like LAWA, LHW, and the Maintenance Association have specialized skills and capacity, but their engagement in broader communication or debate is limited.
- Low: Not applicable in this context, as all stakeholders have a baseline level of human capital suitable for their roles.

Figure 16 Stakeholder matrix based on power/interest in Bode, Germany.

Based on the Power/Interest Grid in Figure 16, brings out very vividly the roles played and how influential different stakeholders are in the Bode River Basin. Here is an explanation of how to engage with each group:

1. **High Power/High Interest (LHW, Rappbode Reservoir Authority):**
These stakeholders are crucial to the project's success due to their significant influence and high interest in water management. They should be closely managed through regular engagement and consultation. Strategies should focus on involving them in decision-making processes and keeping them well-informed on project developments to harness their support and obtain valuable inputs.
2. **High Power/Low Interest (FEO, BMU, LAWA, MWU, MWL, WFD):**
While ICPER has considerable power, their interest appears lower. Strategies should focus on increasing their interest to prevent potential opposition and to transition them towards the High Power/High Interest quadrant. This could involve highlighting the impacts of water management issues on areas they value or showing how changes in water management can benefit them.
3. **Low Power/High Interest (Lower Water Authority, Lower Nature Conservation Agency, Maintenance Association, Farmers' Association, NGOs):**
These groups, while having lower power, are highly interested in the project's outcomes. They can be key allies and supporters. Regular updates and consultations will help maintain their support and utilize their interest to foster community backing and gather localized insights.
4. **Low Power/Low Interest (FGG Elbe, ICPER):**
These stakeholders require less active engagement but should still be monitored. Keeping them informed with minimal effort, such as through periodic updates or general communications, is sufficient. This approach ensures they are aware of project progress without requiring significant resources to manage the relationship.

Table 11 Stakeholders classification based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local) in Bode, Germany.

	STATE	MARKET	CIVIL
<u>INTERNATIONAL</u>	International Commission for the Protection of the Elbe River (ICPER)	-	European Commission (WFD)
<u>NATIONAL</u>	Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, and Nuclear Safety (BMU)	Drinking Water Authority (FEO)	-
<u>State</u>	Landesbetrieb für Hochwasserschutz und Wasserwirtschaft (LHW)	Farmers' Association of Saxony-Anhalt	Environmental NGOs (BUND Sachsen-Anhalt, NABU Sachsen-Anhalt)
	Elbe River Basin Authority (FGG Elbe)	Maintenance Association of Saxony-Anhalt	-
	Lower Water Authority (Untere Wasserbehörde)	-	-
	Lower Nature Conservation Agency (Untere Naturschutzbehörde)	-	-

Figure 17 Water governance stakeholder map of Bode demo site, Germany.

4.2.1 State Actors

State actors are primarily responsible for the formulation and enforcement of policies, as well as the management and conservation of water resources at various levels:

- **International:** The **International Commission for the Protection of the Elbe River (ICPER)** oversees international collaboration and regulatory frameworks to manage and protect the Elbe River, impacting multiple countries.
- **National:** The **Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, and Nuclear Safety (BMU)** develops environmental policies and sets standards for water management across Germany.
- **State:** Organizations like the **Landesbetrieb für Hochwasserschutz und Wasserwirtschaft (LHW)** and the **Elbe River Basin Authority (FGG Elbe)** manage regional water resources and flood protection. Additionally, the **Lower Water Authority** and the **Lower Nature Conservation Agency** regulate local water quality and conservation efforts, ensuring compliance with environmental regulations.

4.2.2 Market Actors

Market actors in the Bode River Basin are engaged in activities that directly affect the use and management of water resources, influencing policy through economic channels:

- **National:** The **Drinking Water Authority (FEO)** is pivotal in managing national water supply and quality, playing a crucial role in the infrastructure and regulation of water services.
- **State:**
 - o The **Farmers' Association of Saxony-Anhalt** represents agricultural interests, advocating for policies that support sustainable irrigation and water usage in farming.

- The **Maintenance Association of Saxony-Anhalt** is critical for maintaining water infrastructure, ensuring the functionality and efficiency of water management systems at a local level.

4.2.3 Civil Actors

Civil actors are involved in advocacy, education, and the promotion of sustainable water management practices, often influencing policy and public opinion:

- **International:** The **European Commission (WFD)** plays a transformative role by setting directives that shape water management practices across Europe, promoting sustainability and conservation.
- **State:** Environmental NGOs such as **BUND Sachsen-Anhalt** and **NABU Sachsen-Anhalt** actively engage in conservation efforts, policy advocacy, and community education to promote sustainable water use and biodiversity conservation. These organizations are instrumental in shaping local environmental policies and fostering community engagement in conservation activities.

4.3 Governance Analysis

The governance framework of the Bode River basin, is founded upon the all-inclusive climate change adaptation and sustainability in the water management approach, with active stakeholder inclusion. This multi-stakeholder, multi-level approach considers potential stakeholders at international, national, and state levels of engagement. At the core of this multi-faceted strategy is recognizing local, regional, and international cooperation based on or toward broader EU strategies, such as those underpinning the Green Deal.

Governance Processes and Mechanisms

Regulatory Compliance and Enforcement: The governance framework includes mechanisms for ensuring compliance with established standards through inspections, monitoring, and legal actions by bodies like LHW and FGG Elbe.

Stakeholder Participation: The framework emphasizes engaging local communities, farmer groups, and NGOs in decision-making processes to consider diverse perspectives in water management strategies.

Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM): The system adopts a holistic approach, considering the interconnections between different water uses, conservation, and socio-economic development.

Scientific Research and Data-Driven Decision Making: Research by institutions like UFZ and LHW provides the foundation for data-driven policies, risk assessments, and evaluations of water management interventions.

International and Regional Collaboration: ICPER and FGG Elbe facilitate cooperation and coordination between countries and regions within the Elbe River Basin to address transboundary water management challenges.

The water governance in the Bode River basin aligns with the Water Framework Directive (WFD) implemented in the Elbe River basin. The WFD aims to achieve good status for

surface and groundwater bodies by 2027, requiring member states to set up procedures and instruments for compliance.

The **Gewässerrahmenkonzept (Water Framework Concept) for Sachsen-Anhalt 2022-2027** outlines comprehensive water management in the region, including the Bode River catchment. This concept focuses on restoring natural water body structures and improving water quality, with significant investments in water structures since 2000. It also includes a sediment management plan to address pollutant accumulation. Collaboration across government levels and stakeholders is essential to achieve the WFD's goals, with public participation and economic instruments playing key roles.

4.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

Water management is significantly influenced by the European Water Framework Directive (WFD). This directive requires water management practices to be coordinated at the river basin level, rather than being confined to administrative boundaries. Adopted in 2000, the WFD mandates achieving "good" ecological and chemical status for all European waters, leading to substantial changes in water governance across Europe, including Germany.

In Germany, the Water Management Act (Wasserhaushaltsgesetz, WHG) serves as the foundational legal framework for implementing the WFD. This is complemented by specific regulations like the ordinance for surface waters (OGewV) and the ordinance for groundwater (GrwV), which set quality standards and management practices for water bodies. Additionally, the State Water Acts (Landeswassergesetze) of each federal state, including Sachsen-Anhalt, provide further specifications and adaptations suited to regional conditions.

The Gewässerrahmenkonzept (Water Framework Concept) for Sachsen-Anhalt, covering 2022 to 2027. This framework is part of the third management cycle under the WFD, emphasizing efforts to restore and protect water ecosystems through both structural and non-structural measures.

4.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

The governance structure for the Bode River catchment is organized across multiple levels: international, national, and state, reflecting a comprehensive framework that integrates various stakeholders from governmental bodies to local organizations.

- **International Level:**
 - o The **International Commission for the Protection of the Elbe River (ICPER)** works on cross-border water management issues.
 - o The **European Commission (WFD)** sets overarching water policies through directives like the Water Framework Directive, which all member states, including Germany, are required to implement.
- **National Level:**
 - o **Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, and Nuclear Safety (BMU)** oversees environmental policies across Germany.
 - o **Drinking Water Authority (FEO)** ensures the quality and supply of drinking water.

- **German Working Group on Water Issues of the Federal States (LAWA)** coordinates water management strategies across different federal states.
- **State Level:**
 - **Landesbetrieb für Hochwasserschutz und Wasserwirtschaft (LHW)** manages water resources and flood protection within Saxony-Anhalt.
 - **Ministries** such as the Ministry for the Environment, Agriculture, and Energy (MULE); Ministry of Economy, Tourism, Agriculture, and Forestry (MWL); and the Ministry of Science, Energy, Climate Protection, and Environment (MWU) are involved in specific aspects of environmental governance and resource management.
 - **Local entities** such as Lower Water Authority and Lower Nature Conservation Agency regulate and oversee local water and conservation efforts.

Figure 18 Governance structure of Bode demo site, Germany.

4.3.3 Analysis

The governance framework for the Bode River catchment illustrates the complexity and multi-layered nature of water management in Germany. The WFD has been crucial in reshaping governance structures to focus on ecological outcomes and cross-boundary coordination. However, several challenges have emerged during implementation.

One major issue is the need for effective coordination across different administrative levels and among various stakeholders. The creation of river basin organizations has helped address some of these challenges by providing a platform for joint planning and decision-making. However, coordinating remains complex, given the diverse interests and priorities of different states and local entities.

Financial and human resources required for effective water management are also significant. States like Sachsen-Anhalt, which have weaker water administrations and financial constraints, often rely on synergies created through basin-wide cooperation and

external funding, including European Union support. Despite these efforts, achieving the desired ecological status for all water bodies by the WFD's deadlines remains challenging.

Additionally, the governance structure must continually adapt to emerging challenges such as climate change, which impacts water availability and quality. Initiatives like the KLIMSA¹⁸ project in Sachsen-Anhalt aim to integrate climate adaptation into water management, highlighting the dynamic and evolving nature of governance in this field.

During the OurMED project, the UFZ decided to streamline communication for project progress by holding stakeholder meetings exclusively with the LHW, a key and influential stakeholder. The LHW not only holds authority over the Rappbode Reservoir but also has established relationships with other local stakeholders. This pre-existing collaboration between UFZ and LHW has enhanced the efficiency and effectiveness of their joint efforts.

The first stakeholder meeting between UFZ and LHW, held on June 14, 2024, marked significant progress. UFZ shared its research goals and updates, while LHW provided valuable insights and data. Both parties agreed to maintain continuous communication, scheduling biannual meetings to monitor progress and exchange knowledge. Additionally, LHW shared their reports on mitigation measures within the Bode River catchment and granted access to their discharge data, which will be instrumental for research purposes.

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5 Jucar, Spain

5.1 System Characterization

The Albufera of Valencia, henceforth referred to simply as the Albufera or Albufera Lake, is the Spanish demo site of the OurMED project. Situated along the Mediterranean coast of Spain, about 15 kilometres from the southern end of Valencia, between the Túria River to the north and the Júcar River to the south. It is the largest natural lake on the Iberian Peninsula, covering a surface area of 24 km² with an average depth of 1.0 m. To the north and west of the lake area, there is a string of towns and several thousand small, medium, and large industries. Also, it is surrounded by rice fields, fruit orchards (mainly citrus), mixed crop areas, and a sandbar (around 30 kilometres long and 1 kilometre wide).

Over the course of history, both natural forces and human activities have significantly influenced the configuration of the lake as it is recognised today. Originally, a brackish lagoon, the lake has transformed into a freshwater ecosystem due primarily to centuries of extensive irrigation agriculture in its surrounding area. This shift has seen a notable reduction in the open water surface, which has dwindled from an estimated expanse of over 30,000 hectares during the Roman era to a mere 2433 hectares presently. This alteration can be attributed to a combination of natural sedimentation processes and human interventions, such as the conversion of waterlogged regions into rice paddies in the XIX-XX centuries (Martín et al., 2020).

In the mid-1970s, the Albufera lake experienced a decline in water quality due to the influx of untreated sewage and agrochemicals, stemming from inadequate sanitation facilities. Over the subsequent four decades, urban development led the lake to function as a de facto wastewater treatment site.

Despite of this and acknowledging its ecological significance, the lake and its surrounding areas (approximately 216 km²) gained recognition as a Natural Park in 1986 by the Valencian Community (see Figure 1). In addition, the Albufera holds special protection status at both the community and international levels. Designated a Special Protection Area for Birds (SPA) in April 1991 under the Birds Directive (79/409/EEC), it was listed in the RAMSAR Convention's Wetlands of International Importance in 1989. The Albufera also features habitats and species protected by the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC). Furthermore, it is part of the Natura 2000 Network.

Nowadays, enhancing water quality and ecological status remains a challenging task and a primary goal for managing its unique water system, developed over centuries.

5.1.1 Main issues

For the Albufera Natural Park demo site, the main issues, followed by the proposed solutions, are presented as follows:

1. Addressing eutrophication: Increasing the number of constructed wetlands to improve water quality and enhance the naturalization of Albufera Park.
2. Optimisation of Reclaimed Waters: Enhancing the utilisation of treated wastewater from major wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in the area such as Pinedo, Quart-

Benácher, Albufera Sur, and Sueca is imperative to bolster the reliability of irrigation practices.

3. Integration of Reclaimed Waters in perellonà¹⁹: Implementing reclaimed water systems in perellonà areas can significantly contribute to sustainable irrigation practices.
4. Water Swaps Initiatives: Developing mechanisms for water swaps, wherein regenerated water is utilized for irrigation while providing natural water sources to the lake, can optimize water resource management.

Maintaining High Water Levels: Sustaining elevated water levels is crucial to mitigate the risk of salinization resulting from sea intrusion, safeguarding the ecological balance of the region.

5.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder mapping is based on some references (Jégou and Sanchis-Ibor, 2019), documents from the regional government and the experience of UPV members.

Table 12 Classification of stakeholders based on their stock of resources in Júcar, Spain.

	SOCIAL CAPITAL	ECONOMIC CAPITAL	HUMAN CAPITAL	
NGO: Acció Ecologista-Agró	HIGH	LOW	HIGH	
NGO: SEO - BirdLife	HIGH	MEDIUM	HIGH	
NGO: Fundació Global Nature	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	
NGO: Fundació Assut	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	NA
Residents: el Palmar, el Saler, el Perelló-Perellonet.	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	LOW
Surrounding residents: Valencia...	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM
Irrigation communities: Acequia Real del Júcar, Favara, Oro...	HIGH	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	HIGH
Fishermen's Guild	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	
Hunting associations	MEDIUM	LOW	LOW	
Journalists	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	
Cultural associations: Lateen sailing	LOW	LOW	LOW	
Governing Board of Natural Park	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	
Corporate Social Responsibility companies and foundations: Coca-Cola, Bancaixa-CaixaBank, Carrefour, Parador Nacional de el Saler.	LOW	HIGH	LOW	
National Government: Júcar Water Authori	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM	
Valencia City Council: Devesa-Albufera technical office	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	
Autonomous Community Authority (GVA).	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	
National Government: public company ACUAMED.	LOW	HIGH	LOW	
EU: Environmental projects (LIFE, PRIMA...)	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	LOW	
Agro-industry companies	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	
Drainage Board	LOW	LOW	HIGH	
Tourism small enterpises	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	
Universities- Research centers	HIGH	LOW	MEDIUM	
Professionals	MEDIUM	LOW	MEDIUM	

¹⁹ Perellonà is the peak winter flooding, submerging roads, banks, and ditches, expanding l'Albufera's surface temporarily and increase, promoting nutrient mineralization.

Figure 19 Stakeholder grid based on power/interest in Júcar, Spain.

Table 13 Stakeholders classification based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local) in Júcar, Spain.

	STATE	MARKET	CIVIL
NATIONAL	Ministry of Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITECO)		
	Aguas de las Cuencas Mediterráneas (ACUAMED)		
REGIONAL / BASIN SCALE	Júcar Water Authority (CHJ)		
	Regional Government	Agro industry (rice)	NGO: Seo-BirdLife
		Tourism companies	NGO: Fundación Global Nature
LOCAL / SUB-BASIN SCALE	Valencia City Council		Fishermen's Guild
	Drainage Board		NGO: Acció Ecologista-Agró
	Other municipalities		NGO: Fundació Assut
			Irrigation Communities
			Hunting associations

5.2.1 State Actors

Four are the main State Actors that can make decisions about water management.

1. Autonomous Community Authority (GVA). Two organisms are involved:
 - Albufera Natural Park Authority. Is the environmental authority.
 - Public Entity for Water Sanitation (EPSAR). Is a public company responsible for wastewater treatment plants. Sanitation investment in the area is proposed and financed by EPSAR.
2. Valencia City Council: It is the lake's owner. *The Oficina Técnica Devesa-Albufera* is the department responsible for maintenance works.
3. Júcar Water Authority (CHJ): It depends on the Ministry of Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge. According to Water Law (1986)²⁰ it is the owner of Spanish water masses (but not of Albufera Lake) and it distributes the resources among the authorized users.

Drainage Board: it is the organism that controls the water level in Albufera Lake. They open/close the connecting gates to the sea according to the rice production and some environmental constraints.

5.2.2 Market Actors

Some economic activities are developed inside the Natural Park:

1. Agricultural activities: fruits (oranges), vegetables and rice. Food processing industry: rice.
2. Tourism: recreational, restoration and birdwatching.
3. Fishing.

During the last few years, different companies have supported different environmental actions jointly with NGOs. The Corporate Social Responsibility of companies is an opportunity to obtain funds for environmental monitoring and restoration. Also, for educational and environmental awareness.

New market products are being studied to solve environmental problems. In the face of rice straw burning, collecting, and distributing rice packs is seen as a promising management. Rice packs can be used for isolation in small buildings, etc.

5.2.3 Civil Actors

Different NGOs develop intense activities, not just reporting any environmental impact, but collaborating in the management of some wetland areas. Municipalities, public administrations, and different companies collaborate with NGOs co-financing educational activities, bird watching and biological surveys, and water quality monitoring. In some spaces, land stewardship is the legal figure used to link landowners and managers, with high success.

The Governing Board of the Natural Park is a consultative organism created to support the regional administration. It is the forum where all the stakeholders are represented. They have one or two meetings per year and discuss diverse issues. The Governing Board

²⁰ BOE-A-2001-14276 Real Decreto Legislativo 1/2001, de 20 de julio, por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley de Aguas.

can create specific committees to help it. The last created is the Scientific Committee, with members from the Universities, Research Centres, and professionals.

5.3 Governance Analysis

Fragmentation is the word that best defines water governance in the Albufera Natural Park. Different actors and responsibilities, sometimes lack of transparency, pressures from stakeholders, and conflicts between farmers and fishermen, make the governance of this area a permanent conflict between conservationist and productivism opposite visions.

5.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

The national hydrological plan, ratified by the Spanish Congress under Law 10/2001²¹ on July 5th and subsequently amended by Laws 53/2002 and 62/2003 on December 30th, as well as Royal Decree-Law 2/2004 on June 18th, and Law 11/2005 on June 22nd, is a comprehensive hydrological planning tool implemented at the national level in Spain. This plan delineates policies, strategies, and measures aimed at the integrated management of water resources across the entirety of Spanish territory. Its primary aim is to ensure the availability and sustainable utilisation of water, while also safeguarding aquatic ecosystems and mitigating risks such as floods and droughts.

At the basin level, the basin hydrological plans are aligned with the strategies outlined in the national hydrological plan. Moreover, their composition adheres to the principles outlined in the Directive 2000/60/EC²² of the European Parliament and the Council, commonly known as the EU Water Framework Directive, as well as the principles²³ outlined in the consolidated Law of Water, ratified by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2001, dated July 20. According to that law, the territorial scope of each basin hydrological plan must correspond to the boundaries of the respective river basin district (or demarcation), which is composed of the natural boundaries of river basins and their associated drainage networks. Furthermore, it specifies that these plans are developed either by the corresponding basin organisation or by the competent hydraulic administration.

The OurMED Spanish demo site of Albufera Natural Park falls under the regulatory framework of the hydrological plan of the Júcar Hydrographic Demarcation for the 2022-2027 term (CHJ, 2023), which was approved by Royal Decree 35/2023²⁴, dated January 24, and authored by the Júcar Basin Water Authority, is the territorial jurisdiction of the Júcar Water Authority. It was delineated in Article 2.3 of Royal Decree 125/2007²⁵, dated February 2.

The Albufera Natural Park's water management is also regulated by Decree 71/1993²⁶ dated May 31, of the Valencian Government, regarding the legal regime of the Albufera Park and by the Special Plan for the Albufera, which acknowledges the environmental, historical, and cultural importance of the area. This plan details measures for conservation and sustainable development, prioritizing the protection of biodiversity,

²¹ <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/l/2001/07/05/10/con>

²² <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=DOUE-L-2000-82524>

²³ <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2001-14276>

²⁴ <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2023/01/24/35>

²⁵ <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2007/02/02/125>

²⁶ https://dogv.gva.es/portal/ficha_disposicion_pc.jsp?sig=1546/1993&L=1

natural resources, and cultural heritage. It encompasses strategies for ecosystem conservation, water resource management, flora and fauna protection, and land use planning. Serving as a consensus solution among all administrations, it aims to facilitate the attainment of the water body's environmental objectives (CHJ, 2019).

In the context of hydrological planning, the Special Plan Albufera is first mentioned in Royal Decree 595/2014²⁷, which sanctions the Hydrological Plan of the Júcar Hydrographic Demarcation. This plan aims to achieve ecological potential in the Albufera.

5.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

The Júcar Water Authority (CHJ), a public entity under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Ecological Transition, establishes the allotments of water resources for irrigation demands in the Basin Management Plan. This Plan, having the rank of law, is reviewed every six years but the allotments can be modified according to extreme circumstances such as long drought periods. The irrigation allotments are very important in water balance because *return flows*, those supplied but not used, end up in the lake. As lower the assigned flows from rivers Turia and Júcar to crops, lower the inflows to Albufera Lake. This has been observed over the past 20 years, because of changes in irrigation techniques upstream of Natural Park, transitioning from surface irrigation to drip irrigation.

The second main decision-maker is the Drainage Board (DB). An organism independent from CHJ but with authority in water lake management. Until 2017 and since the XIX century, the DB decided the water level according to rice production. In other words: from the point of view of DB, the Albufera lake is a reservoir. The water level is controlled by opening/closing the connecting gates to the sea. In 2017, the control shall lie with the Autonomous Community and since then, some environmental constraints have been introduced but without forgetting the farmers.

In brief: CHJ makes decisions about inflows and DB about outflows.

The control of gates before 2017 resulted in tensions between farmers and fishermen because fishing productivity was reduced.

A third actor plays a minor role. The irrigation community of *Oro*, a sector of rice paddies close to Valencia city, decided some years ago to ensure the water supply by using reclaimed waters from Pinedo's WWTP, the biggest of Valencia. In this case, the regional government using the Public Entity for Wastewater Sanitation of the Valencian Community (EPSAR) gives the corresponding permits.

The priority every year is ensuring the crop production. If after the campaign there is enough water in reservoirs, between mid-October and mid-February rice paddies are flooded after harvesting. It is a traditional management named *perellonà*. CHJ decides, year by year, how much water can be used or none.

²⁷ <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2014-7371>

Figure 20 Organisational structure of water governance authorities in Spain.

5.3.3 Analysis

Water management in la Albufera Natural Park is in permanent conflict between agricultural activities and wetland environmental conservation.

According to the conclusions of Jégou and Sanchis-Ibor (2019), it would be necessary to create a transversal coordination office integrating all the institutions. Júcar Water Authority, Regional Administration and Valencia City Council tried to go this way when promoting in 2019 the *Plan Especial Albufera*, a framework for the water management in the Natural Park. After different meetings with administrations and stakeholders, the plan was presented to the Governing Board of Natural Park.

Some of the proposed measures are about water governance:

- Improvement of coordination between public administration involved.
- Improvement of coordination with Irrigation Communities, Fishermen's Guilds and other groups involved.
- Establishment of collaboration agreements with the Irrigation Communities.

5.4 References

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6 Konya, Turkey

6.1 System Characterization

The Konya Closed Basin (KCB), situated in Central Anatolia, is the largest endorheic basin in Turkey, encompassing a total area of 49,963 km². The basin occupies 6.4% of the country's land area. There are two main water bodies in the basin, one of them on the west side (Lake Beyşehir) and the other on the north side (Lake Tuz). The center and north parts of the basin have a lower elevation than the west and east parts. One of Turkey's twenty-five watersheds, the Konya Closed Basin, has long been the nation's main hub for wheat production. In addition, 60% of Turkey's overall salt production originates from this basin, specifically from Tuz Lake (JMO, 2010). Consequently, the inhabitants of the area have a longstanding tradition of engaging in farming, and the industrial output heavily relies on agricultural produce. In recent years, there has been a notable increase in both industrial and agricultural production, leading to an expansion of the region's contribution to the national economy and commerce.

Some surface water sources in the basin, like Beyşehir Lake, are important sites for various bird species. This lake, a class-A wetland, is vital for ecological balance, water system regulation, and biodiversity conservation in the basin. There are thirty-two islets in the lake, all of varying sizes. However, as a result of the significant amount of water used for irrigation from this source, it led to the formation of a muddy area in 1990. Since 1991, the Turkish Ministry of Culture has granted this lake 1st-degree Natural Protection Status. Despite having legal protection, the lake faces difficulties such as fluctuations in water levels brought on by insufficient regulations, excessive vegetation growth, fishing activities, urban development, and water contamination (Dursun, 2010).

The basin has a semi-arid climate with hot and dry summers and cold and dry winters, with annual precipitation ranging between 280 and 350 mm (FAO & GEF, 2019). Rainfall occurs mostly in the winter and spring seasons and is limited or zero in the summer. Despite being historically known for wheat production, farmers in the basin have been increasingly choosing crops with higher water demands such as sugar beets, corn and alfalfa for economic motivations. However, with the adoption of crops that are high in water demand, the issue of water scarcity and sustainable use of water resources in the basin also became vital for the future of the basin. The State Hydraulic Works (DSI) has constructed a number of channels and tunnels as well as unnatural water storages to transport and distribute water from Lake Beyşehir to the basin's center for use in agricultural and domestic demand sites. The most important channel is the Beyşehir-Sugla-Apa (BSA) channel which provides water supply to most agricultural regions in the Beyşehir and Konya-Cumra subbasins.

6.1.1 Main issues

Overexploitation of surface water resources is one of the main issues in the Konya Closed Basin. The water demand is high for irrigation purposes, making up to 90% of the basin's water potential, creating an almost 2 billion m³ deficit yearly. Rapid depletion in groundwater resources also increases the demand for surface water resources. Lake Beyşehir, as the main surface water resource, is under high pressure for agricultural water supply as well as domestic use in the basin. However, the water levels in the lake have

been much less than desired for the last years; the situation is exacerbated with a trend of decreasing precipitation. The depleting groundwater and surface water levels pose severe threats. The formation of sinkholes due to excessive and misuse of groundwater and the drying up of many wetlands, which are important hotspots for biodiversity in the basin, are among the problems faced in the basin.

In addition, the water level of Lake Beysehir, Turkey's largest freshwater lake, has decreased significantly and some of the endemic fish species in the lake are under threat, which is also a vital problem. Another fundamental issue in the basin is that the sharing of water leads to conflicts both within the management and at the local level in the multi-sectoral basin. Many projects and plans are planned and implemented such as inter-basin water transfer projects. However, even with the big-scale projects, the rate of meeting agricultural water demand is predicted to decrease significantly in severe drought scenarios, including in areas with important surface water resources (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2018). A monitoring program in the Konya Closed Basin assessed water quality at 62 points, finding 18% of water bodies in good condition, 34% moderate, 3% poor, and 12% weak; 25% are unknown. Lake Beysehir has moderate ecological conditions. About 56.5% of water bodies fail chemical status analysis, with 5% passing; 38% are unknown.

6.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder mapping and discovering the intricacy of the network of governance regarding surface water resources is key to understanding the complex dynamics in Konya Closed Basin. Diverse stakeholders from different sectors with different incentives are at play in the basin, contributing to the creation of multifaceted conflicts. Below, 3 graphs can be seen. Table 14 demonstrates the classification of stakeholders according to their strength in social, economic and human capitals; empty cells represent NA, light green represents low level, mid-green represents medium level, and dark green represents high level of respective capitals. Figure 21 shows the stakeholders' allocation on the power/interest matrix. Lastly, Table 15 shows stakeholder classification based on their status and governance scale. Together, they offer valuable insight on power and governance dynamics on surface water governance in the basin as well as in the country on a larger scale.

Table 14 Classification of stakeholders based on their stock of resources.

Stakeholders	Social Capital	Economic Capi	Human Capital
Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry			
State Hydraulic Works (DSİ)			
State Hydraulic Works 4th District Office (DSİ 4th Dist.)			
SYGM			
SUEN			
Directorate of Institute of Agricultural Economics and Policy Development			
General Directorate of Agricultural Reform			
General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM)			
Agriculture and Rural Development Support Institution (TKDK)			
General Directorate for the Protection of Natural Assets			
General Directorate for Combating Desertification and Erosion			
Konya Provincial Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry			
District Directorates of Agriculture and Forestry			
General Directorate of Nature Conservation and National Parks Beyşehir Chief			
MEVKA			
KOP BKİ			
Konya Metropolitan Municipality			
Beyşehir Municipality			
KOSKİ			
Ova Irrigation Union			
Çumra Irrigation Union			
Seydişehir Irrigation Union			
Konya Seker A.S.			
Fishermen			
Individual Irrigators (Farmer & Animal Husbandman)			
IFAD			
UNDP			
WWF TR			
Nature Conservation Centre (DKM)			
Nature Association			
Yolda Initiative			
Beyşehir Culture and Tourism Association			
Rural Development Cooperatives			
Irrigation Cooperatives			
Çaglayan Agricultural Irrigation Cooperative			
Irrigation Cooperatives Union			
Çumra Chamber of Agriculture			
Bozkır Chamber of Agriculture			
Beyşehir Chamber of Agriculture			
Seydişehir Chamber of Agriculture			
Karatay Chamber of Agriculture			
Fisheries Cooperative			
Academics			

Figure 21 Stakeholder grid based on power/interest in Konya, Turkey (detailed version can be found via this [link](#)).

Table 15 Stakeholders classification based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local) in Konya, Turkey.

	STATE	MARKET	CIVIL
NATIONAL	<p>Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Directorate of Nature Conservation and National Parks - SYGM - General Directorate of Agricultural Reform - TAGEM - DSI - SUEEN - TKDK - General Directorate of Turkish Sugar Factories Inc. <p>Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change</p>		<p>International Organisations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IFAD UNDP WWF Türkiye

	- General Directorate for the Protection of Natural Assets - General Directorate for Combating Desertification and Erosion		
			Nature Conservation Center (DKM) Nature Association Yolda Initiative
REGIONAL / BASIN SCALE	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry - Konya Provincial Directorate of Agriculture - DSİ 4th Regional Directorate	Konya Şeker/Torku	Academicians
	Ministry of Industry and Technology - MEVKA - KOP BKİ		
	Konya Metropolitan Municipality - KOSKİ		
SCALE	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry - District Directorates of Agriculture and Forestry - Irrigation Unions (Ova, Çumra, Seydişehir) - Nature Conservation and National Parks Beyşehir Chief Office	Self-irrigators Fishermen (Individual)	Rural Development Cooperatives Irrigation Cooperatives Union of Irrigation Cooperatives Chambers of Agriculture (Çumra, Beyşehir, Bozkır, Seydişehir, Karatay) Çağlayan Agricultural Irrigation Cooperative Beyşehir Fisheries Cooperative
			Beyşehir Culture and Tourism Association
	Beyşehir Municipality		

6.2.1 State Actors

Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (Central Organization): The Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry is the highest relevant and responsible institution related to surface water governance in the country. Although its economic capital is high, its engagement with other relevant stakeholders in the field is lower than desired partly due to being a central organization in the capital city. The meritocracy of the officials are often questioned by the local population and among local stakeholders, creating a distrust.

General Directorate of Water Management (SYGM): SYGM (Su Yönetimi Genel Müdürlüğü) is a regulatory management body that operates at national scale, under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. It has six departments working on basin management, water quality, monitoring and water information system department, flood and drought management, research and assessment, water law and policy, and therefore has a significant impact at local scale. Although planning and designing the necessary policies and regulations is the primary competence and expertise of SYGM, implementing the developed policies and management plans is not in the scope of SYGM's competence and area of primary interest (Su Yönetimi Genel Müdürlüğü, n.d.). The competency levels of officials of SYGM regarding water management and work in accordance with latest scientific findings; however, as a policy-making body, it lacks necessary relations in the field with local population due to their organizational structure.

SUEN: SUEN works as a think tank for developing sustainable water policies and strategies both on a national and international level.

State Hydraulic Works (DSI) & DSI 4th District Office: The State Hydraulic Works General Directorate's mission involves the utilisation of the country's water resources in accordance with science and technology, focusing on the development of water and related soil resources in line with environmental sensitivity and sustainability principles. DSI is responsible for planning, managing, developing, and operating all water resources in the country, operating within the Central Government Budget and under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. The Directorate prioritises its activities, particularly in dam construction, a common point of the four aforementioned purposes. Consequently, it is recognized as an organisation that constructs dams in the country and is an authoritative institution in the allocation of various uses for the country's water resources (Devlet Su İşleri Genel Müdürlüğü, n.d.). The State Hydraulic Works, both the Central Organisation in Ankara and the 4th District Office, have high levels of influence and interest. The Central Organization of State Hydraulic Works has no direct engagement with the local population. On the other hand, the 4th District Office as the implementing body has a medium level of social capital. It is considered to be an aspect for improvement in its organization.

Directorate of Institute of Agricultural Economics and Policy Development: The directorate of the Institute is to inform decision-making bodies both in the public and private sector, especially the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, through the means of conducting or commissioning economic research on related areas. Works as a research and consulting body for improved policies and decisions based on their research results.

General Directorate of Agricultural Reform: The General Directorate of Agricultural Reform funds extensively rural development projects in close coordination with national and international stakeholders and institutions.

TAGEM: TAGEM is a policy developing body that works under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry to ensure accessibility of quality agricultural products, sustainable use of agricultural and ecological resources and implement policies to raise the living standards in rural areas of the country. It designs and implements several sector based policies.

TKDK: The Agricultural Development Support Institution (TKDK) is a public institution established to ensure the sustainability of rural development in Turkey. The institution

aims to implement rural development programs effectively by using the resources provided by the European Union, national and international organizations. Working in line with the principles and objectives set out in national development plans and strategies, TKDK develops and implements projects to support economic development in rural areas, increase agricultural production and raise rural living standards.

General Directorate for the Protection of Natural Assets: The directorate's responsibility is to determine the procedures and principles regarding the registration, approval and announcement of national parks, nature parks, nature monuments, nature conservation areas, wetlands and other areas with similar protection status and to register the boundaries of these areas. It is to determine the procedures and principles regarding the determination, registration, approval, amendment and announcement of natural assets and natural protected areas and special environmental protection zones and to determine and register the boundaries of these areas, to manage and ensure their management.

General Directorate for Combating Desertification and Erosion: Previously established under the now defunct Ministry of Forestry and Water Affairs, the General Directorate for Combating Desertification and Erosion is currently under the Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Forestry, which determines policies and strategies related to soil protection, development of natural resources, desertification and erosion control activities and ensures cooperation and coordination between institutions and organizations.

Provincial and District Directorates of Agriculture and Forestry: The Provincial Directorates of Agriculture and Forestry, along with the District Directorates of Agriculture and Forestry, play a crucial role in the development and enhancement of agricultural practices within their respective regions. The District Directorates are responsible for various tasks, including collecting and proposing necessary information for the preparation of programs and projects aimed at the development of the district and the improvement of farmers' income and living standards. They implement and evaluate relevant portions of programs and projects, conduct training programs for farmers, assist in the establishment of farms based on sample farm development plans, and identify and communicate agricultural input needs to the provincial directorate.

On the other hand, the Provincial Directorates of Agriculture and Forestry have a broader set of responsibilities. They conduct agricultural inventories, prepare and disseminate agricultural extension programs, collaborate with stakeholders for program implementation, organise trials and demonstrations in collaboration with research institutions, address farmers' issues, facilitate processing and marketing of agricultural products, predict agricultural product yields, assess risk criteria in animal and plant health, and formulate plans to prevent the spread of infectious diseases. They also manage animal breeding activities, oversee quarantine services, monitor the production and distribution of agricultural products, and enforce regulations related to food safety. Although they are the regulatory and implementation bodies of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry in districts, they have a medium level of economic and social capital along with a medium level of know-how.

General Directorate of Nature Conservation and National Parks Beyşehir Chief Office: Beyşehir Chief Office for the nature conservation and national parks works under the

Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. Their scope of responsibility is to protect, govern the designated national park area around Lake Beyşehir, though the protection of the lake itself is not under the chief office's scope of responsibility.

Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration (KOP BKI): Konya Plains Project (KOP) Regional Development Administration (BKI), established in 2011, plays a pivotal role in accelerating the development of the KOP Region, comprising Konya which is the centre of KOP BKI, Aksaray, Karaman, and Niğde provinces. Operating under the Ministry of Industry and Technology, KOP BKI's primary responsibilities include preparing action plans to ensure the harmonious execution of projects and activities by relevant institutions, coordinating their implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. KOP BKI is one of the institutions with the highest levels of influence and interest regarding surface water management in the Konya Closed Basin. However, similar to other highly influential stakeholders, it has a deficit of local engagement. This translates onto projects that might hinder the socio-economic conditions of the local population as KOP BKI is the financing body of many large-scale projects.

Mevlana Development Agency (MEVKA): Mevlana Development Agency is an institution working under the Ministry of Industry and Technology, established to promote cooperation between sectors and institutions for regional development.

Konya Metropolitan Municipality: Konya Metropolitan Municipality is a local governance institution. Its population is 2,277,017 as of the end of 2021 and it is the 6th most populous province in Turkey.

Beyşehir Municipality: Beyşehir Municipality is the local governance institution in the Beyşehir District which includes Lake Beyşehir. Although it has long been considered as one of the strong institutions that support activism and conservation efforts for the lake, currently it does not carry out practices towards the conservation of the lake such as awareness building and lobbying.

KOSKI: KOSKI meets the domestic and industrial water needs within the borders of Konya Metropolitan Municipality; wastewater collection, treatment and redistribution are also among the main duties of KOSKI.

Irrigation Unions: The irrigation unions play a crucial role in the rational use of the country's surface water resources for irrigation purposes, in coordination with DSI. They are tasked with operating, maintaining, and managing irrigation facilities approved by DSI, as well as developing new projects to enhance these facilities. The unions are not to pursue profit in their activities related to the operation, maintenance, and management of transferred facilities. User service fees are designated every year accordingly. The law dictates that all revenues collected from water user service fees, penalties, donations, and other income sources should be entirely allocated to the operation, maintenance, and management responsibilities of the transferred facilities. Irrigation unions have a high level of interest regarding surface water governance with a high level of local engagement. They are the regulatory bodies and responsible for the regulation of irrigation water distribution. As the primary authority for the farmers to engage with, their position as stakeholders is important.

Beyşehir Forest Management Directorate

6.2.2 Market Actors

Konya Seker A.S.: Konya Seker is one of the main market actors in agricultural production in the basin regarding the trade of many agricultural products such as sugar beets and potatoes both in national and international markets.

Fishermen

Self-irrigators: Individuals who engage in husbandry and farming, using Lake Beysehir and other small-scale water reservoirs for their activities.

6.2.3 Civil Actors

IFAD: IFAD funds many rural development projects in the basin among other activities and projects.

UNDP: UNDP has been conducting several rural development projects especially working in the South of the Basin.

WWF TR: WWF TR published many substantial reports on water use and governance in the basin in the past, though their level of activity has decreased in the basin in recent years.

Nature Conservation Centre (DKM): Nature Conservation Centre works for ensuring the effective conservation of biological diversity and sustainable management of natural resources based on scientific approaches. The centre has been doing many projects in the basin focusing on a variety of topics such as sustainable water management and agricultural production and biodiversity monitoring.

Nature Association: Nature Association is an Izmir based NGO mainly focused on wetland protection and biodiversity monitoring and assessment.

Yolda Initiative: Yolda Initiative is a nature and biodiversity conservation initiative that finds value in the promotion of traditional cultures that benefit biodiversity and contribute to efforts of climate change mitigation. Sarıkeçili mobile pastoralists are an old community that migrate to Konya Closed Basin for the winter. However, the construction of dams and tunnels, increasing areas of orchards and general agricultural land in the basin put their livelihood at risk. Sarıkeçili mobile pastoralists are not included in policymaking processes, often leading to policymaking processes and implementation without considering them. This creates a deficit in inclusion in the surface water governance in the region. Some Yolda Initiative's works can be considered as advocacy for their rights and inclusion.

Beysehir Culture and Tourism Association: The association was formed and ran by local residents for the purpose of promoting the Beysehir district and Lake Beysehir through activities such as outdoor sports and hosting international cycling events. The basin's main resource of surface water is Lake Beyşehir and its level of elevation has been decreasing due to overexploitation for irrigation and changing patterns of precipitation. Currently the association operates under the Municipality of Beysehir. During an interview with a local resident and Lake Beysehir conservation activist who is also an active member of the association, it was mentioned that it is not easy to stand up and lobby against further water extraction from the lake. Since the municipality is linked to a political party and the association is now operating under the Beysehir Municipality, the

management council of the association is uneasy at standing against the decisions of water management authorities in the region.

Chambers of Agriculture: Chambers of agriculture aim to provide professional services and their objectives include meeting the common needs of farmers, facilitating their professional activities, promoting the development of the agricultural profession in line with public interests, fostering honesty and trust in the relationships among professionals and the public. Primary responsibilities and powers of the Chambers include gathering agricultural-related news and information, conducting necessary studies and gathering key statistics, providing information and records upon request, making recommendations to public and private institutions, collaborating with trade and industry chambers, and engaging in educational, promotional, and advisory activities to support agricultural development. Other key functions involve maintaining farmer records, organizing and participating in fairs and exhibitions related to agricultural production and development. The project focused on 4 main agricultural chambers in the basin. Beyşehir Chamber of Agriculture with 7000 active members, Bozkır Chamber of Agriculture with around 4000 active members, Seydişehir Chamber of Agriculture and Çumra Chamber of Agriculture with over 8000 active members with relatively bigger land-holdings. The chambers of agriculture differ from one another in their economic and social capacities. Where there are farmers with stronger solidarity and knowledge networks and higher economic capital such as in the case of Çumra, the chamber of agriculture has higher levels of local engagement, trust and power among other stakeholders. They have higher capacity for lobbying and networking, often leading to being an affluent and well-acknowledged stakeholder in the basin. On the other hand, where there are comparatively weaker farmer networks with less social and economic capital such as in Bozkır, the chamber of agriculture is found to be less affluent of a stakeholder. Political lobbying is an important aspect/issue of local governance of water in the basin; the more affluent a chamber of agriculture gets, the more power they hold within the governance sphere.

Rural Development Cooperatives: There are numerous rural development cooperatives actively working in the basin in cooperation with national and international NGOs for project management, local engagement and funding for many activities.

Irrigation Cooperatives: Irrigation cooperatives mainly use groundwater for irrigation in the basin with a few exceptions. Although the majority do not actively use surface water resources of the basin, they are still among important stakeholders mainly due to fastly decreasing groundwater levels in the basin. As a result, the demand for surface water resources for irrigation purposes increases rapidly. Therefore, the future of groundwater and surface water resources are interrelated.

Caglayan Agricultural Irrigation Cooperative: Caglayan Agricultural Irrigation cooperative operates in the district of Bozkır, using surface water for irrigation purposes. Their main water resources are small dams and ponds.

Union of Irrigation Cooperatives: Irrigation cooperatives in the basin are united under this union which has over 300 cooperatives and operates groundwater wells. Assistance in operation of irrigation facilities, educational activities regarding irrigation and farming, giving financial loans for cooperatives and multisectoral cooperation are some of the union's main activities. The current head of the union is a well-known figure in the region

and often makes public appearances in local media advocating for the irrigation cooperatives in the basin.

Fisheries Cooperative: The cooperative mainly works for the fishermen who are making their livelihoods off of Lake Beysehir.

Academicians: The basin is home to many universities. There are numerous academicians who are conducting research on diverse topics such as water governance in the region, crop patterns, ecological conditions of water resources. However, there are not many who take a radical stance on the inefficient and harmful agricultural policies and practices in the region. With some exceptions, the current severe conditions of the surface water governance issues and its possible improvement in the basin have not been a focal point as much as it should have been.

Konya Chamber of Agricultural Engineers

6.3 Governance Analysis

The effective governance of surface water resources in the Konya Closed Basin plays a crucial role in the sustainable management of the basin's natural resources. Governance analysis involves examining the institutional structures, main policies, and regulations that govern water allocation, use and management in the basin. In this section, the aim is to uncover the effectiveness, efficiency as well as gaps and weaknesses of the existing governance framework in addressing the challenges faced in the basin such as water scarcity issues, environmental degradation and competing water demands. By analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of the current governance mechanisms, relevant stakeholders and decision makers can identify areas for improvement and implement strategies to ensure and enhance the sustainable management of surface water resources in the Konya Closed Basin.

6.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

Turkey's Water Code was adopted in 1926, almost a century ago, however, it has not been updated since then. There have been recent attempts to update the code in the last two decades, however there has not been an absolute output yet. In the meantime, there have clearly been many changes, developments and sectoral growths that have changed the amount and nature of water use in the country, which necessitates a comprehensive update of the water code in line with today's dynamics and future scenarios. The basin's water resources are being managed closely and utilised for sustaining water supply and addressing challenges related to water scarcity. Here is an overview of the key aspects of water management and usage in the basin:

- River Basin Management Plan: A National River Basin Management Plan alongside basin-specific management plans based on the former has been crafted by the General Directorate of Water Management which operates under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. The plan includes specific measures and actions that are monitored through the National Water Information System to guide water resource management. It aims to ensure the sustainable management of river basins in Turkey in accordance with the EU environmental and water management standards due to the country's candidacy. The KCB Management Plan underscores the urgent need for holistic basin management to address environmental challenges, emphasizing compliance with EU Water Framework Directive and the formulation of effective

measures to safeguard water quality and biodiversity in the Konya Closed Basin. However, when examining the ecological, chemical, and environmental conditions of various surface water reserves, a significant majority is at moderate or high risk, with most unable to meet expected criteria. Factors such as high agricultural demand, inefficient irrigation techniques, increased evaporation due to rising temperatures, and reduced rainfall contribute to the exacerbated condition. Holistic basin management is deemed necessary to address these critical challenges according to the KCB Management Plan.

- Sectoral Water Allocation Plans: To ensure efficient and sustainable use of water resources, Sectoral Water Allocation Plans have been developed for the Konya Closed Basin (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2018). These plans prioritize the allocation of water based on the basin's hydrological structure, climatic conditions, drought severity, and socioeconomic factors. However, the highest priority is always given to drinking and domestic water supply as well as environmental water needs. One of the significant efforts within the Sectoral Water Allocation Plans is the optimization of crop patterns, particularly in the agricultural sector. By determining water requirements in advance and predicting potential drought conditions, optimal crop patterns are established to allow continuous production and increase the net income of farmers, even in the face of decreasing water resources. The economic benefits of water allocation and the potential social impacts are evaluated in the Sectoral Water Allocation Plans. Action Plans have been prepared, specifying the responsible institutions and organizations. These plans are to be regularly monitored to ensure the implementation of the defined measures. The Sectoral Water Allocation Plan and Action Plan for the Konya Closed Basin are currently in effect. However, these plans are not implemented well enough or they fail to observe important factors. As it is mentioned in the Grand National Assembly of Turkey Research Commission Report (2021), the water scarcity and distribution issues are not to be solved unless the crops which are high in water demand are opted out from the agricultural production in the basin.
- Drought Management Plan: A drought management plan, as it was deemed necessary in the National River Basin Management Plan (2014), was developed for Konya Closed Basin to address potential water scarcity issues. The plan was initially published in 2015 and updated in 2023 to incorporate changing climatic conditions and their impacts of water resources. The Konya Closed Basin Drought Management Plan adopts an integrated watershed management approach to mitigate the adverse impacts of drought on production resources and socio-economic activities in the Konya Closed Basin. The plan considers the basin's water budget, sensitivity to drought, and employs drought indices, indicators, threshold values, and sectoral impact analyses (Tarım Reformu Genel Müdürlüğü, 2022). This plan was later supported by an action plan called “Strategy and Action Plan for Combating Agricultural Drought in Turkey (2023-2027)” crafted by the General Directorate of Agricultural Reform (2022). In this document, the importance of the situation is further recognised and it is stated that the use of water resources is at an even more critical level, especially in the context of the practice of using water resources in agricultural activities, but the impact of action plans on outputs is not sufficient due to various deep and structural problems and weaknesses such as lack of coordination

between the institutions authorized with water management, the fact that a comprehensive water law has still not been enacted and the uncertainty of the measurable criteria of the action plans issued on the subject.

6.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

There are several key institutions mainly operating under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry in the decision-making sphere regarding surface water governance in Konya Closed Basin.

SYGM is one of the main decision-makers established to manage water on a basin basis with a participatory and integrated approach to protect, develop, control and sustainably use the country's water resources in terms of both quantity and quality. The relevant units of SYGM on surface water management are Department of Basin Management, Department of Monitoring Quality and Information System, Department of Flood and Drought Management, Department of Water Efficiency, and Department of Water Law and Policy.

State Hydraulic Works (DSI) is the practical owner of water resources in the country. DSI has the control over and the responsibility of the management, allocation and distribution of the surface water resources. Along with the relevant directorates working under the General Directorate of DSI, the important directorates working under the 4th Regional Directorate of DSI are as follows: Basin Management, Monitoring and Allocations Branch Directorate, Operation and Maintenance Branch Directorate, Planning Branch Directorate, Flood Control Branch Directorate, Irrigation Branch Directorate, Dams and HEPP Branch Directorate, Konya Plain Irrigation Operation and Maintenance Branch Directorate.

The General Directorate of Nature Conservation and National Parks is another central unit of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. Looking at the departments working under it, it appears to have a comprehensive structure and organization, but in the context of Beysehir Lake, this institution, which is responsible for the control and protection of the area around the lake within the scope of the national park status, not the lake itself, does not have any authority over the water source.

The General Directorate of Agricultural Reform is also an important institution in terms of policy development and is one of the central units under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. Some of the important units operating under the General Directorate are as follows: Department of Rural Development, Department of Irrigation Systems and Agricultural Infrastructure Services, Department of Agricultural Land Management, Department of Protection of Agricultural Environment and Natural Resources.

Under the General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM), there are R&D departments related to agriculture and animal husbandry. There are also departments actively working on agricultural economy and natural resource management.

6.3.3 Analysis

Examining the social, economic, and human capital of stakeholders involved in surface water governance in the Konya closed basin reveals crucial insights. One key finding is the

limited local engagement of affluent stakeholders who are also policymakers and decision-makers. Many influential state stakeholders have little to no social capital, which is concerning for effective and equitable governance. The framing of water scarcity issues by policymakers often overlooks socioeconomic vulnerabilities and increasing water demands, focusing instead on natural drought conditions. This de-politicizes the issue and fails to address the complex social, economic, and political factors at play. Moreover, state stakeholders may struggle to mobilize social change due to political interests, power dynamics, and limited resources, exacerbating social and environmental issues.

Despite the pressing issues in surface water governance in the Konya closed basin, there is a noticeable absence of active engagement from non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in the field. The limited presence of NGOs working on water governance and related topics in the basin suggests a gap in civil society's involvement in addressing these critical challenges. This absence highlights the need for greater collaboration and participation from diverse stakeholders, including NGOs, to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of surface water governance efforts in the region.

Meritocracy is another issue in surface water governance in the basin, with local stakeholders criticizing Ministry officials for misleading or false statements, leading to a growing distrust. This lack of trust hinders coordination efforts within and between stakeholders at different scales. Inefficient coordination within and between state institutions, along with ambiguous ownership of Lake Beysehir, further complicates governance efforts. While there are promising plans and strategies, overlapping responsibilities and fragmented governance undermine efforts to improve surface water governance in the basin.

Valuable insights from workshops highlighted several key issues affecting surface water resources in the basin. Inefficient and ineffective agricultural policies, along with a lack of basin-specific crop planning, are major problems. Stakeholders also called for improved inter-institutional communication and cooperation. The lack of engagement by central ministries and regional officials, inefficient irrigation infrastructures, slow adaptation of new technologies, and inadequate monitoring systems were identified as critical issues. Suggestions included promoting crops with low water demand, implementing pasture and water laws more strictly, and establishing a supra-institutional water authority for better coordination. Human pressures on the environment were recognized as a complex issue intersecting with various sectors, with suggestions for population control, improved urbanization management, and policy changes.

The discussions during the workshop revealed a consensus among stakeholders on the need for comprehensive and integrated strategies to address these challenges. There was a recognition of the need for basin-specific approaches that consider the unique social, economic, and environmental characteristics of the Konya closed basin. Stakeholders emphasized the importance of participatory decision-making processes that involve all relevant stakeholders, including local communities, in the development and implementation of water governance strategies. Overall, the workshop provided valuable insights into the complexities of surface water governance in the Konya closed basin and the need for collaborative and sustainable solutions.

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7 Medjerda, Tunisia

7.1 System Characterization

The Medjerda river is shared by Tunisia and Algeria and produces more than 1 Billion cubic meters (Bm³) of surface water per year, which irrigates an area of approximately 52,740 ha, in the basin, with additional irrigated areas outside the hydro-system through water transfer. The region experiences an average annual precipitation of 350-600 millimeters, with an average of 40 to 70 rainy days per year (Rajosoa et al., 2021).

More than 70% of the watershed is used for agriculture, with a focus on rainfed crops such as cereals and fodder, while irrigated crops like vegetables and fruits are mostly limited to areas near dam reservoirs and the lower valley. Only about a quarter of the area is covered in wooded and pastoral lands, indicating a significant level of human impact on the environment, with a trend of declining natural vegetation.

The Wadi Medjerda remains the most vulnerable river due to its morphology, which favors overflows in the part downstream of Ghardimaou and approaching the towns crossed by the watercourse (MARHP, 2023).

7.1.1 Main issues

The Medjerda basin in Tunisia faces numerous challenges in water management, including inefficiencies in governance, poor water quality, inadequate infrastructure, and unsustainable practices. The lack of coordination and information sharing among stakeholders hinders effective decision-making, while water pollution and poor treatment of wastewater threaten both ecosystems and human health. Moreover, the existing infrastructure is insufficient or poorly maintained, leading to water scarcity and waterlogging. The promotion of sustainable water use practices is also lacking, and climate change is exacerbating the problems, making it essential to develop a more adaptive and sustainable water management strategy.

7.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Considering the different dimensions of OurMED Project related to the use, distribution and management of water resources, the stakeholders mapping was carried out using the following methodology. The identification and categorization of stakeholders in the Medjerda basin, as part of the OurMED project, was an important step, providing a clear understanding of who is impacted and how they can contribute to the project's success. A comprehensive list of stakeholders was compiled through a review of scientific literature, followed by validation sessions with key-players in the water sector and academic experts to ensure its accuracy. This allowed for the creation of a detailed stakeholder matrix (Table 16), which classified stakeholders based on their level of interest and engagement in water resources management, exploitation, and protection.

Table 16 List of Stakeholders classified based on their level of interest and engagement in the Medjerda basin, Tunisia.

Stakeholders	Authority	Interest/Engagement in OurMED
Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fisheries (MARHP)	National Authority	Impact of climate change on water resources in the Medjerda basin
Ministry of Environment (ME)	National Authority	Monitoring of water quality and point focal for climate change
Ministry of Public Health (MSP)	National Authority	Water quality control
Ministry of Equipment, Housing, and Territories' Management (MEHAT)	National Authority	Flood management in urban areas
General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE)	National Authority	Monitoring of water resources
General Directorate of Dams and Hydraulic Structures (DGBGTH)	National Authority	Dam Management
General Directorate for Management and Conservation of Agricultural Land (DGAFTA)	National Authority	Soil and water conservation
General Directorate of Rural Engineering and Water Exploitation (DGGREE)	National Authority	Irrigation and drinking water in rural areas
Northern Water Canal, Adductions and Exploitation Company (SECADENORD)	National Authority	Water transfer
National Water Distribution Company (SONEDE)	National Authority	Drinking water
Regional districts of SONEDE	Regional Authority	Drinking water
National Office for Sanitation (ONAS)	Regional Authority	Waste water
National Agency for Environment Protection (ANPE)	National Authority	Monitoring of water quality
Bureau of Water Planning and Hydraulic Equilibriums (BPEH)	National Authority	Hydraulic resources' planning
General Directorate of Investment, Funding, and Professional Organizations (DGFOP)	National Authority	Investment in water sector
Academics	Research institutes	Research and development programs
Tunisian Union of Agriculture and Fisheries (UTAP)	National Authority	Interest in the multi-sectoral water management and climate change
National Institute of Field Crops (INGC)	Research institute	Impact of climate change on water resources in the Medjerda basin
Agricultural Extension and Training Agency (AVFA)	Public administrative establishment	Promotion of sustainable development
North West Office for Sylvo-Pastoral Development (ODESPANO)	Public non administrative establishment	Promotion of sustainable development
Center Medjerda	Regional Authority	Dam operations
Regional Agricultural services of Beja, Jendouba, Siliana, ElKef, Mannouba, Ariana, Bizerte (CRDAs)	Regional Authority	Interest in the multi-sectoral water management and climate change

Agricultural Development Groups (7 governorates)	Local Authority	Irrigation or Rural Drinking Water resource management
Municipalities	Local Authority	Waste and drinking water supply authorization
FAO, GIZ, KfW, AFD, FFEM, BAD, BID, BM-FMI, Arab Bank for Economic Development in Africa...	International organizations	Design, funding, technical support...
NGOs	NGO	Water preservation
Tunisian Water Observatory (OTE)	NGO	Water preservation
ONAGRI	National Authority	Data sharing
Tunisian Agency for the Promotion of Investment in Agriculture (APIA)	National Authority	Funding and incentive
Assembly of People's Representatives (ARP)	National Authority	Regulation
Public Agricultural Land Office (OTD)	National company	Water use
Factories	Private sector	Water pollution and overexploitation
Farmers	Private sector	Water use

A classification of stakeholders based on their relation to water resources was realized. An estimation of the importance of their role and implication in each subject matter related to every stock of resources (social, human, and economic) was done by assigning each a number ranging from +1 to +5 through meetings with experts in water resources' monitoring and management (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Classification of stakeholders based on their stock of resources in Medjerda, Tunisia.

Stakeholders were categorized based on two criteria (Power and interest) in the following clusters: high power/high interest, high power / low interest, low power/high interest, low power/low interest clusters. The clustering was made by assigning each stakeholder a number ranging from +1 to +7 for each criterion through an estimation of their involvement in the decision-making process and the interest given to each subject matter related to the water management in the Medjerda basin.

A cartesian graph (Figure 23) was drafted to semi-quantitatively evaluate the power and interest (high and low) of each stakeholder.

The differentiation per cluster provides an additional key insight and outlines the extent and imperative presence and power of the state and mainly the Ministry of Agriculture (MARHP) and the correspondent technical directorates, CRDAs, ONAS, SONEDE, and the Ministry of Environment (ME); the various associated public agencies with specific mandates, such as ODESYPANO, SECADENORD, APIA, AVFA, ONAGRI and international organizations have limited power and interest.

Civil society organizations such as non-governmental organizations (NGOs and UTAP), farmers, academics and community groups advocating for water conservation and environmental protection (municipalities and water observatory) have limited or no power despite their interests.

The parliament (ARP) in charge of regulations and mainly the approbation of the new water code, INGC, Center Medjerda and GDAs have high power but limited interest.

Figure 23 Stakeholder grid based on power/interest Medjerda, Tunisia.

A Stakeholder classification based on their status (public, private, or civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, or local) was carried out as shown in Table 17.

Table 17 Stakeholders classification based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local) Medjerda, Tunisia.

	STATE	MARKET	CIVIL
NATIONAL	Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fisheries (MARHP)	Public Agricultural Land Office (OTD)	The Tunisian Union of Agriculture and Fisheries (UTAP)
	Ministry of Environment (ME)		International organizations (FAO, GIZ, KfW, AFD, FFEM, BAD, BID, BM-FMI, Arab Bank for Economic Development in Africa...)

	Ministry of Public Health (MSP)		NGOs
	Ministry of Equipment, Housing, and Territories' Management (MEHAT)		Tunisian Water Observatory
	Northern Water Canal, Adductions and Exploitation Company (SECADENORD)		
	National Water Distribution Company (SONEDE)		
	National Observatory of Agriculture (ONAGRI)		
	Tunisian Agency for the Promotion of Investment in Agriculture (APIA)		
	Assembly of People's Representatives (ARP)		
	National Office for Sanitation (ONAS)		
	National Agency Environment Protection (ANPE)		
	Technical directorates of the (MAPRH): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE) - General Directorate of Dams and Hydraulic Structures (DGBGTH) - General Directorate of Rural Engineering and Water Exploitation (DGGREE), - General Directorate for Management and Conservation of Agricultural Land (DGACTION) - Bureau of Water Planning and Hydraulic Equilibriums (BPEH), - General Directorate of Investment Funding and Professional Organizations (DGFIOF) 		
<u>REGIONAL / BASIN SCALE</u>	Regional districts of SONED	Factories	NGOs
	Academics		
	National Institute of Field Crops (INGC)		
	Agricultural Extension and Training Agency (AVFA)		
	Regional Agricultural Services (CRDAs) (7 governorates)		
	Center Medjerda		
	North West Office for Development Sylvo-Pastoral (ODESYANO)		The Tunisian Union of Agriculture and Fisheries (UTAP)

LOCAL / SUB-BASIN SCALE	Agricultural Extension and Training Agency (AVFA)	Factories	Agricultural Development Groups (7 governorates)
	Municipalities	farmers	NGOs

7.2.1 State Actors

- The Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Fisheries (MARHP)
The Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources, and Fisheries (MARHP) is responsible for developing policies to address water stress in a climate change context, including better resource management, and a sustainable agricultural system. However, the country faces challenges such as declining agricultural crops, preserving productive lands, and developing agroecological engineering to adapt to climate change. To address these challenges, MARHP has established a national climate change committee to coordinate efforts and optimize funding opportunities to mitigate climate change impacts.
- The Ministry of Environment (ME)
The Ministry of Environment is responsible for proposing and implementing environmental protection policies, promoting sustainability, and ensuring the integration of environmental considerations into national development strategies. The ministry's duties include establishing the foundations for sustainable development, promoting environmental laws, improving environmental conditions, and managing natural resources in a sustainable way.
- The Ministry of public health (MSP)
The Ministry of Public Health is in charge of sanitary control of water, which includes ensuring the quality of drinking water, mineral water, raw used water, and treated water. MSP has the responsibility to validate the quality of drinking water considering the standards.
- The Ministry of Equipment, Housing, and Territories' Management (MEHAT)
The Ministry of Equipment, Housing and Territories' Management contributes to water sector management through the monitoring, development and control of studies and structures to protect cities and urban areas against flooding, as well as the upkeep and maintenance of city protection structures against flooding.
- Northern Water Canal, Adductions, and Exploitation Company (SECADENORD)
The SECADENORD is an essential part of Tunisia's water system, both economically and socially, as it has a strategic mission to supply around 60% of the needs of the SONEDE from raw water. This enables it to supply six million people with access to drinking water, via the Medjerda Al-Watan Al-Quibli canal and the northern water pipelines, at a rate of 320 million cubic meters per year. In addition, the company supplies irrigation water for around 55,000 hectares of irrigated land in Tunisia, representing some 150 million cubic meters per year, or around 15% of national irrigation water requirements for public irrigated areas, as well as helping the groundwater replenishment.
- National Water Distribution Company (SONEDE)
The National Water Distribution Company is a public institution responsible for managing and distributing drinking water in the country. The primary functions of the SONEDE are:
 - Designing and building infrastructure to collect and store water

- The ministry of agriculture is in charge of treating and producing drinking water for consumption, through SONEDE
- Overseeing the technical aspects of the water distribution network
- Managing commercial aspects related to subscriber services
- National Observatory of Agriculture (ONAGRI)
The National Observatory of Agriculture (ONAGRI) is a public administrative body under the authority of the Ministry of Agriculture, Hydraulic Resources, and Fisheries (MARHP). It is responsible for carrying out the following missions:
 - Set up a reliable information system for analysing the situation of the agriculture and fisheries sectors at national and international levels through relevant, reliable, and periodic indicators.
 - Collect, analyse and process national and international information and data relating to the agriculture and fisheries sector.
 - Disseminate the information and data collected and make them available to various stakeholders, such as decision-makers, planners, researchers, producers, exporters, and others...
- Assembly of People's Representatives (ARP)
The Tunisian Parliament is the bicameral institution exercising the legislative power of the Tunisian Republic.
- Technical directorates of the MARHP
- General Directorate of Water Resources Management (DGRE)
The DGRE is the institution responsible for the monitoring of water resources in order to plan the supply of drinking water and agricultural uses. Its mission is to develop, apply and monitor the national policy on water resources management, as well as the planning, implementation, and control of public policies relating to drinking water and agricultural uses, in order to guarantee the availability, quality, and access to these resources for Tunisian citizens.
- General Directorate of Dams and Hydraulic Structures (DGBGTH)
The missions of the DGBGTH are to manage, regularize, and monitor water quantity and quality from dams and their infrastructure, as well as promote of research and development in the field of hydraulic technologies, and provides the necessary water resources to be transferred by SECADENORD. The DGBGTH designs the realization of projected hydraulic structures, considering the MAHRP policy.
- General Directorate for Management and Conservation of Agricultural Land (DGACTA). The responsibilities of the DGACTA are to:
 - Draw up plans and guidelines for better preservation of natural soil, vegetation, water, and farmland resources;
 - Propose, develop, and promote all measures to ensure better use of natural resources;
 - Evaluate soil resources and their use;
 - Draw up studies and conduct research for agricultural land protection;
 - Ensure coordination between all those involved in water and soil conservation;
 - Evaluate water and soil conservation projects.
- General Directorate of Rural Engineering and Water Exploitation (DGGREE)
The DGGREE is one of the Ministry's departments mandated to provide agricultural extension services and training related to agricultural irrigation to farmers and

drinking water in rural areas as well as disseminating innovative agricultural technologies and solutions. The DGGREE is also the national institution empowered to prepare and propose laws and regulations relating to the promotion and development of the agricultural sector and the use of conventional and non-conventional water resources.

- Bureau of Planning and Hydraulic Balance (BPEH)

The BPEH's key responsibilities include planning water resource mobilization, developing non-conventional resources to meet medium and long-term demands, scheduling annual water allocations, managing risk and emergency plans, and coordinating between service providers and water users in various sectors. The BPEH developed the "Water Strategy 2050", that aims to create a national water vision and strategy for water resources up to 2050, ensuring water security and socio-economic development through efficient, equitable, and sustainable provision.

- General Directorate of Investment, Funding, and Professional Organizations (DGFIOF). The DGFIOF is not only responsible for managing and regulating water, forests, and fishing in Tunisia but also finances projects related to the agricultural sector and oversees the management of projects financed by international institutions.

- National Office for Sanitation (ONAS). The National Office for Sanitation was established in 1974 to manage the sanitation of waste water. Its missions include addressing water pollution sources, managing and maintaining sanitation infrastructure, promoting the distribution and sale of treated water and wastewater, planning and implementing sanitation projects, and developing integrated projects on water and wastewater management.

- National Agency for Environment Protection (ANPE)

The National Agency for Environment Protection was created in 1988 and is supervised by the Ministry of Environment. Its general missions include participating in developing the state's policy to tackle pollution and protect the environment, proposing measures to ensure the implementation of this policy, and addressing all sources of pollution and environmental degradation.

Tunisian Agency for the Promotion of Investment in Agriculture (APIA)

The Tunisian Agency for the Promotion of Investment in Agriculture (APIA) is a non-administrative public establishment, established in 1983. The main objective is to promote private investment in agriculture, fishing, and related services, as well as agricultural and fishing projects, through the development and transformation of these sectors.

- Regional Agricultural Services (CRDAs)

The water-related responsibilities of the Regional Agricultural Services in Tunisia include preserving natural resources, managing watersheds, constructing hydraulic structures, developing infrastructures for irrigation and drinking water in rural areas, and providing technical support to farmers, as well as offering financial incentives and authorizations to promote the sector.

- Municipalities

The municipalities within the Medjerda basin in Tunisia play crucial roles in managing the region's natural resources, ensuring sustainable development, and improving the quality of life for citizens. Some of the key missions of these municipalities include providing access to clean water and sanitation services, promoting agricultural

practices that conserve soil and water, protecting biodiversity and natural habitats, managing solid waste and wastewater, and implementing measures to mitigate the effects of climate change.

- Center Medjerda

The Center Medjerda mission, as a regional directorate located in the upstream Medjerda Basin, is to monitor the operating dams located within the basin, to coordinate water transfer with BPEH, SECADENORD, DGBGTH, MAHRP..., and to avoid flood through reservoir management. The Center Medjerda communicates water release from dams to local, regional, and national levels.

7.2.2 Market Actors

- Public Agricultural Land Office (OTD)

The Office of State Lands ensures the management and development of a significant area of state lands in Tunisia (156,000 ha). It actively participates in the diversification of agricultural and agri-food production, contributes to the national stock of strategic products and plays an important role in promoting exports of agricultural products.

- Factories

The market actors are mainly factories that could exist at regional and local levels. They are involved in the transformation and packaging of agro-industrial products such as olive extraction units, industrial tomatoes, milk industrial units... Several of these factories establish partnerships with farmers through technical support during the agricultural production process. They deeply impact water consumption used for crops growing and the selection of type of crops. Also, they impact the water quality by the water used in the industrial process, as waste.

- Farmers

Farmers in the Medjerda Basin face many challenges in producing quality crops and ensuring a sustainable livelihood, due to the vulnerability of their farming systems and increasing pressure on water resources. Farmers in the project area are the main producers and the main water users, through irrigation. Due to drought and the climate change effects, farmers are extending their irrigated area and may over irrigate when water is available. There are also some conflicts between those in the basin and those outside and also between upstream and downstream which manifest by the increasing illicit water withdrawal (from the river itself or groundwater).

7.2.3 Civil Actors

- NGOs

NGOs in the Medjerda basin play a crucial role in promoting a more open and inclusive approach to water and sanitation services by contributing to the ongoing reform process. With a highly developed fabric of NGOs, Tunisia has a wealth of expertise and knowledge that can be leveraged to support the development of sustainable water management practices, promote community engagement, and advocate for policy changes that benefit all stakeholders.

- Tunisian Union of Agriculture and Fisheries (UTAP)

The Tunisian Union of Agriculture and Fisheries (UTAP) is a professional organization that represents the interests of farmers, agricultural producers, and fishermen in Tunisia. As a major player in the country's agricultural sector, UTAP works to promote the development of agriculture and fisheries, improve the living standards of its

- members, and ensure the availability of food and agricultural products. This entity makes pressure on water authorities for more water allocated to agricultural sector.
- Agricultural Development Groups
Agricultural Development Groups (GDAs) play a crucial role in managing natural resources, such as water, forests, and pastures, in the region. As the only democratically legitimate local structures, they bring together owners and users to manage these resources. However, their members lack knowledge of democratic consultation processes and have limited technical and administrative skills. The legal framework exacerbates the issue, making it essential to establish an efficient participatory and inclusive management mechanism to ensure effective natural resource management.
 - International organizations (FAO, GIZ, KfW, AFD, FFEM, BAD, BID, BM-FMI, Arab Bank for Economic Development in Africa, etc)
These international organizations provide technical support and funding to promote the sustainable use of water resources in the region. By working together with public, private, and civil society organizations, they help to develop solutions for agricultural practices and rural development that conserve water resources.
 - Tunisian Water Observatory (OTE)
The Water Observatory is an NGO that provides data, information, and monitoring of the water sector in the region, supporting decision-making and policy development in water resources management, planning, and governance. Water observatory is one the civil society entities that (i) communicate on water in order to improve regulation, governance, and management and (ii) publish statistics (mainly on social media).

7.3 Governance Analysis

The Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources, and Fisheries (MARHP) and the technical directorates/institutions under its jurisdiction are in charge of the monitoring, management, and exploitation of water resources.

Urban flood management and general water control are under the purview of the Ministry of Public Health (MSP) and the Ministry of Equipment, Housing, and Territories' Management (MEHAT), respectively. The management of public domains, mobilization and development of water resources, water management projects, agricultural withdrawals, and the provision of water resources for domestic and other uses are the primary responsibilities of the MARHP. The General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE), the General Directorate of Rural Engineering and Water Exploitation (DGGREE), the General Directorate of Dams and Hydraulic Structures (DGBGTH), the General Directorate for Management and Conservation of Agricultural Land (DGACTA), and the Bureau of Water Planning and Hydraulic Equilibriums (BPEH) are the main departments within MARHP that play important roles in the management of water resources.

There is now a National Water Council that is meant to unite users and administration. A number of independent public companies handle various tasks, including the provision of drinking water (SONEDE), managing the canal and the Northern water supply (Northern Water Canal, Adductions and Exploitation Company; SECADENORD), which operate under the Ministry of Agriculture's supervision, and an office in charge of management and sanitation (ONAS).

Subcontracting to these companies can ultimately lead to a private sector takeover of the water sector through them. The beginning of decentralization was signaled by the replacement of the Agricultural Development Offices by the Agricultural Development Commissions in 1989. Participatory and user involvement have become more important in the current policy by setting up Collective Interest Associations (AIC) for rural water supply and public irrigated areas. The AICs are under the supervision of a Hydraulic Interest Group, which is the same as the National Water Committee in the regional area (Treyer, 2002).

Eventually, these associations developed into agricultural development groups (GDAs). Participatory management of water systems is facilitated by the GDAs, who are the main local institutions. User participation is accomplished through the GDAs. The GDAs' situation remains unchanged, and they are incapable of performing their tasks (MARHP, 2023).

7.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

The Water Code promulgated in 1975 governs the allocation of water resources and includes several articles to protect and preserve water resources. A water law reform was initiated in 2009 to reflect the actual social and economic situation in the country. The law was approved by the Council of Ministers in September 2019 for submission to Parliament. Until now the law has not yet been passed (CEDARE, 2014).

Public water policies have evolved significantly since the 1960s and remain a constant concern for public authorities. Nowadays, the agricultural sector remains the largest user, using 75.5% of resources, however, priority is given to drinking water when needs exceed availability.

From the 1960s to the 1990s, political strategies focused primarily on supply management, particularly the construction of hydraulic structures and centralized resource management. The country was committed to identifying water potential, mobilizing the resources thus inventoried and hydraulic developments. The State had to increase the rate of mobilization of water resources for the creation of irrigated areas and the establishment of modern and productive irrigated agriculture. Priority was given to large dams in the north of Tunisia and namely Medjerda Region.

The central objective of this policy was to ensure national socio-economic development, particularly in terms of food security and quality of life for citizens (FAO, 2023).

The years 1990-2010 saw increased mobilization of supply and the beginning of the transition towards demand management. On the one hand, the identified resource mobilization strategies were implemented. The primary objective of these strategies was to meet the water demand of different sectors over the coming decades, to achieve a mobilization rate of 90% of the water resources potential, and 97% of water supply, drinking water for rural areas, and to improve the quality of drinking water in urban areas.

On one hand, although it has brought social and economic progress, this supply-side policy has been the subject of criticism, particularly given its social and environmental impacts (FAO, 2023). On the other hand, the transition to demand management aimed to maintain demand at a level compatible with resources.

Centered on the use and optimal development of available resources, the objectives of the new water policy orientation were accompanied by significant reforms on the institutional level (promotion of user associations and the decentralization of water management); the legal (“polluter pays” principle), and economic (objective of “true prices”, limitation of government’ interventions). Parallel to the application of these measures during the 1990s, the exploitation of groundwater and the use of desalination of brackish water opened the way to new extraction possibilities.

Reforms have been implemented through several programs and strategies, including:

- The National Strategy for the Promotion of Collective Interest Associations (1992): its objectives consist of promoting user associations within the framework of autonomous technical and financial management and redefining the role of government in the water supply of rural areas and the management of public irrigated areas (PPI).
- The National Irrigation Water Saving Program (1995): its objective is to rationalize the use of agricultural water. It is favoured by the decision relating to the increase in the investment subsidy granted to modern irrigation equipment.
- The establishment of adequate pricing systems and recovery of the cost of water: the pricing policy applies particularly in large public irrigated areas managed by regional agricultural development commissions (CRDA) with a view to recovering costs and maintenance granted by these management organizations. The main objective lies in optimizing the cost recovery rate based on pricing approaches acceptable to all stakeholders (FAO, 2023).

Considering that pricing is an essential tool of water policy, Tunisia established a tariff revision program in 1998. This revision, which provided for an annual increase of 15 percent, was more or less applied during the period 1998-2003 and these increases took place until 2003. These increases then stopped, hence the low current recovery rate (MARHP, 2016).

The scarcity of water following increased demands due to the effects of climate change has prompted those responsible for managing the water system to rethink their methods of intervention. Attempts to decentralize and involve various levels of the decision-making process are underway. These adaptations should ultimately lead to the establishment of a sustainable water governance approach in Tunisia.

In connection with this trend towards demand management, the Tunisian Constitution of 2014 established the right to water and the obligation for the State and society to preserve this resource and rationalize its exploitation (article 44), as well as the right to a healthy and balanced environment (article 45). The new Constitution of 2022 stipulates that the State must provide drinking water to all in equity, and must preserve water resources for future generations (Article 48).

The move towards integrated water resources management (IWRM) focused on demand management is confirmed, and new strategies are emerging:

- The Strategy for the Sustainability of Hydraulic Systems (2014): its objective is to upgrade agricultural development groups (GDA) and their professionalization for better participatory management of hydraulic systems in a rational, autonomous, and sustainable manner.

- The third Water and Soil Conservation Strategy (CES): its objective is to improve resilience to climate change through the promotion and revitalization of rainfed agriculture, the protection of watersheds, the recharge of water tables, and the promotion of soft techniques such as agroecology.
- The post-2020 National Environmental Strategy: is focused on the urgency, if not to stop, at least to slow down the destruction of renewable and non-renewable resources, on the establishment of regulations to facilitate its implementation and a policy for the sustainable use of energy, land, water, terrestrial, and marine biological resources, as well as the reduction of pollution and nuisances of all kinds. Four strategic axes were retained with strategic orientations and quantitative and qualitative objectives: i) the strengthening of the legal and institutional system for environmental protection; ii) protecting environments (water, air, soil, and subsoil); iii) the consistency of sectorial policies and programs in terms of environmental protection; and iv) developing and implementing of an environmental governance system (FAO, 2023).

Water governance plays a crucial role in managing water resources effectively and sustainably in the Medjerda River basin. Strong water governance frameworks are essential to ensure equitable access to water, efficient water use practices, and effective water resource management strategies. Mechanisms such as stakeholder engagement, regulatory frameworks, monitoring systems, and enforcement of mechanisms are vital in promoting transparent decision-making processes and addressing the complex water challenges facing the region. Collaborative efforts between government agencies, local communities, and other stakeholders are essential to enhance water governance in the Medjerda River basin and ensure the long-term sustainability of water resources in the area.

7.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

The decision-making structure and process for water use, management, and distribution in the Medjerda Basin involve multiple stakeholders and institutions at local, national, and international levels. However, the institutional organization of the sector is structured around the Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources, and Fisheries (MARHP) for water strategy; the Ministry of Environment (ME) for sanitation policy and environment protection; Ministry of Equipment, Housing and Territories' Management (MEHAT) for flood protection; and the Ministry of Public Health (MSP) for water quality.

The management of water resources is overseen by several government agencies. The General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE) is responsible for supervising and monitoring water resources, granting permits, and monitoring water quality. The General Directorate of Dams and Hydraulic Structures (DGBGTH) focuses on dam construction and operation, while the General Directorate of Rural Engineering and Water Exploitation (DGGREE) handles irrigation and water conservation in rural areas. The DGGREE is also responsible for the supply of drinking water in dispersed rural areas, relying on local user associations: The DGGREE constructs the infrastructure for which delegated management and operation by user associations created under the status of "Agricultural Development Groups" (GDAs). The General Directorate for Management and Conservation of Agricultural Land (DGACTA) focuses on water protection, hydraulic structures' siltation, and climate change adaptation. The Regional Commissions for

Agricultural Development (CRDA) are decentralized bodies responsible for implementing agricultural policies in each governorate. However, a lack of dialogue between stakeholders and the Ministry, combined with limited resources allocated to CRDA, hinders accurate inventorying and monitoring of water resources in Tunisia (Closas et al., 2018).

The National Office of Sanitation (ONAS), in charge of wastewater sanitation services, and SONEDE is responsible for supplying drinking water, sanitation and hygiene in urban and rural areas. This organization of the sector has made it possible to almost generalize water supply in the country.

Figure 24 Key water stakeholders and their intervention level in Medjerda, Tunisia.

7.3.3 Analysis

Tunisia's water policies have evolved significantly since the 1960s, moving from a supply-side approach to a demand-side management approach. The country has faced various challenges, including overexploitation of resources, degradation of quality, and the impacts of climate change. The current approach of transferring water from the north to the east and south in Tunisia has reached its limitations, and exploring non-conventional sources of water is a costly solution. Meanwhile, water operators are struggling financially due to rising costs, low tariffs, and the need to provide high-quality services, leading to signs of exhaustion (OECD, 2014). Despite the progress made, Tunisia's water code is currently under revision, and the country still struggles to achieve equitable

access to water and efficient water use practices. The government has implemented various reforms, including the establishment of GDAs, decentralization of water management, and promotion of sustainable irrigation practices. Instead of these efforts, the governance of the water sector, still based on a strong centralization of responsibilities and decision-making power. This governance approach shows its limits, leading to a continued deterioration of infrastructure and service performance, as well as increasing financing difficulties in the Tunisian water sector.

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8 Mujib, Jordan

8.1 System Characterization

The Mujib River Basin (MRB) 31°16'53.76" N, 36° 4'18.54" E (center point) is one of Jordan's fifteen surface water basins found in Jordan. The MRB occupies 7.4% of Jordan's land area. It is located on the eastern slopes of the Rift Valley Region, and flowing westward from the peripheries of the Jordanian eastern desert, gradually then rapidly accelerating through the eastern highlands then discharge in the Dead Sea Basin at the junction joint with Wadi Al Walah Basin in a confluence point local known as Al Malaqi which is located in the heart of the Mujib Biosphere Reserve. The Elevation of the MRB starts from 1300 m above sea level and the Jordan Valley (central zone) morphology with an altitude ending at -420 below sea level.

Figure 25 Main landmarks in Mujib River Basin (MRB).

Mujib River Basin (MRB) represents semi-arid to arid plateau land, forming 91% of the basin total area and 7% of the Kingdom's territory. It is the fifth largest basin among Jordan's water basins, covering an area of 6,586.76 km² including two sub-basins: Wadi

Al Mujib Sub-Basin, with an area of 4,449 sq km, and Wadi Al Walah Sub-Basin, with an area of 2137.76 km².

The Mujib Basin is characterized by predominantly Mediterranean bioclimatic in the northern part, with scorching hot, dry summers and cool to cold, wet winters, and Saharo-Arabian bioclimatic in the southern part, with more aridity. The precipitation range in the catchment area varies from 350 mm/year up mountains down to 100 mm/year in the Dead Sea area. There are Three dams within the basin namely Mujib Dam which is considered the largest dam in the basin, Wala Dam, and Allujon Dam. Both Wala and Allujon Dams were built to offer a more consistent and long-term sustainable water supply to charge the aquifer for domestic and agricultural uses.

Administratively, the MRB is a vibrant area with a high to moderate population density that extends across five governorates, Table (00). The most significant expansion is in Amman, with an area of (2338.7 km²), then in Karak (2132.7 km²), Ma'an (1712.8 km²), Madaba (399.4 km²), and Tafila (10 km²).

Table 18 Administrative Divisions of MRB (Data Source: The Jordanian Department of Population and Social Statistics, 2023).

Governorate	Amman	Karak	Madaba	Ma'an	Tafileh
The area of the Governorate covers the Basin (km ²)	2338.7	2132.7	1712.8	399.4	10
Percentage of Governorate Cover the Basin	35.4%	32.6%	6%	26.4%	0.2%
Percentage of the Governorate's area within the basin to its total area	31%	61%	42.5%	5.2%	0.8%
Number of Municipality	10	9	3	0	0
Number of Residential Areas	77	29	17	0	0
Population Size	885,796	372,070	47,696	0	0
Number of Male	490,092	194,550	24,887	0	0
Number of Female	395,704	177,520	22,809	0	0

Built-up areas are concentrated within the MRB in Amman (the Capital) compared to other governorates, representing about 35.4% of the total area. The Moderate Climate, diversity of land uses, and proximity to services make the area popular for urban expansion. It includes an important upstream part of the Mujib Dam and extends well into the eastern slopes, feeding into its main catchment.

Figure 26 Administrative Divisions Maps of MRB (Data Source: The Jordanian Department of Population and Social Statistics, 2024).

Karak Governorate is the second largest governorate in the basin where 32.6% of the Governorate area are within the basin. This substantial percentage indicates the primary importance of MRB for Karak. Because of the higher rainfall and less harsh climate, the Karak MRB Governorate hosts most built-up areas of cities, towns, villages, agriculture activities, and water bodies. This is also due to the governorate expansion that covers most of the downstream regions of the basin including the Mujib Dam and other desert dams built on the peripheries of the Irano-Terranean biogeographical region. It is important to note that the eastern parts of the Karak Governorate also include most of the ongoing mining activities due to the area's geology and the desert highway crossing the basin from north to south.

In Madaba Governorate, MRB represents around 6% of the total area of the Governorate. Although relatively small, the MRB Madaba sector is of crucial importance to the other basin as it includes the northern slopes directly feeding into the Walah Valley downstream of the Walah Dam and is critically proximate to the borders of the Mujib Biosphere Reserve and its Buffer Zone.

Ma'an sector of MRB represents around 26.4% of the total area and falls entirely under the Saharo-Arabian Biogeographic region thus with more aridity and lower biodiversity. The area includes important reserves of natural resources; however, it is targeted by some major mining activities. the Ma'an sector within the MRB mainly includes areas set aside as concession areas for major mineral extraction such as oil shale, Uranium and Phosphates. It includes the least built-up areas with land use mainly focusing on livestock grazing and some small-scale agriculture.

8.1.1 Main issues

Being a vital component of Jordan's water resources, fundamental for domestic, industrial, and agricultural needs. The Mujib River Basin faces significant challenges, including the conservation and protection of water resources, ensuring availability for various uses, maintaining water quality, disaster management, public awareness programs, implementing water allocation concepts as needed, and effective land use management. The following section provides an in-depth exploration of these challenges.

1. Water Resources Conservation and Protection

a) Groundwater Resources Conservation and Protection.

The MRB includes several groundwater well fields that cover part of the elevated water demands for the capital, Amman, and the governorates of Madaba and Karak. Thus, given the current chronic shortage of available groundwater resources, the conservation and protection of these sources have become critical and of national importance.

Moreover, implementing the concept of groundwater resources conservation through the wise usage, thus reducing abstraction, needs to be implemented through Institutionalizing a policy and implementation framework to promote the efficiency of water use and expanding the theme of reclaimed water usage for non-domestic usages (where applicable).

b) Surface water resources conservation and protection.

Several dams within the MRB vary in size and extend from small-desert dams to major dams such as the Mujib Dam and the Walla Dam. The stored water at the Mujib and Wala dam usually covers part of the water demands sent to Zara area at the west-northern part of the basin. In Ma'in treatment plant, the calibrated water is pumped (in addition to the water from other sources) to the capital, Amman, in addition to the Karak and Madaba Governorates. Thus, protecting and conserving the said surface water resources is curtailed to ensure the continuity of the drinking water supply to the capital, Amman, in addition to the Karak and Madaba cities.

2. Water sources availability for domestic purposes

Within the MRB, part of the surface and groundwater resources cover part of the elevated domestic water demands at the capital, Amman, and the Karak and Madaba governorates.

Implementing the ministry of water and irrigation (MWI) protection zones guidelines will greatly contribute to securing the designated water volumes from this basin to the end users at the capital, Amman, Karak, and Madaba governorates.

Vandalism to any element of the water supply systems within the Mujib Basin is a major issue of concern that can impact the availability of water resources for domestic usage. Thus, such an issue needs to be taken into consideration. Vandalism can include (i) Sabotage parts of the water supply system such as the well heads, the storage tanks, and the distribution systems; (ii) Dumping harmful materials at the water sources such as groundwater wells, dams, and lakes. Such issues can be controlled by implementing Zone-1 protection guidelines for groundwater wells.

3. Water sources availability for industrial purposes

Currently, the industrial establishments in the Dead Sea area depend on abstracting groundwater from the drilled groundwater wells in the Dead Sea basin and the Jordan Valley basin, in addition to having part of the collected surface water resources at the Mujib and the Wala dams (based on pre-agreed arrangements with Jordan Valley Authority (JVA) and Water Authority of Jordan (WAJ)).

The industrial sector's use of non-conventional water resources (such as reclaimed water and desalinated brackish/saline water) at the MRB needs to be evaluated (where applicable) to reduce the consumption of conventional water resources.

To reduce the needs for ground or surface water abstraction by the major industrial facilities, such as the Potash industry and other related chemical industries in the Dead Sea area, the possibility of treating a portion of the fluid wastes generated by

these industries can be explored, where the reclaimed water can then be reused at each facility, contributing to more sustainable water management practices.

4. Water Sources Availability for Agricultural Purposes

Reclaimed water is considered a major source covering part of the agricultural sector's water demands within the MRB. Thus, a major part of the water consumed by the agricultural sector at the MRB can be redirected for other purposes. The source for such reclaimed water is the four Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs) located in the basin.

5. Water Quality Conservation and Protection

Solid and fluid waste mismanagement, in addition to chemical spills (intentionally or unintentionally), can represent a major threat to the quality of the water sources in the basin. Thus, the water available in the basin for drinking is reduced. It is essential to conserve and protect the quality of the groundwater and surface water resources by initiating a water quality monitoring program to support the conservation and protection targets. Moreover, it is essential to invest in structural and non-structural interventions that reduce point and non-point water pollution.

6. Disaster Management

a) Flood Hazard

The morphological setting within the MRB and the presence of several major wadis and many minor watersheds increase the probability of flood incidences during winter.

The probability of floods increased during the last decades in Jordan due to the change in the rainfall pattern, which became high intensity and low duration. Thus, flood hazards can occur. Controlling flood hazards can be achieved through a flood forecasting system within the MRB supported by relevant hydraulic structures to manage potential floods.

As part of evaluating the flood hazards at the MRB. The following issues of concern need to be taken into consideration:

- Physical Vulnerability: floods can potentially damage physical structures such as buildings, bridges, roads, and public utilities.
- Nonphysical Vulnerabilities is another important vulnerability class. The most considered nonphysical vulnerability is economic loss. There are multiple ways in which floods can have economic impacts, mostly related to the interruption of various activities that then lead to negative economic consequences. These indirect economic impacts are often much more challenging to estimate than are direct impacts on structures and building contents. Possible indirect economic impacts include:
 - o Lost business activity due to interrupted utilities such as water or electricity supply.
 - o Lost business activity due to interruption of supply chains caused by large floods.
 - o Spoiling of agricultural products due to a damaged transportation network.
 - o Lost wages for employees due to any of the above impacts.

In 2018, floods occurred in the Mujib basin, resulting in human casualties, fatalities, and damage to some of the basin's infrastructure. This indicates the absence of an emergency response plan for flood incidents.

b) Drought Management.

The climate change phenomena impacting the climate worldwide are affecting Jordan's climate. Thus, high-temperature waves, high intensity and low duration rainfall, and winter periods with low rainfall intensity have passed during the last decades.

Drought results from a deficiency of precipitation from statistically normal (long-term average) amounts that, when extended over a season or especially over a longer period, are insufficient to meet the demands of human activities. All types of droughts originate from a deficiency of precipitation that results in water shortages for some activity (such as crop production) or some groups (such as farmers).

Thus, responsible agencies need to implement drought monitoring and drought forecasting. According to the monitoring and forecasting results, the water consumption rates in the kingdom need to be modified and adjusted to include the drought scenario. The surface water resources in the basin, such as the Mujib and Wala dams, which are major participants in the basin's water budget, are susceptible to any drought event. The impacts of drought that must be addressed can be classified into one of three principal types: economic, environmental, and social.

The people of Jordan must understand their exposure to drought hazards, such as the probability of drought occurrence at various severity levels. However, the risks associated with drought for any part of the kingdom are products of both the region's exposure to the event and the vulnerability of the area or the community to a drought.

However, much can be done to lessen societal vulnerability to drought by developing preparedness plans emphasizing risk management and adopting appropriate mitigation actions and programs.

Many management alternatives to prepare for and respond to drought fall into two broad categories: demand management and supply augmentation. To have a successful demand management plan, the following issues of concern need to be considered and addressed.

- Public information and education campaigns
- Emergency conservation programs
- Water service restrictions
- Restrictions on nonessential uses of water
- Prohibition of selected commercial uses
- Water rationing programs
- Augmentation
- Improvements in water systems (for example, leak detection, lining of transmission canals)
- Emergency sources of supply (for example, emergency interconnections, drilling new wells)
- Management of available water resources (for example, emergency water banks, over-drafting of groundwater aquifers)

- Search for new supplies of water.

In summary, increased emphasis should be placed on drought mitigation and preparedness, as well as prediction and early warning capabilities, if society is to reduce the economic and environmental damages associated with drought and its personal hardships. This will require interdisciplinary cooperation and a collaborative effort with policymakers at all levels.

7. Conduct Relevant Public Awareness Program

Introduce or expand public awareness programs for Integrated water resources management (IWRM) planning in collaboration with civil society organizations and the media. Also, the concept of Water education needs to be introduced through Introducing IWRM into school programs to increase water knowledge and develop leadership among the youth, including responsibility for water monitoring in local water bodies.

The major elements of the required Public Awareness program for the major stakeholders of the Mujib Basin should focus on the following aspects:

- To have livestock graze away from the major water sources within the MRB.
- Reduce the agricultural sector's use of chemical and organic fertilizers at the MRB.
- Introduce the concept of reclaimed water usage by the agricultural sector in the MRB.
- Introduce the concept of reclaimed water usage by the industrial sector in the MRB.

8. Implement the Water Allocation Concept (when & where needed)

Water allocation needs to be considered to manage the different water resources in the Mujib Basin. Expanding the use of reclaimed water will reduce groundwater use for irrigation purposes and thus reallocate such water for domestic purposes, especially during drought periods.

9. Land use management

Similar to the other parts of Jordan, the MRB suffers from the absence of a national law that can organize and plan land use throughout the kingdom. Thus, sensitive areas such as the MRB, where different types of land use patterns occur, need a legislative background to manage the ongoing land use patterns and plan future land use patterns. The major land use patterns in the area are agricultural and industrial, mainly in addition to tourist and residential usage.

These issues are interrelated. For instance, overuse of groundwater can contribute to soil erosion, and pollution can worsen water scarcity. Finding sustainable solutions requires a holistic approach that addresses all these challenges.

8.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Mujib River Basin Stakeholders' analysis and mapping represents a very important step in any development effort and is particularly important for initiatives addressing natural resources planning and management. Through a proper stakeholder analysis process, organizations can identify, understand, reach out to, engage, and involve stakeholders at all levels, and based on that, stakeholders were classified into three categories as shown in the following table.

Table 19 Classification of stakeholders based on their stock of resources in Mujib, Jordan.

Sector	NO	stakeholders	SOCIAL CAPITAL	ECONOMIC CAPITAL	HUMAN CAPITAL
Governorate	1.	Parliament Members	1	3	1
	2.	Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWE)	2	3	3
	3.	Water Authority of Jordan (JVA)	3	3	2
	4.	Mujib National Committee (MNC)	3	3	3
	5.	JVA - Dams Division	2	2	2
	6.	Ministry of Agriculture – Forestry Department	2	2	2
	7.	Ministry of Agriculture – Rangeland Department	2	2	2
	8.	Ministry of Agriculture – Local Department	2	2	2
	9.	Ministry of Environment – Nature Conservation Department	2	2	1
	10.	Ministry of Environment – Licensing and Inspection Departments	2	2	1
	11.	Ministry of Environment – Local Departments	1	1	1
	12.	Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities	2	2	1
	13.	Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources	1	3	1
	14.	Energy and Minerals Regulatory Commission	1	3	1
	15.	Atomic Energy Commission – Uranium Mining Company	1	3	1
	16.	Ministry of Interior – Local Governors	3	1	2
	17.	Ministry of Interior – Rangers	2	2	2
	18.	Ministry of Public Works	1	3	1
	19.	Ministry of Local Administration	2	2	2
	20.	Local Municipalities	3	3	2
	21.	Decentralization Councils	2	2	1
Privat	22.	Hijaz Railway Company	1	1	1
	23.	Arab Potash Company	2	3	1
	24.	Phosphate Mining Company	2	3	1

	25.	Oil Shale Company – Attarat for Energy Co.	2	3	1
	26.	Cement Factories – Qatraneh and Manaseer	2	3	1
	27.	Limestone and gypsum quarries	2	3	1
	28.	Road Construction Companies	2	3	1
	29.	Queen Alia International Airport	2	3	1
	30.	King Abdullah ii Industrial	2	2	1
Civil Society	31.	Local Social Leaders	3	1	2
	32.	Livestock owners – Residents and Nomadic	3	1	1
	33.	Farmers	3	3	1
	34.	Community-Based Organizations – Societies, charities, cooperatives, women's and youth groups.	3	2	2
	35.	Wildlife hunters	2	1	1
	36.	Tourists, picnickers	2	2	1
	37.	Local civil associations	3	1	1
Academic	38.	Mutah University	2	1	3
	39.	Petra University	2	1	3
	40.	Zaytona University	2	1	3
	41.	German Jordanian University	2	1	3
	42.	Middle East University- Jordan	2	1	3
	43.	Isra University	2	1	3
	44.	American University of Madaba (AUM)	2	1	3
Organizations	45.	Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature (RSCN)	3	2	3
	46.	Jordan Farmers Union	3	2	2
	47.	Royal Scientific Society (RSS)	3	1	1
	48.	National Agricultural Research Center (NARC)	3	2	2
	49.	IUCN ROWA	3	1	1
	50.	United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)	2	1	3
	51.	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)	3	1	3
	52.	Birdlife International	3	1	1

In the MRB, stakeholders' analysis forms the basis for planning, managing, implementing, and monitoring the initiative's vision, goals, and actions. The analysis process is based on

qualitatively assessing levels of influence and interest related to the various stakeholders and their relationship to the basin. Levels of influence and interest could be high, medium, or low and could be positive or negative in relationship to the basin's ecosystems and primarily water resources. The analysis process results in an influence-interest matrix, through which four categories of stakeholders are identified as follows:

1. **Core Stakeholders** possess high levels of influence on and interest in the basin. These would generally include government authorities and other entities with strong capacities and a strong legal mandate, such as JVA, Ministry of Agriculture (MoA), and Ministry of Environment (MoEnv).
2. **Potential Stakeholders** have a high level of interest in the site but a low level of influence in decision-making. These normally include civic society organizations, such as local community-based organizations and other NGOs, that have a high level of awareness and often capacities but lack the institutional and legal instruments to influence the decision-making process.
3. **Critical Stakeholders:** those who enjoy a high level of influence but lack the interest to engage, support, and facilitate. This category often includes commercial entities with low environmental awareness and solid economic agendas that conflict with conservation and sustainability. They are usually temporary users of the resources and do not have a social and cultural association with the site. Typically, these include large industries and other temporary-use groups such as hunters.
4. **Marginal Stakeholders** are those who lack enough interest or ability to influence the basin. These typically include temporary visitors and the general public living away from the main basin hotspots.

Based on the above guidelines and the stock of resources stakeholders table, the following is MRB's stakeholders' analysis matrix.

Figure 27 Stakeholder grid based on power/interest in Mujib, Jordan.

1. Parliament Members	9. Ministry of Environment – Nature Conservation Department	17. Ministry of Interior – Rangers	25. Oil Shale Company – Attarat for Energy Co.	33. Farmers	41. German Jordanian University	49. IUCN ROWA
2. Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWE)	10. Ministry of Environment – Licensing and Inspection Departments	18. Ministry of Public Works	26. Cement Factories – Qatraneh and Manaseer	34. Community-Based Organizations – Societies, charities, cooperatives, women's and youth groups.	42. Middle East University- Jordan	50. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)
3. Water Authority of Jordan (JVA)	11. Ministry of Environment – Local Departments	19. Ministry of Local Administration	27. Limestone and gypsum quarries	35. Wildlife hunters	43. Isra University	51. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ)
4. Mujib National Committee (MNC)	12. Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities	20. Local Municipalities	28. Road Construction Companies	36. Tourists, picnickers	44. American University of Madaba (AUM)	52. Birdlife International
5. JVA - Dams Division	13. Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources	21. Decentralization Councils	29. Queen Alia International Airport	37. Local civil associations	45. Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature (RSCN)	
6. Ministry of Agriculture – Forestry Department	14. Energy and Minerals Regulatory Commission	22. Hijaz Railway Company	30. King Abdullah II Industrial	38. Mutah University	46. Jordan Farmers Union	
7. Ministry of Agriculture – Rangeland Department	15. Atomic Energy Commission – Uranium Mining Company	23. Arab Potash Company	31. Local Social Leaders	39. Petra University	47. Royal Scientific Society (RSS)	
8. Ministry of Agriculture – Local Department	16. Ministry of Interior – Local Governors	24. Phosphate Mining Company	32. Livestock owners – Residents and Nomadic	40. Zaytona University	48. National Agricultural Research Center (NARC)	

The stakeholders were defined and divided based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local) in the Mujib Water Basin.

Table 20 Stakeholders classification based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local) in Mujib, Jordan.

	STATE	MARKET	CIVIL
<u>NATIONAL</u>	Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWE) - Secretary General of the Ministry of Water and Irrigation	Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources	International Organizations - UNDP - GIZ - USAID - IUCN
	Ministry of Environment - Secretary General of the Ministry of Environment	Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities	
	Water Authority of Jordan (JVA) - Secretary General of the Jordan Valley Authority		
<u>REGIONAL / BASIN-SCALE</u>	Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWE) - JVA - Dams Division - Water Demand Department	Phosphate Mining Company	Jordan Farmers Union
	Mujib National Committee (MNC)	Arab Potash Company	Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature (RSCN)
	Ministry of Agriculture - Forestry Department - Rangeland Department	Oil Shale Company – Attarat for Energy Co.	
	Ministry of Interior - Local Governors	Cement Factories – Qatraneh and Manaseer	
	Local Municipalities - Decentralization Councils	Limestone and gypsum quarries	
	Ministry of Environment - Nature Conservation Department - Licensing and Inspection Departments	Queen Alia International Airport	
<u>LOCAL / SUB-BASIN SCALE</u>	Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWE)	Wildlife hunters	Academic
	Ministry of Environment		Farmers

	Ministry of Agriculture - Forestry Department - Rangeland Department		Community-Based Organizations – Societies, charities, cooperatives, women's and youth groups.
			Mujib Biosphere Reserve
			Tourists, picnickers
			Livestock owners – Residents and Nomadic

8.2.1 State Actors

State actors in the Mujib River basin are the partners who present the highest levels of collaborative effort and directly achieve the project vision and objectives.

- Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI)
 The Ministry of “MWI” is responsible for enforcing the relevant legislations (laws, regulations, and guidelines) related to protecting, conserving, and managing the water resources and the other elements of the environment that have direct and indirect impacts on the water resources (quantity & Quality wise).
- Water Authority of Jordan (WAJ)
 Water Authority is responsible for the public water supply and wastewater services, as well as for the overall water resources planning and monitoring in the Jordan Valley and carries full responsibility for the public water supply, wastewater services, and related projects, as well as for the overall water construction, operations, and maintenance.
- Ministry of Environment (MoEnv)
 Conserving the environment and its ecosystems through developing legal, strategic, and policy frameworks, spreading environmental culture, enhancing environmental monitoring and law enforcement, transitioning to a green economy with a participatory approach, and supporting RSCN to achieve sustainable development in the MRB.
- Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)
 Focus on the used Irrigation water quality and quantity monitoring. Also, manage (as possible) the farmer’s practices using pesticides and insecticides, soil analysis, and research.
- Mujib National Committee (MNC)
 The MRB National Committee is an independent Committee established in May 2023 by the decision of the Jordanian Council of Ministers. The MNC chaired by the Jordanian Ministry of Water and Irrigation includes 13 members of the secretaries-general of the ministries, academics, and non-profit organizations representing the local community.
 The committee coordinates and organizes procedures among stakeholders to contribute to the management of the Mujib Water Basin in an optimal and sustainable manner and in line with national strategic policies and plans. In addition

to following up on topics related to water policies, protecting the ecosystem and biodiversity, and reducing climate impacts.

8.2.2 Market Actors

Market actors in the Mujib River basin are usually commercial entities with low environmental awareness and solid economic agendas that conflict with conservation and sustainability. They are usually temporary users of the resources and do not have a social and cultural association with the site. Typically, these include large industries and other temporary-use groups such as hunters.

- Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources
Planning and managing a comprehensive process for the energy and mineral resource sector and ensuring their implementation in order to achieve the sector's general objectives. The most important of these are providing energy in various forms for the development process, organizing its affairs, and optimum utilization of natural resources complying with international best practices.
- Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities
Develop and manage tourism destinations and protect and research archaeological sites and cultural values
- Arab Potash Company
Potash factories are located in the southern Jordan Valley out of the border of Mujib basin. However, water is pumped from downstream of the Mujib River to the complex of Potash factories and mines in the south, these quantities of surface water are not the only source to satisfy this industry demand. However, the average volume of water from the Mujib River to industry is 3.6 MCM annually.
- Jordan Phosphate Mining Company (JPMC)
Operation and production of phosphate mining in the MRB, exploration, and excavation open areas in the Abyadh and Hasa mines in Karak and Tafileh Governorates, and Al Shidiyyeh Mines in Ma'an Governorate. adopts a corporate strategy for environmental rehabilitation and invests in rehabilitating some of the mining areas through collecting and reusing industrial water using dirt dams as a main water harvesting mechanism.
- Oil Shale Company
Operating under the Attarat Oil Shale Company (APCO) between the Ma'an, Karak, and Amman sectors in Lajjoun, Assultani, Attarat Um Ghudran, Wadi Mghayyer, Jarf Addarawish, Suwaqa, Khan Al Zabib, and Athamad areas. Improve compliance with environmental codes and standards with environmental compensation schemes.
- Cement Factories – Qatraneh and Manaseer
Including MRB, Excavation and production of Gypsum Mining occur in five main areas, mainly in the Amman and Karak sectors to the north of Abu Rukbah's Proposed Protected Area.
- Queen Alia International Airport (QAIA)
QAIA is the largest airport in Jordan, located in Zizya, 30 kilometers south of Amman in the MRB; its risks generally include air and landscape pollution, and it is working on improving compliance with environmental codes and standards with environmental compensation schemes.
- Wildlife hunters

Responsible for Legal and illegal Wildlife (and fishing) hunting, collection, and trade.
Mainly affecting biodiversity and water pollution.

8.2.3 Civil Actors

Civil actors in the Mujib River basin have a high level of awareness and often capacities but lack the institutional and legal instruments to influence the decision-making process. These actors typically include farmers, local community-based organizations, and other NGOs.

- Jordan Farmers Union
Allowing participation of farmers in the work of the Federation and its activities, touching the needs of farmers and providing services to them to achieve sustainable agricultural development and conservation of natural resources and environment, paying attention to women farmers and the revival of its historic role in the production process of agricultural and food processing, promoting community awareness of the importance of agriculture and the need to preserve agricultural land, and addressing the problem
- Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature (RSCN)
The Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature RSCN is a non-governmental organization established in 1966 under the patronage of His Majesty the Late King Hussein. RSCN is authorized by the Ministry of Environment to conserve the biodiversity of Jordan and integrate its conservation programs with socio-economic development while promoting wider public support and action for protecting the natural environment and ecology system within Jordan and neighbouring countries. It is playing the role of facilitator in the national committee, and is manipulating the stakeholders in the basin toward the sustainable use of water resources considering the need of water for biodiversity.
- Academic
The MRB includes many educational institutions and universities that enrich knowledge about the basin through hydrological and environmental studies and research. These educational edifices also provide recommendations, guidelines, and policies that help achieve MRB-integrated and sustainable management.
- Farmers
Agricultural activities in the MRB are divided into rain-fed and irrigated fruit and vegetable crops. Individual farmers in the Mujib Basin are major users of water resources; helping them develop subsistence farming and adopt environmentally friendly techniques will preserve the sustainability of water and environmental resources in the MRB.
- Community-Based Organizations – Societies, charities, cooperatives, women's and youth groups.
Promote sustainable livelihoods and environment-based solutions for local development.
- Tourists, picnickers
The MRB includes many tourist areas that support the local economy and promote sustainable recreation. The Mujib and the Dead Sea are considered important areas for touring tourism, climbing rugged mountains, and outdoor camping, in addition to observing nature, birds, and animals. Medical tourism in the Al-Zara area, which has

hot mineral springs that help treat skin diseases, also represents a distinctive landmark.

Wadi Mujib Reserve in Jordan is considered one of the largest reserves listed by UNESCO in 2011 as a biosphere reserve. It has become an important tourist attraction in the country and a destination for water sports lovers. This reserve is considered the lowest reserve on the surface of the Earth.

- Livestock owners – Residents and Nomadic
Responsible for sustainable rangeland management practices.

8.3 Governance Analysis

In general, the Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI) is responsible for the overall water governance, Policies, strategic direction, and planning; the MWI works with the Water Authority of Jordan (WAJ) and the Jordan Valley Authority (JVA).

8.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

Considering the ongoing water challenges, a National Water Strategy has been created to manage the water sector and to ensure optimal service levels. The National Water Strategy (2016–2025) is part of the MWI’s plan, which explores the need for more development of water legislation, including the need for a comprehensive water law and moving toward realizing humans’ rights to water and sanitation while recognizing these rights and their standard content for all. The strategy’s key areas are as follows: (i) Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM); (ii) water, sewage, and sanitation services; (iii) water for irrigation, energy, and other uses; (iv) institutional reform; and (v) sector information management and monitoring. The strategy also addresses the issues related to climate change adaptation, transboundary/shared water resources, public-private partnerships, and the economic dimensions of water. Within the timeframe for this strategy, the MWI aims to adopt a sector-wide, integrated water-resource planning and management approach; develop sector policies and legislation to enhance performance, equitable service provision, and optimization of available resources; initiate institutional reforms to restructure sector management; enhance fiscal discipline for cost recovery; improve internal efficiencies for sector coordination and management; and build technical capacity (MWI 2016).

From this standpoint, many policies have been created to achieve these goals and place them within a legislative framework approved by the Prime Minister of Jordan, such as Water Demand Management and Groundwater Sustainability Policies 2016 and Vulnerable Water Resources in Jordan 2020.

Currently, Jordan’s water policy efforts are primarily directed toward managing water demand and moving forward with implementing the national water plan. Moreover, water policy encourages water harvesting, conserving, and protecting resources. In contrast, the water substitution and reuse policy propose the reuse of treated wastewater in irrigation to enable the freeing of fresh water for municipal uses.

In irrigation, it is recommended that water-saving technologies and replacing groundwater with treated wastewater be considered for farms near existing or planned wastewater plants.

8.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

Water resources management (exploration, wise usage, and monitoring) in Jordan is a “Multiple parties Responsibility” headed by the Ministry of Water Irrigation (MWI). The MWI and its operational arms (WAJ including the utility operators and JVA) are Jordan's water resources (Surface & Ground) safeguard. The implemented management and monitoring operation covers the quantity and quality aspects. On the other hand, the Ministry of Health is responsible for monitoring the quality of the provided water for drinking purposes all over Jordan, in association with WAJ- Central Labs.

Moreover, the Ministry of Environment is monitoring water as one of the major elements of the environment, with a particular focus on the quality perspective against pollution. In this regard, the mandate was assigned to the Royal Scientific Society (RSS) through a long-term contract. For operational purposes, all water utilities operators are responsible for monitoring the quality and quantity of water used for domestic purposes within their operational areas.

Other governmental agencies provided what can be called an in-kind contribution to the protection and conservation of Jordan's water resources through close monitoring of the implementation of its relevant laws. The best examples are the Ministry of Interior (MoI) and Municipal Affairs (MoMA).

In 2023, an ambitious step towards sustainable water management, the Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature (RSCN) under a project funded by MAVA foundation launched a National Committee for the Management of the Mujib River Basin (MRB). This one-of-a-kind initiative represents a significant milestone in addressing Jordan's water scarcity challenges. This has resulted from the sustained efforts of the RSCN over the years to involve all stakeholders and achieve long-term sustainability and environmental balance in the MRB.

The MRB National Committee, headed by the Jordanian Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI), includes general secretaries of ministries, academics, and non-profit organizations representing the local community. The MWI will follow up on the committee's work, hold periodic meetings, and prepare the resulting outputs.

The formation of this national committee will help RSCN share the projects it is implementing within the basin, facilitate access to available information, and ensure the preservation of ecological values in the basin (Figure 28).

Figure 28 Decision-making structure and water distribution process in Mujib, Jordan.

8.3.3 Analysis

Key steps are mentioned during the MRB stakeholder analysis workshop:

1. The Importance of understanding the current water situation in the Mujib Basin and the impact of climate and human challenges on the linked decision-making process between users and decision-makers.
2. Achieving sustainable water management requires effective and continuous information management, which will contribute to the process of problem analysis and decision-making.
3. The Importance of improving the resilience of farmers and local communities in the MRB by improving knowledge and awareness, and providing services, and Agriculture technologies related to water and energy.
4. The positive impact that will affect the governance and decisions related to the MRB because of the formation of the Mujib Basin National Committee.
5. Improving the natural ecological flow in the Mujib Biosphere Reserve, and paying attention to that environmental flow is a key indicator of the quantity and quality of water in the Mujib Basin
6. Considering the matter of finding sustainable water solutions as a very important subject, whether through increasing water harvesting projects, nature-based solutions (NBS), or using clean energy.

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9 Sebou, Morocco

9.1 System Characterization

The Sebou basin, centrally located in Morocco, spans an extensive area of approximately 40,000 km², making it one of the largest and most vital river systems in the country. The basin plays a crucial role in the hydrological, ecological, and socio-economic framework of northern Morocco, supporting over 6 million inhabitants and a diverse array of ecosystems. This section characterizes the Sebou basin's system by examining its biophysical attributes, hydrological context, water resource infrastructure, and ecological significance.

The Sebou basin experiences a Mediterranean climate with oceanic influence, transitioning to a continental climate towards the interior. This climate variability results in distinct microclimates influenced by altitude, latitude, and exposure. The average annual precipitation across the basin is approximately 600 mm, with significant spatial variability. Temperatures vary seasonally, with winter temperatures often dropping to cause frost and occasional snow, while summer temperatures can be extremely high. These climatic conditions affect the region's water availability and agricultural practices.

Figure 29 Precipitation Map of the Sebou Basin in Morocco (ABHS, 2018).

Hydrologically, the Sebou basin can be divided into four main components: the Upper Sebou, the Inaouène, the Middle Sebou, and the Lower Sebou. The basin's hydrological network is characterized by numerous tributaries, extensive wetlands, and significant water bodies (Figure 30). The average annual water inputs amount to 5,560 Mm³, with

substantial variability influenced by seasonal and inter-annual changes. Groundwater resources in the basin are among the richest in Morocco, with several significant aquifers, including the Dradère-Souière, Mamora, and Gharb aquifers.

Figure 30 Precipitation Map of the Sebou Basin in Morocco (ABHS, 2018).

The Sebou basin's water supply system is supported by an extensive dam infrastructure, comprising 10 large dams and 45 smaller dams or hillside lakes. These dams collectively have a storage capacity of 5,872 Mm³, enabling the regulation of approximately 1,830 Mm³ of water annually. Major dams such as Al Wahda, Idriss I, and Allal Al Fassi play pivotal roles in managing the basin's water resources for irrigation, potable water supply, hydroelectric power generation, and flood control. The distribution network is designed to adapt to the temporal and spatial variability of water availability, ensuring the efficient supply of water to urban centers, agricultural areas, and industrial zones.

The Sebou basin supports a diverse range of ecosystems due to its varied climate and topography. It includes several Ramsar sites recognized globally for their biodiversity conservation value. These wetlands are crucial for water purification, flood control, and providing habitats for numerous species of flora and fauna. However, the basin faces significant environmental challenges, including habitat degradation, pollution from agricultural and industrial sources, and the impacts of climate change. The basin's land use is primarily agricultural, accounting for 60% of the area, with urban areas making up 2.76% and natural drylands representing 34.61%.

The governance of water resources in the Sebou basin involves multiple stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, NGOs, and industry representatives. Effective governance is achieved through integrated water resource management (IWRM) approaches that emphasize stakeholder engagement, sustainable management

practices, and policy enforcement. The water policy framework, governed by national water laws such as Law 10-95 (1995) and Law 36-15 (2016), includes water rights, allocation frameworks, and regulatory compliance mechanisms to ensure the equitable distribution of water resources and the protection of ecological flows.

9.1.1 Main issues

The Sebou basin, while vital to the hydrological, ecological, and socio-economic fabric of northern Morocco, faces a multitude of challenges that threaten its sustainability and resilience. These challenges are multifaceted, encompassing water management, environmental degradation, socio-economic pressures, and the impacts of climate change. A detailed examination of these main issues and challenges is essential to inform effective management and policy responses.

- **Balancing Water Demand vs. Conservation:** One of the foremost challenges in the Sebou basin is balancing the increasing water demand with the need for conservation. The basin supports a dense population, extensive agricultural activities, and significant industrial operations, all of which exert substantial pressure on the available water resources. The growing population and urban expansion further amplify this demand, necessitating the implementation of strategies that promote water efficiency and conservation while ensuring the equitable distribution of resources among various sectors.
- **Over-exploitation of water resources:** The over-exploitation of water resources, particularly groundwater, is a critical issue in the Sebou basin. Intensive agricultural practices, driven by the need to sustain food security and economic stability, have led to the excessive extraction of groundwater, resulting in the depletion of aquifers and a significant decline in water levels. This over-exploitation not only threatens the availability of water for future use but also impacts the quality and sustainability of the water supply, necessitating urgent measures to regulate and manage water extraction practices.
- **Pollution from agricultural and industrial sources:** Pollution poses a significant threat to water quality in the Sebou basin. Agricultural runoff, laden with chemical fertilizers and pesticides, contaminates water bodies and disrupts aquatic ecosystems. Industrial discharges, particularly from the agribusiness, leather, and textile sectors, introduce harmful pollutants into the water, exacerbating the degradation of water quality. Urban wastewater, often inadequately treated, further compounds this issue. Effective pollution control measures, including stricter regulations, monitoring, and the promotion of sustainable practices, are crucial to mitigate these impacts and protect the basin's water resources.
- **Degradation of natural habitats:** The Sebou basin's diverse ecosystems, including its wetlands, forests, and riparian zones, are under threat from habitat degradation. Human activities such as land conversion for agriculture, urbanization, and industrial development have led to significant habitat loss and fragmentation. The degradation of these natural habitats not only reduces biodiversity but also impairs the ecological functions that are vital for maintaining water quality, regulating hydrological cycles,

- and providing habitat for numerous species. Protecting and restoring these habitats is essential for sustaining the ecological integrity of the basin.
- Aging water infrastructure: The aging water infrastructure in the Sebou basin presents a significant challenge to effective water management. Many of the dams, canals, and pipelines are outdated and in need of maintenance and modernization. The inefficiencies in the infrastructure lead to water losses, reduced storage capacity, and increased vulnerability to extreme weather events. Upgrading and modernizing the water infrastructure is necessary to enhance the efficiency of water distribution, ensure reliable water supply, and support the region's socio-economic development.
 - Climate change impacts: Climate change exacerbates the existing challenges in the Sebou basin by altering precipitation patterns, increasing the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, and raising temperatures. These changes impact water availability, increase the risks of droughts and floods, and put additional strain on the basin's water resources. Developing and implementing climate adaptation strategies, such as building climate-resilient infrastructure, promoting community-based adaptation programs, and integrating climate projections into water management planning, is essential to enhance the basin's resilience to climate variability and change.
 - Socio-economic pressures: The socio-economic pressures within the Sebou basin, driven by population growth, urbanization, and industrial development, intensify the challenges of water management. The need to support economic growth and improve living standards often conflicts with the goals of environmental conservation and sustainable water use. Ensuring that socio-economic development is aligned with sustainable water management practices is crucial for achieving long-term sustainability and resilience in the basin.
 - Governance and policy implementation: Effective governance and policy implementation are critical to addressing the challenges in the Sebou basin. The governance system must involve multiple stakeholders, including local communities, government agencies, NGOs, and private sector representatives, to ensure inclusive and transparent decision-making processes. Strengthening the regulatory framework, enforcing compliance, and promoting stakeholder engagement are essential for fostering a collaborative approach to water management and ensuring the sustainable use of the basin's water resources.

9.2 Stakeholder Mapping

The stakeholder mapping for the Sebou basin was conducted to identify and categorize the various stakeholders involved in the management, use, and conservation of water resources within the basin. This mapping is essential for understanding the roles, interests, and influences of different stakeholders, and for fostering collaborative efforts towards sustainable water governance.

The methodology used for stakeholder mapping involved several key steps:

- Identification of stakeholders: Stakeholders were identified through a comprehensive review of relevant literature, project documents, and consultations with local experts.

This included identifying government agencies, private sector actors, civil society organizations, and local communities involved in water resource management. Key sources of information included in the Sebou Water Fund Feasibility Study and the Master Plan for integrated development of water resources in the Sebou Basin, and various mission reports, which provided detailed insights into the entities operating within the basin.

- Classification of stakeholders: Identified stakeholders were classified based on their roles, interests, and levels of influence. This classification was done using a combination of qualitative assessments and consultations. Stakeholders were grouped into categories such as state actors, market actors, and civil actors, each playing distinct roles in the water management landscape.
- Mapping stakeholder relationships: Relationships between stakeholders were mapped to understand the network of interactions and dependencies. This involved analyzing how stakeholders influence each other and the flow of resources and information among them. For example, the interactions between the Sebou Hydraulic Basin Agency (ABHS), local municipalities, and agricultural cooperatives were closely examined to identify key leverage points for collaborative governance.
- Assessment of stakeholder capacities: The capacities of stakeholders were assessed in terms of their social, economic, and human capital. This helped in understanding their strengths and areas where they might need support. Factors such as the capacity to mobilize resources, technical expertise, and the ability to influence policy were considered in this assessment.
- Development of stakeholder grid: A stakeholder grid was developed to visualize the stakeholders based on their power and interest in water resource management. This grid helps in identifying key players, potential allies, and those who need more engagement. The grid categorizes stakeholders into high power/high interest, high power/low interest, low power/high interest, and low power/low interest groups, enabling targeted engagement strategies.

Table 21 Classification of stakeholders based on their stock of resources in Sebou, Morocco (Ranking: 1=Low,2=Medium,3=High).

Sector	No	Stakeholders	SOCIAL CAPITAL	ECONOMIC CAPITAL	HUMAN CAPITAL
Government	1.	Ministry of Equipment and Water	3	3	3
	2.	Sebou Hydraulic Basin Agency (ABHS)	3	3	3
	3.	Ministry of Agriculture (Agriculture Department and National Agency for Water and Forests)	2	2	2
	4.	Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development	2	2	1
	5.	Ministry of Tourism	2	2	1
	6.	Ministry of Industry and Trade	1	2	1

	7.	Ministry of Interior (Regional and Municipal Councils)	3	3	2
	8.	Ministry of Finance	2	3	1
Private Sector	9.	Agribusiness Companies	2	3	1
	10.	Textile Industries	2	3	1
	11.	Mining Companies	2	3	1
	12.	Road Construction Companies	2	3	1
Civil Society	13.	Local Water Users Associations	3	1	2
	14.	Farmers' Unions	3	2	2
	15.	Community-Based Organizations	3	2	2
Academic/Research	16.	Universities (e.g. Fez, Meknes, Ifrane)	2	1	3
	17.	Research Institutes (e.g. INRA Meknes)	2	1	3

Figure 31 Stakeholder grid based on power/interest in Sebou, Morocco.

Table 22 Stakeholders classification based on their status (public, private, civil society) and governance scale (national, regional, local) in Sebou, Morocco.

	STATE	MARKET	CIVIL
NATIONAL	Ministry of Equipment and Water, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Interior	Agribusiness Companies, Textile Industries, Mining Companies, Road Construction Companies	Local Water Users Associations, Farmers' Unions, Community-Based Organizations
REGIONAL / BASIN SCALE	Sebou Hydraulic Basin Agency (ABHS), Ministry of Agriculture (Agriculture Department and National Agency for Water and Forests), Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development, Ministry of Tourism, Ministry of Industry and Trade, Ministry of Interior (Regional Councils)	Agribusiness Companies, Textile Industries, Mining Companies, Road Construction Companies	Universities (e.g., Fez, Meknes, Ifrane), Research Institutes (e.g., INRA Meknes)
LOCAL / SUB-BASIN SCALE	Ministry of Interior (Municipal Councils)	Agribusiness Companies, Textile Industries, Mining Companies, Road Construction Companies	Local Water Users Associations, Farmers' Unions, Community-Based Organizations, Universities, Research Institutes

9.2.1 State Actors

- **Ministry of Equipment and Water:** This ministry is crucial in the management and allocation of water resources in the Sebou Basin. It oversees the development and implementation of water policies, infrastructure projects, and ensures the sustainable use of water resources in Morocco's basins. The ministry coordinates with other governmental and non-governmental entities to address water-related issues, focusing on long-term planning and crisis management during droughts and floods.
- **Sebou Hydraulic Basin Agency (ABHS):** ABHS plays a pivotal role in the management and regulation of water resources within the Sebou Basin. It is responsible for the monitoring of water quality and quantity, the enforcement of water laws, and the

implementation of integrated water resources management (IWRM) strategies. ABHS collaborates with various stakeholders to develop and maintain infrastructure such as dams and hydraulic systems, ensuring efficient water distribution and conservation.

- **Ministry of Agriculture (Agriculture Department and National Agency for Water and Forests):** This ministry focuses on the sustainable use of water for agricultural purposes, which is the largest consumer of water in the Sebou Basin. It promotes modern irrigation techniques, supports farmers through training and resources, and works on soil conservation and agricultural projects to maintain the economic balance. The National Agency for Water and Forests also engages in the protection and management of forested areas that are critical for biodiversity and water catchment.
- **Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development:** This ministry is involved in promoting sustainable practices and the development of renewable energy projects within the basin. It addresses environmental concerns related to water use and pollution, implements policies to mitigate climate change impacts, and ensures that water management practices align with national sustainability goals.
- **Ministry of Tourism:** The ministry supports the development of (eco-)tourism initiatives that rely on the health and beauty of the Sebou Basin's natural resources. It promotes the conservation of national parks and wetlands and other natural attractions that draw visitors, contributing to the local economy.
- **Ministry of Industry and Trade:** This ministry ensures that industrial activities in the basin, such as textile and mining operations, adhere to environmental regulations to minimize water pollution. It also facilitates investments in water-efficient technologies and processes that support sustainable industrial growth.
- **Ministry of Interior (Regional and Municipal Councils):** Local and regional councils under the Ministry of Interior are crucial for implementing water policies at the local level. They coordinate community-based water management initiatives, ensure compliance with national water regulations, and engage local stakeholders in decision-making processes.
- **Ministry of Finance:** The ministry provides the financial resources needed for water management projects. It allocates budgets for infrastructure development, supports funding for conservation programs, and ensures that economic policies are conducive to sustainable water management practices.

9.2.2 Market Actors

- **Agribusiness Companies:** These companies are major consumers of water in the Sebou Basin, especially for irrigation. They are involved in the production of crops, livestock, and related products. Agribusinesses must comply with regulations regarding water use efficiency and pollution control, adopting sustainable practices to maintain their operations.
- **Textile Industries:** The textile sector in the Sebou Basin relies heavily on water for processing and manufacturing. These industries are required to implement water treatment solutions to manage wastewater and reduce environmental impact. The adoption of cleaner production technologies is encouraged to ensure compliance with environmental standards.

- **Mining Companies:** Mining operations, including those for phosphates and other minerals, have significant water requirements and potential impacts on water quality. These companies are regulated to ensure they manage their water use sustainably and mitigate any pollution resulting from their activities.
- **Road Construction Companies:** Involved in the development of infrastructure within the basin, these companies must manage water use efficiently and ensure that their activities do not negatively impact water resources. They are required to implement measures to control erosion and sedimentation during construction projects.

9.2.3 Civil Actors

- **Local Water Users Associations:** These NGOs represent the interests of local water users, primarily farmers, and play a key role in the management and distribution of irrigation water. They facilitate communication between farmers and government agencies, ensuring that water management practices are tailored to local needs and conditions.
- **Farmers' Unions:** These unions advocate for the rights and needs of farmers in the Sebou Basin. They work to ensure that agricultural policies and practices support sustainable water use and provide training and resources to farmers to improve water efficiency and productivity.
- **Community-Based Organizations:** These organizations engage local communities in water management and conservation efforts. They focus on raising awareness about sustainable practices, promoting community-led initiatives for water conservation, and advocating for policies that protect local water resources.
- **Universities (e.g., Fez, Meknes, Ifrane):** Academic institutions conduct research on various aspects of water management, providing valuable data and insights that inform policy and practice. They also offer training and education programs that build the capacity of local stakeholders to manage water resources effectively.
- **Research Institutes (e.g., INRA Meknes):** Research institutes focus on agricultural research, developing innovative solutions to improve water use efficiency and sustainability in the Sebou Basin. They collaborate with government agencies, private sector entities, and local communities to implement research findings and support sustainable development initiatives.

9.3 Governance Analysis

The governance analysis of the Sebou Basin involves examining the structures, processes, and frameworks that guide water management within the region. This section details the key aspects of governance, including the policy and regulatory framework, decision-making structures, and an overall analysis of the current governance system's strengths and weaknesses. This analysis aims to identify areas for improvement and suggest strategies for enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of water governance in the Sebou Basin.

9.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

The Sebou Basin's water governance is shaped by a comprehensive policy and regulatory framework designed to ensure sustainable management of water resources. Key policies and regulations include:

- Law 10-95 (1995): This law establishes the framework for water resource management in Morocco, emphasizing integrated water resource management (IWRM) and sustainable use of water resources. It mandates the establishment of basin agencies, like the Sebou Hydraulic Basin Agency (ABHS), to manage water resources at the basin level.
- Law 36-15 (2016): This law updates and strengthens the provisions of Law 10-95, introducing more stringent measures for water conservation, pollution control, and stakeholder engagement. It enhances the role of basin agencies and promotes the participation of local communities and stakeholders in water management.
- Water Policy Instruments: Various policy instruments are employed to support water management goals, including financial incentives for water-saving technologies, subsidies for sustainable agricultural practices, and grants for Research & Development and raising awareness in water management.
- Regulatory Compliance Mechanisms: These mechanisms ensure adherence to water quality standards and sustainable practices through monitoring, enforcement, and penalties for non-compliance. Regulatory agencies work closely with stakeholders to promote best practices in water use.

9.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

The decision-making structure for water governance in the Sebou Basin involves multiple stakeholders at different levels:

- National Level: The Ministries (Equipment and Water, Interior, Agriculture, etc.) set the overarching policies and regulatory frameworks. They also provide guidance and support to regional and local entities.
- Regional/Basin Level: The Sebou Hydraulic Basin Agency (ABHS) plays a central role in managing water resources within the basin. It is responsible for implementing national policies, developing basin-specific management plans, and coordinating activities among various stakeholders.
- Local Level: Local governments, municipalities, and community-based organizations are involved in the implementation of water management strategies. They ensure that local needs and priorities are addressed and facilitate community participation in decision-making processes.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Regular consultations and forums are held to engage stakeholders, including farmers, industry representatives, NGOs, and academic institutions. These interactions ensure that diverse perspectives are considered in decision-making and that collaborative solutions are developed.

9.3.3. Analysis

The governance system in the Sebou Basin exhibits several strengths and weaknesses:

This governance analysis highlights the necessity for a balanced and integrated approach to water resource management in the Sebou Basin. Effective governance requires the following key elements:

- **Stakeholder Engagement:**
 - Inclusivity: Ensuring the active participation of a diverse range of stakeholders, including local communities, government agencies, private sector actors, and NGOs. This broad engagement fosters a sense of ownership and collective responsibility, ensuring that water management strategies are comprehensive and consider the needs and perspectives of all parties involved.
 - Capacity Building: Investing in capacity-building programs to empower stakeholders with the knowledge and skills needed for effective water management. This includes training on sustainable practices, technological advancements, and adaptive management strategies.
 - Collaboration: Strengthening networks among stakeholders to facilitate knowledge sharing and collaborative problem-solving. Regular consultations and forums can help maintain an open dialogue and foster partnerships that enhance the implementation of water management plans.
- **Policy Enforcement:**

- Regulatory Compliance: Implementing and enforcing stringent regulations to ensure adherence to water quality standards and sustainable practices. Effective enforcement mechanisms, such as monitoring and penalties for non-compliance, are crucial for maintaining the integrity of water resources.
- Incentive Structures: Developing financial and non-financial incentives to encourage stakeholders to adopt sustainable water management practices. This can include subsidies for water-saving technologies, grants for research, and recognition programs for best practices.
- Transparency and Accountability: Ensuring transparency in decision-making processes and holding stakeholders accountable for their actions. This can be achieved through clear reporting mechanisms and public access to information on water management activities and outcomes.
- **Adaptive Strategies:**
 - Climate Resilience: Developing and implementing strategies that enhance the resilience of the Sebou Basin's water resources to the impacts of climate change. This includes building climate-resilient infrastructure, promoting community-based adaptation programs, and integrating climate projections into water management planning.
 - Innovative Technologies: Leveraging advanced technologies, such as digital tools for data collection and analysis, to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of water management. Technologies like Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and remote sensing can provide valuable insights into water resource dynamics and support informed decision-making.
 - Continuous Improvement: Establishing a framework for continuous monitoring and evaluation to assess the effectiveness of implemented strategies and make necessary adjustments. This iterative process allows for the dynamic adaptation of water management practices to emerging challenges and opportunities.
- **Key Challenges and Opportunities:**
 - Balancing Water Demand and Conservation: Addressing the challenge of increasing water demand due to population growth and industrial activities while promoting water conservation to sustain the basin's resources.
 - Pollution Control: Tackling pollution from agricultural runoff, industrial discharges, and urban wastewater through stricter regulations, sustainable agricultural practices, and advanced treatment technologies.
 - Resource Allocation: Ensuring equitable allocation of water resources among competing uses, such as agriculture, domestic supply, and industry, while maintaining ecological flows to support the basin's ecosystems.
 - Infrastructure Investment: Investing in the maintenance and modernization of aging water infrastructure to improve efficiency, reduce losses, and support sustainable water distribution.

By focusing on these key elements, the Sebou Basin can develop a robust and adaptive governance framework that ensures the sustainable management of its water resources, supporting both ecological health and socio-economic development.

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10 The Mediterranean region

10.1 System Characterization

The Mediterranean region is a heterogeneous landscape marked by a wide range of climatic conditions, geographic and hydrologic features. It is also characterized by complex socio-economic, cultural and political contexts. Current climatic variations and human pressures across the Mediterranean are increasing the frequency and severity of water scarcity, consequently affecting both human needs and ecosystem requirements of the second largest biodiversity hotspot in the world. The region faces substantial water management challenges to meet rising demand from population growth and water-dependent activities like intensive agriculture and mass tourism. Recent political and economic instability, combined with climate change and demographic shifts, have even driven some areas of the region into a water crisis. Economic activities characterized by over-exploitation and high seasonal water demand, generally peaking in summer, could further intensify future tensions and conflicts over water quantity and quality. Improving water governance is essential worldwide, but it has become even more vital in the Mediterranean to ensure effective, fair, and sustainable water management and to address ongoing environmental and socio-economic challenges.

Indirect drivers of changes such as the demography are crucial to understand the pressure on water resources in the Mediterranean basin. From 1990 to 2015, the total population of the Mediterranean region grew by more than 32%, rising from 463 million to over 590 million people by 2015 (Mediterranean Wetlands Observatory, 2018, data: Gridded Population of the World version 4). Significant disparities are evident, with the highest population growth occurring in the southern and eastern countries, while negative trends are observed in some countries of the Balkans. These trends are

reflective of projections that anticipate further population increases in the southern and eastern countries, surpassing half of the total Mediterranean population. Along with the expanding urban concentration and decreasing rural population, strong pressure on water is associated with urban development. Nearly one-third of the Mediterranean population resides in coastal areas, and more than 70% live in cities (UNEP/MAP and Plan bleu, 2020). Moreover, tourism further intensifies the demographic pressure in the Mediterranean region, which attracts around one-third of global tourism, making it the top tourist destination worldwide, with more than 400 million international tourist arrivals in 2019 (Eco-union 2021, UNWTO data).

Alongside demographic trends, water resources in the Mediterranean exhibit significant disparities due to their uneven distribution over time and spaces. In 2008, Ludwig et al. identified the ten largest rivers discharging into the Mediterranean Sea: the Rhône, Po, Drin-Buna, Nile, Neretva, Ebro, Tiber, Adige, Seyhan, and Ceyhan rivers. These rivers illustrate the imbalanced regional distribution of mean annual discharge into the Mediterranean Sea, with the northern part contributing 71%, while eastern countries contribute 12% and southern countries contribute 17% (Struglia et al., 2004). Besides the surface water resource, if most of the Mediterranean countries are able to fulfill the water demand by withdrawing freshwater, the southern and the eastern part of the Mediterranean show notable dependence on groundwater. Groundwater resources are the primary water source in several Mediterranean countries, including Libya, Palestine, and Israel (FAO 2003; Leduc et al. 2017). The overexploitation of renewable groundwater resources and the dependence on fossil water resources is a significant issue, particularly in Palestine and Jordan.

These disparities in water distribution, along with the demographic trends, further explains the critical water situation in the South and East. According to 2016 FAO data highlighted by MedECC in 2020, the distribution of population and renewable freshwater resources varies significantly across Mediterranean regions: the northern part holds 36% of the population and controls 72% to 74% of the renewable freshwater, while the eastern part represents 24% of the population and possesses 19.5% to 21% of the freshwater resources. In contrast, the southern Mediterranean region, with 40% of the population, has access to only 5% to 8.5% of the freshwater resources (MedECC, 2020, FAO data 2016).

As a result of these spatial disparities in water availability, 180 million people in the southern and eastern Mediterranean countries experience water scarcity (<1,000 m³ per capita per year), with an additional 80 million facing extreme water shortages (<500 m³ per capita per year).

Figure 32 Total renewable water resources per capita in the Mediterranean, 2020.

Figure 33 Level of water stress in the Mediterranean, 2020.

Regarding water management strategies, many Mediterranean countries rely extensively on dams and reservoirs for various water uses, especially irrigation. This is particularly true for southern Mediterranean countries, where approximately 70% of the water is

used for agriculture (Figure 33). The current percentage of irrigated land of the total cultivated area is 25% for the Mediterranean Basin and is currently increasing (MedECC, 2020). Over the past decades, hundreds of dams have been constructed around the Mediterranean Sea. While dams play a crucial role in water supply and hydropower, their implementation also carries numerous adverse impacts that must be carefully managed to ensure sustainable water stock and provisioning, as well as the conservation of wetlands and water-related ecosystems, which are already negatively impacted by agriculture (expansion and intensification) but also urban sprawl, climate change, natural systems modifications and invasive species. According to the Mediterranean Wetlands Observatory, half of the natural wetlands have disappeared since the 1970s, mainly due to their direct conversion into other land use classes, particularly crops, or to water shortages caused by the overexploitation of resources (both surface and underground), mostly for irrigation (Mediterranean Wetlands Observatory, 2018).

Figure 34 Water demand per sectoral use as percentage of total water demand, 2020.

The 2020 MedECC report states that climate change, interacting with other factors such as demographic and socio-economic developments, predominantly has adverse effects on the water cycle in the Mediterranean Basin. These effects include diminished runoff and groundwater replenishment, increased agricultural water demands, escalated conflicts among water users, and intensified risks of overexploitation and degradation. Recent monitoring improvement and deep studies have also documented a significant decline in streamflow across basins in the Mediterranean region in recent decades (Lutz et al., 2016; Suárez-Almiñana et al., 2017) and long-term reductions in flow trends are also recorded in many Mediterranean rivers. These changes are expected to be significantly more severe if global warming exceeds 2°C, with increased probability of drought years in the Mediterranean region, and flood risk, associated with extreme

rainfall events and damaging consequences that could be exacerbated by poorly planned stormwater management systems and land uses changes such as urban sprawl and sealed surfaces. The overall impacts of climate change and water-related issues are expected to be more severe on less-developed countries, which have limited capacity for adaptation and mitigation measures.

10.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Various stakeholders exert influence or have specific interests in water policies, governance and management across different spatial scales in the Mediterranean basin, encompassing the public sector, private sector, and civil society. In the public sector, there are notable differences between countries regarding administrative systems and the capacity of local governments. Generally, on one hand, European countries have shown significant changes since the implementation of the EU Water framework directive and the development of river basin management plans with stakeholders' involvement and public consultation. On the other hand, Arab countries have shifted from traditionally locally managed water uses under customary laws to highly centralized top-down system managing at the national level for large scale irrigation projects. Typically, water supply agencies share governance with other governmental institutions, such as ministries or agencies responsible for water, agriculture, irrigation, environmental management or health. Depending on the level of decentralization, municipalities and regional authorities manage local water supply and sanitation services. In many countries, public institutions frequently remain fragmented across ministries and agencies, leading to confusion due to overlapping policies and unclear roles and responsibilities (FAO, 2016).

At the international and regional scale, the international water agreements are designed within the unique context of Mediterranean cooperation, including UN policies, policies of the European Union, Arab League, EU-Africa and EU-Asia cooperation, North African Unions, Maghreb, and Mashriq. Hence, organizations such as the European Union, the Mediterranean Action Plan, Union for the Mediterranean, MedWet and the United Nations develops policies, supports capacity-building, and provides funding for projects focused on sustainable water use and conservation of water-related ecosystems. International stakeholders include bodies fostering regional cooperation among governments, river basin organizations, entities managing transboundary aquifers, multinational corporations, and international partners like UN agencies, donors, and scientific associations. NGOs and other civil society organizations also participate at various spatial scales, including international, regional, and national levels, as well as local NGOs focusing on specific sites or regions.

10.3 Governance Analysis

Effective governance is the cornerstone of sustainable water resource management, particularly in the Mediterranean region, where the challenges of climate change, disaster risk, and socio-economic disparities are pronounced. This section delves into the intricate governance structures and policies that shape water resource management, emphasizing the necessity for cohesive, cross-sectoral approaches that integrate climate adaptation, disaster risk reduction, and sustainable development.

10.3.1 Policy and regulatory framework

It is crucial to develop a thorough inventory of international, regional, and national policies related to water resource management, disaster risk reduction, and climate change adaptation and mitigation for the Mediterranean countries. This inventory will lay the groundwork for proposing a suitable policy framework that integrates security, climate change adaptation, and water management issues. Subsequently, specific recommendations can be formulated to streamline policies at the UN, EU, regional and national levels based on this inventory. Here is a first list of relevant international and regional water policy frameworks:

EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) (WFD) which was established for the sustainable use of freshwater resources and the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters and groundwater, ensuring to achieve good ecological (qualitative and quantitative) status of all water bodies, through the implementation of river basin management plans, monitoring and reporting, public participation.

The EU Bathing Water Directive (EU BWD, 2006) which sets standards aimed at enhancing the quality of bathing waters and safeguarding public health. The monitoring of bathing water, guided by the EU Directive EU 76/160/EEC, represents a notable achievement for Mediterranean countries, whether they are member states or non-member states as this focus on bathing water quality is crucial for sustaining tourism.

The UNEP/MAP Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development 2016-2025 (MSSD), adopted by all Mediterranean countries at the 19th Meeting of the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, promote sustainable water management practices across the Mediterranean region, with for example the implementation of national water-related action plans

The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015-2030) highlights the interconnectedness of water management and disaster risk reduction, emphasizing the need to enhance resilience against water-related hazards through integrated and participatory strategies.

The UN Sustainable Development Goal 6 which aims to "ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all." encompassing targets related to water quality, water use efficiency, integrated water resources management, water-related ecosystems, and sanitation services.

The UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) which aims to prevent and reverse land degradation in affected areas, restore degraded land, and promote sustainable land management practices. It faces challenges such as tackling water scarcity and mitigating desertification, promoting integrated approach, drought resilience and community engagement.

In the Southern and Eastern regions, significant progress has been achieved over the past two decades regarding the design of water governance policies and their implementation and enforcement. However, there is still a critical need to establish more sustainable approaches at local, national, and transboundary levels with appropriate planning and management considering climate change impacts. Although many Mediterranean countries have already established national water strategies, the regulatory frameworks

for water quantity and quality still vary significantly both between and within these countries.

10.3.2 Decision-making structure and process

The states are the legislator and regulator of natural resource use and each country in the region has institutions responsible for the management of water resources. There is often a separation between agencies dedicated to biodiversity conservation, forestry, and agriculture, and those managing water and waste management. However, strategies and policies for water management and climate change adaptation are strongly interconnected with all other sectors (e.g., the Water-Energy and Food Nexus). Interestingly, water governance and conflicts related to water in the Mediterranean region seem to be influenced more by political, economic, and social factors rather than climate-related variables or water resources availability (MedECC, 2020). Countries with a long history of water management and stability tend to prioritize sustainability and environmental issues, unlike countries in earlier stages of management that focus more on increasing water supply. Moreover, administrative, monitoring, and enforcement capacities differ greatly, with several countries still facing challenges such as fragmented responsibilities among authorities, inadequate planning capacities, ineffective operational strategies, and weak enforcement of policies and laws. Regarding strategies and management plans, national frameworks should be guided by internationally recognized Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) principles and practices, and adaptation measures, emphasizing management at appropriate local scales such as catchments, basins, and sub-basins. Robust science-policy interface and knowledge-exchange processes should consider the region's diversity. It is crucial to emphasize inclusive governance involving civil society, address differences between EU and non-EU regulations, and tackle the absence of cross-sectoral policies needed to operationalize integrated resource management. Efforts should be made at different scales for example to promote decentralization to the most appropriate level or collaboration and coordination at transboundary and sub-regional level to ensure peaceful cooperation.

10.3.3 Analysis

The governance of water resources in the Mediterranean region faces several challenges that are deeply rooted in the political, economic, and social contexts of the countries involved. While some countries have advanced governance systems that prioritize sustainability and environmental protection, others are still in the early stages of development, focusing more on increasing water supply rather than on sustainable management.

Key issues include:

1. **Fragmented Responsibilities and Coordination:** Governance in many Mediterranean countries is characterized by fragmented responsibilities among various authorities, leading to inefficiencies in water management. The separation between agencies responsible for different aspects of natural resource management often results in a lack of cohesive strategies, undermining efforts to implement integrated water resource management.
2. **Regulatory Disparities:** There is significant variability in the regulatory frameworks governing water quantity and quality across the region. These disparities not only

- exist between different countries but also within them, particularly between urban and rural areas. This inconsistency hampers the development of uniform standards and practices necessary for effective transboundary water management.
3. Administrative and Enforcement Capacity: The capacity for administration, monitoring, and enforcement of water management policies varies widely among Mediterranean countries. Some nations struggle with inadequate planning capacities, ineffective operational strategies, and weak enforcement mechanisms, which exacerbate the challenges of managing water resources sustainably.
 4. Impact of Political and Socio-Economic Factors: Water governance in the region is influenced not only by environmental conditions but also by political and socio-economic factors. Political instability, economic pressures, and social inequalities can all undermine effective water management, leading to conflicts and unsustainable practices.
 5. Climate Change and Disaster Risk Reduction: The region's vulnerability to climate change and water-related disasters highlights the need for governance systems that are adaptable and resilient. However, the integration of climate adaptation and disaster risk reduction into water management policies is still lacking in many countries, leaving them ill-prepared to cope with the increasing frequency and severity of water-related hazards.
 6. Opportunities for Improvement: Despite these challenges, there are opportunities to enhance water governance in the Mediterranean. These include strengthening the science-policy interface, promoting knowledge exchange, and fostering collaboration at local, national, and transboundary levels. Decentralization of governance to the most appropriate levels, coupled with enhanced coordination at the sub-regional level, can also contribute to more effective and sustainable water management.

In conclusion, while significant progress has been made in some areas, the governance of water resources in the Mediterranean region requires continued efforts to address the existing challenges. By fostering a more integrated, inclusive, and resilient approach to water management, Mediterranean countries can better navigate the complexities of climate change, disaster risk, and socio-economic development.

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